

D4.4

Value of Data Sharing on SSH

ZSI

D4.4

Value of Data Sharing on SSH

Revision **v1.0**

Work package	WP4
Task	Task 4.4
Due date	31-12-2025
Submission date	19-12-2025
Deliverable lead	ZSI
Version	v1.0
Authors	Daniela Fuchs, Margit Hofer (ZSI); literature review supported by Eduardo Vyhmeister (UCC) and Agnieszka Adzierbunowicz (PSNC)
Reviewers	Ibraheem Al-Dhamari (UNIKO), Chaido Porlou (CERTH) and Maria Makrynioti (CERTH)

Abstract

Task 4.4 conducted a foresight process on impacts of data sharing that are not only monetary. Thus, D4.4 provides a description of the DATAMITE foresight process, as well as activities related to gender equality. Moreover, it offers a tool for reflection on non-monetary impacts of data sharing in practice.

Keywords

non-monetary impacts, responsible innovation, foresight, visioning, reflection, digital data.

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
V0.1	30-10-2025	Main structure	Daniela Fuchs (ZSI), Margit Hofer (ZSI)
V0.2	11-11-2025	Draft version	Daniela Fuchs (ZSI), Margit HoferZSI
V0.3	19-11-2025	Review	Ibraheem Al-Dhamari (UniKo), Chaido Porlou (CERTH) and Maria Makrynioti (CERTH)
V1.0	17-12-2025	Final	Santiago Cáceres (ITI)

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are provided by the DATAMITE project's consortium under EC grant agreement **101092989** and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Copyright notice

© DATAMITE 2023-2025

Project co-funded by the European Commission in the Horizon Europe Programme

Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	3
1.1 Context, Deliverable Purpose and Scope	3
1.2 Document Structure	4
2 Capturing the full value of Data Sharing: Beyond Monetisation	7
2.1 DATAMITE's Perspective.....	8
2.2 Embedding and Research Focus.....	9
3 The DATAMITE Methodology of Social Sciences and Humanities for Data Sharing and its Future Perspective	10
3.1 Foresight Approach and Methodological Rationale	10
3.2 Applied Methods	12
3.2.1 Exploring and Mapping the Initial SSH Framework.....	13
3.2.2 Investigating and Capturing Real-world Practices: Refined SSH Framework	14
3.2.3 Anticipating by Co-developing Desirable Futures and Feasible Actions: Foresight and validated SSH framework.....	14
4 Literature-Based Insights: Exploring and Mapping Non-Monetary Impacts of Data Sharing	17
4.1 Overview of the Literature Corpus	17
4.2 General Assumptions and Insights	17
4.3 Impact Dimensions.....	20
4.4 Conclusions from Literature-based Research.....	27
5 Empirical Insights from Pilots: Investigating, Capturing and Validating against Real-world Practices	30
5.1 Semi-structured Interviews.....	30
5.1.1 Organisational Shifts in Practice: How do Practices Change within Organisations due to the (planned) Introduction of Data Sharing?	30

5.1.2	Shifting Mindsets	31
5.1.3	Shifting Workflows	33
5.1.4	Shifting Resources	34
5.1.5	Shifting Collaborations	34
5.1.6	Conclusions on Shifting Practices of Organizations due to Data Sharing	35
5.2	Perceived Impact of Data Sharing: Assessment of Expected Impacts	36
5.2.1	Perceived Risks	37
5.3	Future Visions	39
5.3.1	Cross-Pilot Synthesis	40
5.4	Recommendation and Likelihood of Happening	44
5.4.1	Sectoral Recommendations for Data Sharing	44
5.4.2	Cross-Pilot Comparison	48
5.4.3	Likelihood of Recommendations	49
5.4.4	Overall Learning and Empirical Insights from Recommendations	51
6	Reflection and Limitations	53
7	The Future of Data Sharing Beyond Economic Value	55
7.1	Cross-section Synthesis	55
7.2	Meta-level Reflection	56
7.3	Recommendations	57
7.3.1	Policy Recommendations	57
7.3.2	Business Recommendations	58
7.4	Further Forward-Looking Considerations	59
8	An Output for Practice: Enhancing Responsible Innovation through Reflection.....	61
8.1	Reflection Tool (DATAreflect)	61
8.2	Reflection on the Issue of Gender Equality and Bias Awareness	62
8.2.1	Gender Equality and Bias Awareness Activity as part of the CM in Bilbao (M28)	66
9	Ethics, Consents and Use of AI	68

10	References	69
	Annex A: Methods in Detail	77
	Explorative Stakeholder Workshop (M6)	77
	Systematic Literature Review.....	77
	Corpus of Literature	77
	Literature Analysis.....	79
	Semi-structured interviews with Pilot partners (M12-24)	80
	Explorative Poll of Pilot Partners (M23)	81
	Backcasting, Recommendations and Feasibility Assessment (M23)	83
	Annex B: Literature Basis - What are Impacts of Data Sharing in General and in Different Sectors?	85
	General Overview on the Review	86
	Areas	87
	Dimensions.....	89
	Nature of Data	91
	Process and Modes of Sharing Data	92
	Target Groups of Papers and Users	93
	Grid Charts/ Column Analysis	94
	Research Gaps and Conclusions according to Impact Dimensions	100
	Assumptions and Impacts in Detail.....	120
	Assumptions on Data Sharing	120
	(Expected) Benefits in Detail.....	124
	Risks and Challenges in Detail	134
	The Issue of Trust	147
	Conclusions of the Chapter.....	149
	Annex C: In-depth Recommendations Analysis of Pilots per Topics	152
	Urban Services Sector (GIDI)	152
	Energy Sector (HEDNO and E-REDES).....	153

Agriculture Sector (PSNC / eDWIN) 156

Telecommunications Sector (OTE Group)..... 158

Meteorology Sector (CINECA / MISTRAL) 160

Annex D: Interview Questionnaire 163

Annex E: Visions of Pilot Partners 165

Annex F: Thematic Comparison Matrix 179

Annex G: Preliminary Version of the DATAMITE Reflection Tool ('DATAreflect')..... 188

List of Figures

Figure 1: Overview of methodology applied in the DATAMITE study	13
Figure 2: Expected benefits of data sharing in different dimensions for pilot partners from ‘no benefit’ to ‘very high’ benefits	36
Figure 3: Expected risks of data sharing in different dimensions for pilot partners from ‘no risks’ to ‘very high’ risks	38
Figure 4: Average estimated likelihood of recommendations to be implemented.	50
Figure 5: Cross-analysis sectors and dimensions	95
Figure 6: Benefits in relation to dimensions	97
Figure 7: Risks and challenges in relation to dimensions	98
Figure 8: Benefits in relation to sectors	99
Figure 9: Risks and challenges in relation to sectors	100

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of Methodologies, Purpose and Sample Size	15
Table 2: Identified topics per impact dimension	26
Table 3: Keywords for queries	79
Table 4: Poll on impacts of data sharing in different dimensions for pilot partners	83
Table 5: Number of papers according to sectors	89
Table 6: Number of papers per impact dimension	91
Table 7: Number of papers per nature of data (if mentioned)	92
Table 8: Number of papers per target group	93
Table 9: Number of papers mentioning data user groups	93
Table 10: Number of papers according to expected benefits	126
Table 11: Number of papers according to risks and challenges	135

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DoA	Description of Action
WP	Work Package
SSH	Social sciences and humanities
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
OGD	Open Government Data
FAIR	Fair Principles (F indability, A ccessibility, I nteroperability, and R euse of data)
DIH	Data Innovation Hubs

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D4.4) presents the results of Task 4.4 of the DATAMITE project. It investigates the non-monetary impacts of data sharing and develops an anticipatory, foresight-driven understanding of how data sharing can generate social, ethical, cultural, and organisational value beyond purely economic considerations. Positioned within Work Package 4, the task strategically complements technical and business-oriented activities by emphasising responsible innovation and ethical governance in designing future data ecosystems.

The document provides (1) a conceptual model of the value of data sharing beyond monetisation, (2) results from an extensive mixed-methods foresight methodology, (3) empirical insights from six European pilot sectors, (4) cross-sector visions of future data sharing, and (5) recommendations for responsible, socially beneficial data ecosystems. Moreover, it provides a practical reflection tool aimed at organisations implementing data-sharing strategies.

Understanding Data Sharing Beyond Monetary Value

Data sharing is a foundational element of Europe's digital transition, supporting the development of AI, transparency, business efficiency, and scientific collaboration. However, the assumption that sharing more data automatically creates more value is critically challenged.

SSH literature and empirical insights demonstrate that data sharing:

- is not neutral, but shaped by historical, political, and social contexts;
- is a socio-technical process, dependent on organisational culture, trust, and governance.
- creates context-dependent value, which does not arise automatically;
- requires the management of ethical, privacy, and power-related risks;

These findings highlight that responsible data sharing requires balancing openness, privacy, ethics, and public interest. In this sense, the approach aligns with the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework.

Foresight Methodology and Research Focus

The insights of this work are based on a multi-stage foresight process, structured to explore possible futures and translate long-term expectations into actionable insights. This process integrated three strands of research: (1) the literature perspective, mapping non-monetary

impacts (environmental, ethical, policy, cultural, societal, organizational, etc.); (2) the perspective on organizational change, which investigated how data sharing reshapes workflows, cultures, competencies, and collaboration structures; and (3) the perspective of vision and foresight to develop desired future scenarios and identifying steps to achieve them.

Methodologically, the process integrated a systematic literature review, semi-structured interviews and polls with pilot partners, and a visioning & back-casting workshop aimed at sector-related recommendations for responsible data sharing. This triangulation of methods produced a validated SSH framework capturing how non-monetary impacts emerge and evolve in organisational settings.

Recognising the need for practical support, D4.4 also introduces a structured reflection tool that enables organisations to assess non-monetary impacts, anticipate risks, and integrate ethical and social considerations into their data-sharing strategies.

Thus, the DATAMITE foresight process shows that the future of data sharing in Europe will also **depend on trust, responsible governance, data quality, and cross-sector collaboration** rather than technology and monetisation only. Non-monetary impacts are central for sustainable and socially beneficial data ecosystems, ensuring a fair distribution of benefits and risks long-term. If this potential is to be realised, organisations must invest not only in technology but also in their organisational culture, competencies, ethics, and long-term strategic alignment.

Task 4.4 offers both a theoretical framework and a practical tool to support this transition, contributing to a more human-centred, trustworthy, and responsible European data economy.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context, Deliverable Purpose and Scope

DATAMITE (“Data Monetization, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange”) is a project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe programme and coordinated by the ITI - Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve DATA Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetization potential at two levels. At internal level, users will have tools to improve quality management of their data, the adherence to FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of data¹), and will be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.

At external level, keeping users in control of their data will provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE’s solutions will function as a catalyst to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.

Furthermore, task 4.4 of the DATAMITE project focused on aspects related to data sharing beyond economic value and sought to bring dimensions that are not only monetary into the discussion on data sharing. Thus, it provided a deeper and forward-looking understanding of how data sharing can contribute positively to different aspects of social sciences and humanities (SSH) in a responsible, regenerative and secure way, maximising benefits, without increasing societal risks or inequalities and environmental damages. Task 4.4 provided an anticipatory foresight study on the impact of data sharing regarding (i) structured anticipation and/or projections of long-

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> [28.11.2025]

term social, economic, and technological developments (drivers, trends), (ii) strategic visioning, and (iii) explicit recognition and explication of the implications for present day decisions and usage. In addition, Task 4.4 will combine these insights by a methodological approach of Responsible Research and Innovation, reaching out to wider contexts of SSH (i.e., ethics, gender, knowledge sharing, government).

As part of WP4 (Beyond Sharing. A Business and Quality Approach to Foster the European Data Economy) and together with Task 4.1. (Strategies to improve data monetization in EU Companies), Task 4.4 provides strategic orientation for pilot partners and other interested organizations for designing data sharing practices. While other tasks of WP4 aim at operationalizing monetization (Task 4.2 - Definition of KPIs for a fair valuation of datasets and mechanisms for their computation, Task 4.3 - Data as an economic perspective. Business cases & models for data sharing platform) or provide pilot partners with an overview on respective regulations and legislations (T4.5 - Legal & ethical aspects for data sharing and trading), Task 4.4 aims at expanding reflection beyond technical possibilities and economic purposes by addressing broader impacts of data sharing. To do so, it accompanied the development of the DATAMITE infrastructure and provided spaces for reflection right from the beginning. Therefore, it contributes to designing data sharing practices in a more responsible way.

This document D4.4. summarizes the anticipatory foresight study on non-monetary impacts step-by-step (explorative workshop, literature review, visions of pilot partners, interviews with pilot partners, visioning workshop). In addition, Task 4.4 acknowledged the importance of practical reflections on impacts of data sharing beyond monetization and developed a reflection tool for responsible data sharing in practice (Annex G). Thus, D4.4 addresses all those interested to reflect on non-monetary impacts of data sharing in more detail, in particular research, policy makers and businesses.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Executive Summary:** A summary of the contents and main findings are provided.
- **Section 1 Introduction** provides the deliverable's general context, dependencies, and structure.

- **Section 2 Capturing the full value of Data Sharing: Beyond Monetization** provides an overview of the topic of data (sharing) from a social science perspective and why non-monetary impacts of data sharing should be reflected.
- **Section 3 The DATAMITE Methodology of Social Sciences and Humanities for Data Sharing and its Future Perspective** outlines the research questions and the applied methods of the DATAMITE foresight process.
- **Section 4 Literature-Based Insights. Exploring and mapping Non-Monetary Impacts of Data Sharing** provides a short version of the findings of the literature review.
- **Section 5 Empirical Insights from Pilots: Investigating Capturing and Validating against real-world practices** contains indications of organisational shifts in practices, as well as assessments of expected impacts, visions and recommendations to implement data sharing in pilot sectors.
- **Section 6 Reflection and Limitation** reflects on the limitations of the DATAMITE approach
- **Section 7 The Future of Data Sharing beyond Economic Value** provides conclusions and recommendations regarding non-monetary impacts of data sharing.
- **Section 8 An output for Practice: Enhancing Responsible Innovation through Reflection** outlines activities for enhancing reflection on non-monetary impacts, as well as responsible innovation more broadly, within the DATAMITE project. It introduces the Reflection Tool and awareness-raising activities regarding gender equality and bias.
- **Section 9 References** lists the references of the deliverable.

Given the extensive volume of data collected, these sections present only **the most relevant findings**. To ensure that valuable details and in-depth analyses are retained, **the comprehensive results have been included in the Annex**. Where appropriate, chapters refer readers to the corresponding Annex sections for further information and extended discussion.

Annex A: Methods in Detail

Annex B: Literature Basis

Annex C: In-depth Recommendations Analysis of Pilots per Topics

Annex D: Interview Questionnaire

Annex E: Visions of Pilot Partners

Annex F: Thematic Comparison Matrix

Annex G: Preliminary Version of the DATAMITE Reflection Tool ('DATAreflect')

2 Capturing the full value of Data Sharing: Beyond Monetisation

Data sharing has emerged as a defining issue across scientific, public, and business domains in Europe. It is widely viewed as a cornerstone of the digital transition, with expectations of improved transparency, efficiency, and innovation potential. European industries and public institutions alike recognise that the capacity to share, reuse, and integrate data will determine competitiveness and resilience in the coming decade.

The **growing importance of big data, machine learning, and artificial intelligence** (AI) reinforces this trend. The performance of AI systems depends critically on the quantity and quality of data available (Pawelke, Fetic, and Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2020). Sharing high-quality data has therefore become a **prerequisite for progress in AI**, a process that turns technological promises into self-fulfilling prophecies (Bareis and Katzenbach, 2022). In this sense, data sharing represents more than a technical enabler; it is a structural force shaping the future of innovation.

However, the path toward realizing this potential remains **contested**. Ethical, legal, and societal challenges persist, from privacy protection and data sovereignty to fairness, ownership, and accountability. Managing these risks has proven difficult for individuals, organizations, and policymakers alike. As a result, the design and governance of Europe's data-driven society, as envisioned by the European Commission, are shaped as much by social and political factors as by technical progress.

It is therefore crucial to recognize that **data is not a neutral resource**. Its meaning and use depend on social, institutional, and political contexts. Different conceptualizations of data, as a technical artifact, as a commodity, or as a societal common, produce different models of sharing, control, and value creation (Prainsack, 2019; Pawelke, Fetic, and Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2020). This **diversity of perspectives** also shapes how data sovereignty, privacy, intellectual property, and investment are understood in practice.

Social science research has long emphasised the **political quality of data sharing** (Prainsack and Leonelli, 2018). The underlying assumption that more openness automatically leads to more innovation, competition, or participation is misleading:

“Access to data alone does not automatically bring social benefits. Greater availability of data does not automatically mean more competition, more innovation or greater social participation. Better access to data can sometimes even lead to the consolidation or further concentration of power” [translated by author].² (Pawelke, Fetic, and Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2020, p. 20)

Consequently, the question of how to share data is not merely technical, it is fundamentally socio-political. It determines who benefits, who bears risks, and whose values shape the data economy.

2.1 DATAMITE’s Perspective

The DATAMITE project brings this complex question into concrete practice. It explores data sharing as a *social and organisational phenomenon* embedded in networks of stakeholders, institutions, and values. Rather than treating it as a purely technical procedure, DATAMITE views **data sharing as a negotiated practice**, dynamic, context-specific, and continuously shaped through human interaction.

This perspective allows for a shift from techno-centric narratives to more comprehensive understandings of value. Instead of seeing data merely as an informational asset, DATAMITE conceptualises value as a process, one that unfolds collaboratively, transparently, and responsibly.

By adopting this lens, DATAMITE contributes to a growing body of research that challenges the narrow economic interpretation of “value” dominant in innovation policy. As Harmon, Caulfield

² Original: *“Der Zugang zu Daten allein bringt nicht ohne Weiteres einen gesellschaftlichen Nutzen. Eine größere Verfügbarkeit an Daten bedeutet nicht automatisch mehr Wettbewerb, mehr Innovation oder größere gesellschaftliche Teilhabe. Der bessere Zugang zu Daten kann mitunter sogar zur Konsolidierung oder weiteren Konzentration von (ökonomischer) Macht führen (Heumann, 2019)“* (Pawelke, Fetic, and Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2020)

and Joly (2012) argue, the prevailing commercialization mandate often limits value measurement to metrics such as patents, licenses, or material transfer agreements. DATAMITE extends this view by explicitly considering non-monetary impacts, such as social trust, ethical alignment, environmental sustainability, and public benefit.

2.2 Embedding and Research Focus

This research is situated within the **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework**, which promotes anticipation, inclusivity, and reflection throughout research and innovation processes (Owen, Macnaghten and Stilgoe, 2012; von Schomberg, 2013; Owen, Von Schomberg and Macnaghten, 2021). The task aims to identify and assess non-monetary impacts of data sharing, benefits and risks that extend beyond economic rationales, and to integrate these reflections into practical strategies for responsible data governance.

It provides a structured space for examining the **“bigger picture” of data sharing** by bridging critical data studies and applied innovation research. It acknowledges that while the policy and business discourse is often driven by economic and technological expectations, sustainable progress also requires attention to other dimensions such as ethics, culture, and social framework.

The foresight approach promotes early reflection on such impacts through continuous stakeholder engagement, particularly with the six DATAMITE pilot partners. It highlights how non-monetary impacts are context-specific and often overlooked, even though they strongly influence trust, adoption, and long-term viability of data-driven solutions.

Thus, the research methods were selected accordingly to ensure that each analytical strand could be addressed with appropriate depth, triangulation, and empirical grounding. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, combining qualitative and quantitative techniques to capture both the conceptual and practical dimensions of non-monetary data-sharing impacts.

3 The DATAMITE Methodology of Social Sciences and Humanities for Data Sharing and its Future Perspective

3.1 Foresight Approach and Methodological Rationale

Foresight refers to structured approaches that explore possible, probable, and preferable futures to inform strategic decisions in the present (Miles, 2008; Popper, 2008). Foresight methods are particularly well-suited for addressing “wicked problems” in complex socio-technical systems, where outcomes are uncertain, path-dependent, and co-shaped by a wide range of actors. The European Commission understands foresight as a process that uses collective intelligence in a structured and systematic way to **shape a desirable future** by exploring possible future developments.³ Foresight studies use manifold methods to explore future developments, ranging from Horizon Scanning, Futures Surveys (e.g. Delphi surveys or expert interviews), Scenario Building, to Roadmapping, or Visioning.⁴

The methodological design is based on foresight principles, chosen deliberately to address the complex and cross-cutting nature of non-monetary impacts of data sharing. Traditional evaluation or impact-assessment approaches are often limited to quantifiable indicators or short-term outcomes. In contrast, foresight enables an anticipatory and integrative perspective, combining empirical evidence with participatory reflection to explore how technological, organisational, and societal factors evolve together.

Foresight methods are particularly suited to topics such as data sharing, where **impacts are systemic, context-dependent, and uncertain**. They allow for identifying emerging trends and weak signals, capturing stakeholder perspectives, and building shared understanding of possible futures. Within DATAMITE, this approach ensured that the analysis did not remain theoretical but

³ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/strategic-foresight_en [18.12.2024]

⁴ <https://www.isi.fraunhofer.de/en/competence-center/foresight.html> [18.12.2024]

linked research insights with practice, translating findings into strategic guidance for responsible data governance.

The anticipatory foresight study aimed to explore the non-monetary impacts of data sharing and to understand how these impacts manifest across different sectors represented in the DATAMITE pilots. The overarching research question guiding this work was:

What are the perspectives and visions for data sharing in different (pilot) sectors, and how are these visions coming into practice?

This overarching question was divided into three analytical strands:

Literature perspective

- What non-monetary impacts (benefits and risks) of data sharing are identified in the scientific literature, particularly from the social sciences and humanities?
- What overarching and sector-specific impact dimensions emerge across different domains relevant to DATAMITE (telecommunication, energy, urban services, weather, agriculture)?

Organizational change perspective

- How do organisational practices and mindsets evolve in response to data sharing initiatives?
- Which weak signals of change can be observed across pilots?

Vision and foresight perspective

- How are non-monetary benefits envisioned in different sectors?
- What actions are needed to make these visions feasible in practice?

Through its combination of analytical rigour and participatory engagement, the DATAMITE foresight process bridged research and practice, translating diverse stakeholder perspectives into actionable policy and innovation insights. The resulting framework strengthens the evidence base for anticipating social, ethical, and organisational dimensions of data sharing, supporting the European Commission's ambition for a human-centred and trustworthy data economy.

The methodological combination, systematic review, interviews, surveys, and visioning, reflects this logic of progressive knowledge integration by (a) **exploring and mapping existing knowledge** and concepts; (b) **investigating and capturing real-world practices and experiences** via interviews and polls and finally (c) **anticipating by co-developing desirable futures** and feasible actions through visioning and backcasting.

This sequence created a robust evidence base for assessing non-monetary impacts and deriving actionable recommendations. It also ensured co-creation with stakeholders, a key requirement of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), and aligned the work with the European Commission's emphasis on anticipatory governance and social responsibility in data-driven innovation. Together, these methodological components form a coherent framework linking evidence, perception, and projection. The triangulation of sources ensured that the study not only maps existing knowledge but also anticipates future transformations in the European data-sharing landscape, thereby grounding DATAMITE's recommendations in both scientific insight and practical foresight.

3.2 Applied Methods

THIS CHAPTER SUMMARIZES THE METHODS APPLIED IN THE FORESIGHT PROCESS. FOR A DETAILED DESCRIPTION SEE ANNEX A.

This study combined several complementary qualitative and analytical methods. Each method addressed different dimensions of the research questions and ensured a balanced integration of literature-based, stakeholder-driven, and future-oriented perspectives.

The figure illustrates the multi-stage foresight design combining literature review, stakeholder interviews, pilot surveys, and visioning/ backcasting workshops. Each stage builds on the previous one to progressively integrate evidence, stakeholder insights, and future-oriented reflection.

Figure 1: Overview of methodology applied in the DATAMITE study

3.2.1 Exploring and Mapping the Initial SSH Framework

3.2.1.1 Explorative Stakeholder Workshop (Athens)

The first workshop took place early in the project to explore perceptions, expectations, and challenges related to data sharing across sectors. Approximately 50 participants included representatives from pilot partners, researchers, and data governance experts. The session aimed to identify initial assumptions about the value and risks of data sharing and to co-develop a preliminary set of impact dimensions. The outcomes of this workshop informed the initial conceptual framework for the literature review and guided the formulation of interview questions.

3.2.1.2 Systematic Literature Review and Analysis

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify non-monetary impacts of data sharing, focusing on recent publications from the social sciences, humanities, and innovation research. The review followed structured search protocols across major academic databases and covered literature published between 2016 and 2025. Studies were coded according to impact dimensions such as ethical, environmental, organisational, societal, and policy-related effects. From an initial pool of over 253 records, 40 studies were selected based on methodological rigour and relevance. The analysis resulted in an integrated overview of cross-sectoral trends and sector-specific insights, forming the analytical foundation for subsequent empirical work.

3.2.2 Investigating and Capturing Real-world Practices: Refined SSH Framework

3.2.2.1 Semi-Structured Interviews

Six semi-structured interviews were carried out with representatives from all DATAMITE pilot partners in 5 areas and selected external stakeholders between August 2024 and December 2024. The purpose was to explore how organizations are adapting to data sharing practices, in terms of the identified key dimensions. Questions focused on perceived opportunities, barriers, and lessons learned from implementation processes, enriched the identified key dimensions and validated the findings from literature. The interviews were coded with MaxQDA and provided qualitative depth to the foresight analysis, as well as revealing “weak signals” codes of change, which were later validated in two workshops. Key patterns and quotes were synthesized into thematic categories reflecting evolving practices and mindsets.

3.2.2.2 Explorative Poll of Pilots

An online poll was conducted among all six pilot partners to quantify perceptions of data sharing benefits and risks and to validate insights from the interviews. The poll targeted representatives from the six DATAMITE pilots. It captured participants’ estimations of the relative importance of non-monetary impact dimensions and their relevance for the pilot contexts. The resulting dataset offered a cross-sectional snapshot of attitudes toward responsible and sustainable data sharing within DATAMITE.

3.2.3 Anticipating by Co-developing Desirable Futures and Feasible Actions: Foresight and validated SSH framework

3.2.3.1 Visioning and Backcasting Workshop

The foresight process culminated in a joint visioning and backcasting workshop held in December during a consortium meeting in Aachen with pilot partners and domain experts. The objective was to articulate preferred future scenarios for responsible data sharing and to identify the conditions and actions required to achieve them (formulated through 49 concrete recommendations). Using structured facilitation, participants co-developed sectoral visions and

ranked the feasibility of proposed actions (using a Likert scale (0–6)). The outputs included a consolidated set of long-term goals, near-term recommendations, and cross-sectoral insights on enabling environments for responsible data ecosystems. The assessment of implementation likelihood highlighted both robust areas and existing gaps, offering clear indications of where additional support and capacity-building are required across the different dimensions.

<i>Method</i>	<i>Purpose</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
Exploring and Mapping		
Stakeholder workshop	explore perceptions, expectations, and challenges	50
Literature Review	to identify non-monetary impacts of data sharing,	253 to 40
Investigating and Capturing real-life		
Interviews	to explore how organizations are adapting to data sharing practices	6
Poll	to quantify perceptions of data sharing benefits and risks and to validate insights from the interviews	66 single entries
Anticipating by Co-development		
Vision development	to articulate preferred future scenarios for responsible data sharing	5 sectorial visions by 6 pilot partners
Recommendations incl. rating	and to identify the conditions and actions required	49 recommendations 42 ratings

Table 1: Overview of Methodologies, Purpose and Sample Size

3.2.3.2 Contextual Validity

To ensure the robustness and credibility of findings, the anticipatory foresight study applied a systematic process of data validation and triangulation across all methodological components. Insights derived from the systematic literature review were first used to develop the initial analytical framework and interview guides, defining key impact dimensions and hypotheses. The semi-structured interviews then served to validate and refine these dimensions through real-world

perspectives from the DATAMITE pilot partners. While this sample is small, it represents the entirety of the project's key decision-makers, thus validating it for this specific consortium. Emerging patterns and “weak signals” identified in the interviews were subsequently tested and quantified through the online pilot poll, which provided comparative data across sectors. Finally, the visioning and backcasting workshop functioned as an integrative validation stage, where stakeholders collectively reflected on, confirmed, or adjusted the earlier findings and co-developed actionable recommendations. This iterative process ensured consistency and alignment between conceptual, empirical, and participatory insights, strengthening both the analytical validity and practical relevance of the results.

A detailed description of each methodology used can be found in Annex A.

4 Literature-Based Insights: Exploring and Mapping Non-Monetary Impacts of Data Sharing

THIS CHAPTER PROVIDES AN ANALYTICAL SYNTHESIS OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW.

FOR THE DETAILED METHOD SEE ANNEX A; FOR THE COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE LITERATURE SEE ANNEX B.

4.1 Overview of the Literature Corpus

Our literature review focused on literature from social science and humanities between 2013-2025. The search query was constructed via PICOC methodology⁵ and applied to Google Scholar and SCOPUS (between 2013 and 2025), covering dimensions (e.g., environmental, scientific, societal, etc.) as well as sectors (e.g., urban, manufacturing, banking, energy, weather, agriculture, telecommunication, etc.). From the initial 253 records, a core team selected 40 studies based on methodological rigor and relevance. Subsequently, these studies were analysed quantitatively and qualitatively analysed to combine deductive and inductive approaches for more comprehensive insights.

4.2 General Assumptions and Insights

A qualitative analysis of the literature (Annex B: Assumptions and Impacts in Detail) revealed several assumptions that frequently underlie conceptions of data sharing that need to be scrutinized. These assumptions are: (a) the inherent interconnectedness of data sharing, openness and goodness; (b) data neutrality (including issues of bias and discrimination); (c) the relational character of data sharing; and (d) the equivalence of data sharing and value creation.

⁵ <https://cebma.org/resources/frequently-asked-questions/what-is-a-picoc> [19.11.2025]

As they “set the stage” for discussion on the impacts of data sharing, they will be shortly outlined here.

Data sharing equals openness equals ‘good’

Rather than being self-evident, ‘openness’ exercises a strongly normative stance (Prainsack and Leonelli, 2018). Moreover, the automatic equation of ‘data sharing’ and ‘openness’ need to be scrutinized as issues of openness may either not be of priority (e.g., replication crisis in environmental health), or not to be solved by data sharing (Hicks, 2023). Although ‘openness’ is omnipresent as a (political) requirement in the context of data (sharing), it does not resolve the tension between transparency and privacy as it can obscure what is withheld or absent and risks people’s right to control what others know about them (Prainsack, 2021). Moreover, shifts in power concentration can move power and responsibility away from democratically legitimized actors towards private institutions only accountable to their shareholders (Prainsack, 2021).

Data is neutral

Social science literature clearly points out that data is shaped by historical and social contexts, transferring conditions of their generation and processing (Emmons *et al.*, 2023) and calling for a thorough explication of the assumptions and interpretations they are based on (Prainsack and Leonelli, 2018). In that sense, data contains subtle normative judgments and perpetuates the relational nature of data production and collection, sometimes indicating shifts in power relations between actors (e.g., Zhang *et al.*, 2021). Also, contextual information of data generates more valuable insights and information, especially when linked to other data (Hassan *et al.*, 2020; Udesky *et al.*, 2020). This implies that bias and power relations need to be addressed when talking about data (sharing) (e.g., Heacock *et al.*, 2020; Slobodova, 2020; Elbe, 2021).

Data sharing is about technical relations

These considerations of biases, contextuality and inherent (potential) discrimination of data emphasizes the effects of political contexts and social relations on practices of data sharing. These include personal and institutional reluctancies to share data, as well as tensions or sustained (or newly arising) conflicts between actors. Thus, looking at data sharing from a social

point of view may support a smoother implementation in real-life settings as technical solutions may never succeed in overcoming political and institutional obstacles (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015). Thus, data sharing is conceptualized as a complex and non-linear process, balancing between lines of conflict and cooperation and thus requires mediation to avoid that its benefits become easily clouded (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015).

Data sharing implies automatic value creation

The creation of value through data sharing is perceived as context dependent and still ambiguous (e.g., Destro Bisol *et al.*, 2014). However, open data's potential to generate public good tends to be overestimated (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020), without generating deeper insights (Pavone *et al.*, 2024). From an economic perspective, pricing of data remains challenging and usually involves a trade-off between different pricing regimes (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Thus, a nuanced approach to evaluate economic and societal benefits of data sharing, and in particular OGD, is needed (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019; Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Reasons for this mismatch between expectations and reality are manifold and include: missing consensus of evaluating management of private and public goods and services; missing gains compared to other statistical methods; a lack of harmonization and standardization (Gessa and Sancha, 2020); challenges in processing/interpreting raw data, i.e., missing information on usefulness and quality of the data (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023; Pavone *et al.*, 2024); economic trade-offs and the need for safeguarding data sharing (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020); and missing innovation networks and respective skills (Slobodova, 2020).

Thus, data sharing and open data should not be equated with automatic value creation: a paradigm of 'the more the merrier' must be rejected, as it does not reveal much about usefulness and quality of data (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023). To create value from (open) data, different actors need to actively participate in different roles (Slobodova, 2020). Moreover, the success of (open) data sharing tends to increase when value creation builds on established practices of organizations (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Thus, despite great hopes in data sharing, its socio-economic benefits are still contested (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020).

These assumptions **emphasize the political (i.e., negotiable) quality** of data sharing practices, its contextuality and relational nature. Thus, benefits of data sharing don't occur automatically,

but need to be targeted and carefully evaluated according to each setting. Here, the issue of trust turned out to be crucial, both as a precondition for data sharing as well as a result from increased transparency and accountability of decision-making. Hence, how to govern data sharing in a social (rather than a technical) way is core for increasing data sharing responsibly.

4.3 Impact Dimensions

A quantitative analysis discussed research gaps in the literature according to eleven impact dimensions, which build the basis for the subsequent DATAMITE foresight process. For a better overview, Table 2 summarizes the identified topics of each dimension.

Impact Dimension	Description	Identified topics from the literature
1. Environmental	Contribution of data sharing to sustainability and environmental performance	<p>Enhancing transparency and environmental governance (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018; Liu, Yu and Lei, 2024).</p> <p>Strengthening civic engagement and environmental activism, e.g. in China (Huang and Lyu, 2022) or Sweden (Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023).</p> <p>Challenges in data utilization and analysis (Gessa and Sancha, 2020; Waterman <i>et al.</i>, 2021).</p> <p>Creating environmental value through OGD (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020; Zhang <i>et al.</i>, 2021; Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023).</p>
2. Security	Protection of sensitive information and resilience against misuse	<p>Security data sharing emphasizes the importance of sharing sensitive information, especially in situations where global threats demand coordinated efforts (e.g., Elbe, 2021).</p> <p>Sector data exchange focuses on the growing necessity for real-time data sharing within industries to ensure smooth operations and risk mitigation (e.g., Gunasekera, 2018).</p> <p>Emerging trends and solutions for data collaboration highlight the shift towards secure, regulated frameworks that enable</p>

Impact Dimension	Description	Identified topics from the literature
		smoother sharing of valuable data (e.g., Gunasekera, 2018; Elbe, 2021).
3. Scientific / Research	Knowledge generation and innovation through open and collaborative data use	<p>Open Data and Enhanced Interdisciplinary Collaboration, e.g., for space weather (Ledvina <i>et al.</i>, 2022) or for precision medicine (Prainsack, 2021).</p> <p>Implementing Government and Institutional Policies on Data Sharing (e.g., Borgerud and Borglund, 2020; Mohammadi, Rawassizadeh and Sheikhtaheri, 2022).</p> <p>Ethical and Privacy Concerns in Data Sharing (Kalkman <i>et al.</i>, 2019; Hassan <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020).</p> <p>Societal and Environmental Impact (improving knowledge generation and related decision-making in policy, e.g., Parker and Bull, 2015; Heacock <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020; Udesky <i>et al.</i>, 2020).</p> <p>Barriers and Incentives for Data Sharing (e.g., privacy concerns, fears about misuse, or not receiving proper credit for their work (e.g., Kaaniche, Laurent and El Barbori, 2014; Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020).</p>
4. Macroeconomic	Structural effects of data sharing on markets and economic relations	<p>Prioritizing economic focus over societal objectives (e.g., Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018; Hansen and Schröder, 2019).</p> <p>Mismatch between objectives and outcomes of OGD initiatives (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).</p> <p>Challenges in engaging civil society hampering effectiveness of OGD platforms (Slobodova, 2020).</p>

Impact Dimension	Description	Identified topics from the literature
		<p>Barriers to cross-sectoral data sharing (including a lack of standardized communication protocols and technical constraints, e.g., Gunasekera, 2018).</p>
<p>5. Customer & Business</p>	<p>Effects on business operations, efficiency, and customer relations</p>	<p>OGD for societal and business use may lag behind expectations (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019) or manifest in improved government efficiency and data accessibility rather than improved innovation or public trust (Emigawaty, Adi and Rochim, 2023).</p> <p>Data Sharing in Public and Private Sectors remains challenging (e.g., Gunasekera, 2018; Elbe, 2021; Waterman <i>et al.</i>, 2021; Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022).</p> <p>Value in Big Data and Data-Driven Business Models is promising for certain industries, e.g., agriculture (Zhang <i>et al.</i>, 2021) or energy (Gunasekera, 2018).</p> <p>Enhancing accountability and Public Value through OGD remains controversial (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019), while in research, open access is seen as a means of promoting transparency, limited by infrastructural, organizational, and policy barriers (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020).</p> <p>Technological Barriers to Data Sharing are consistently cited as a limiting factor across sectors, e.g., lack of standardization and integration (Gunasekera, 2018; Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019; Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022).</p>
<p>6. Policy & Governance</p>	<p>Interaction between data sharing, governance frameworks, and policymaking</p>	<p>Environmental management and governance emerge as a critical area where Open Government Data (OGD) is actively enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of environmental policies, e.g., in China (Liu, Yu and Lei, 2024), in Sweden</p>

Impact Dimension	Description	Identified topics from the literature
		<p>(Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023), in the UK (Waterman <i>et al.</i>, 2021) and in Australia (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015).</p> <p>OGD initiatives enhance societal engagement and transparency between governments and citizens (e.g., Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018; Roche <i>et al.</i>, 2020), although challenges remain (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).</p> <p>Economic value and innovation are the third key area of application where OGD is driving significant changes by unlocking new business opportunities through the reuse of public sector data (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020; Roche <i>et al.</i>, 2020) while tensions between maximizing the economic potential and privacy remain (Udesky <i>et al.</i>, 2020).</p>
7. Ethics	Ethical responsibilities and fairness in data use and distribution	<p>Societal benefits and value, emphasizes the role of data sharing in advancing public health, highlighting community-engaged approaches with tangible benefits for the communities involved (Kalkman <i>et al.</i>, 2019).</p> <p>Trust and engagement, also beyond the GDPR is core, necessitating transparency and ethical practices that encourage stakeholder involvement (Bak <i>et al.</i>, 2023).</p> <p>Community involvement, signifies a shift towards inclusive research practices, e.g., engaging communities in the research process, advocating for respect for individual and group rights (Emmons <i>et al.</i>, 2023).</p>
8. Regulatory	Protection of personal and sensitive data in sharing processes	<p>Privacy Concerns and Data Sharing</p> <p>Privacy is a key concern across sectors, particularly with the rise of data-sharing initiatives, also in the light of re-identification of anonymized data (e.g., Colonna, 2020; Haberer and Schnurr,</p>

Impact Dimension	Description	Identified topics from the literature
		<p>2020; Bak <i>et al.</i>, 2023). Balancing accessibility and privacy are a recurring theme.</p> <p>Ethical and Legal Frameworks for Data Use</p> <p>The GDPR remains a cornerstone of the regulatory framework (Bak <i>et al.</i>, 2023), yet discussions expand beyond, including legal and ethical complexities of (genomic) data sharing (Rahimzadeh, Knoppers and Bartlett, 2020), data reuse (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020), or the alignment of legal frameworks with the practical goals of transparency and accountability (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).</p>
<p>9. Cultural</p>	<p>Cultural relevance and preservation, inclusivity of data ecosystems</p>	<p>Cultural Resistance to Data Sharing emerges as a deep-seated issue rooted in long-standing institutional and societal practices across sectors, prioritizing control of information and individual academic success over collaboration or collective scientific progress (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020; Waterman <i>et al.</i>, 2021).</p> <p>Cultural Perceptions of Openness reflect a long history of balancing transparency with control (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020; Prainsack, 2021), mirroring deeper cultural narratives around ownership, privacy, and the ethical use of data.</p> <p>Cultural Influence on Trust in Technology highlights how historical experiences and long-standing cultural beliefs shape the trust in and acceptance of new technologies, including misuse, institutional competition (e.g., Waterman <i>et al.</i>, 2021), or (missing) individual recognition (e.g., in academia, Borgerud and Borglund, 2020).</p>
<p>10. Organizational</p>	<p>Internal transformation of practices, communication,</p>	<p>Data sharing and collaboration remains a central theme across various organizational dimensions, e.g. in enhancing transparency, accountability, and interagency cooperation,</p>

Impact Dimension	Description	Identified topics from the literature
	and collaboration	<p>collaboration and participation in the context of OGD (e.g., McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015; Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).</p> <p>Technological integration allows to maximize the potential of data within organizational contexts (Gessa and Sancha, 2020; Zhang <i>et al.</i>, 2021) while technological barriers remain (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020).</p> <p>Privacy and ethical concerns are pervasive in the discussion of organizational data management, particularly regarding sensitive and personal data, e.g., in agriculture (Zhang <i>et al.</i>, 2021), public health (Zhou <i>et al.</i>, 2022), interagency collaborations (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015), or OGD (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).</p> <p>Barriers to data management and sharing comprise organizational silos, legal restrictions, political barriers and mismatch between policy and practice (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015; Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019; Borgerud and Borglund, 2020).</p>
11. Societal	Wider social impacts, including equality, trust, and bias	<p>The cluster of Societal Benefits, Innovation, and Economic Impacts involves the role of open data in driving social progress, fostering transparency, and contributing to economic growth through innovation, for example through OGD initiatives in environmental justice (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023), public health (D'Agostino <i>et al.</i>, 2016), or citizen participation (Slobodova, 2020), even if these objectives are not always fully realized (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019). In terms of economic impacts, non-monetary data valuation fosters innovation across sectors, e.g., in improving public services</p>

Impact Dimension	Description	Identified topics from the literature
		<p>(Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018), stimulating competition and innovation (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020), or addressing environmental disparities (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023).</p> <p>This cluster on Public Trust, Accountability, and Barriers to Data Sharing addresses the importance of building public trust, ensuring accountability in data-sharing processes, and overcoming the various barriers to effective data exchange. Public trust in data governance is key (Pavone <i>et al.</i>, 2024), relying on privacy and transparency (Udesky <i>et al.</i>, 2020; Waind, 2020; Etchegary <i>et al.</i>, 2023), as well as accessibility and usability (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023). However, several barriers remain: privacy concerns, technological limitations, and organizational barriers as key obstacles (Waterman <i>et al.</i>, 2021), the lack of harmonized standards (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020; Pavone <i>et al.</i>, 2024), concerns around data ownership and privacy (Emmons <i>et al.</i>, 2023), governance and ethical issues in sharing biomedical research data (Parker and Bull, 2015), governance, risk management, and legal complexities (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015).</p>

Table 2: Identified topics per impact dimension

The analysis shows that data sharing and open data ecosystems **generate multifaceted transformative potential** in different domains (e.g., environmental, societal, economic, and technological domains). Open data can significantly enhance environmental governance, scientific knowledge production, and civic engagement. However, the actual impact **often falls short** of expectations due to persistent challenges such as technological limitations, the lack of standardized protocols, and limited analytical or organizational capacities.

Furthermore, the findings illustrate that **issues of security, regulation, ethics, and governance** are deeply interconnected, highlighting the importance of secure infrastructures, robust privacy

frameworks, and mechanisms that build trust among stakeholders. Balancing openness with the protection of sensitive information is a recurring theme across sectors—from public administration to biomedical research. **Cultural and organizational factors** add additional layers of complexity, as long-standing norms, incentive structures, and institutional practices frequently determine whether data initiatives succeed or fail.

Conclusions indicate that data sharing can boost innovation, transparency and progress in society. However, variants can make it highly context dependent. Accomplishing the benefits requires a tighter alignment of governmental structures, technological infrastructure and social guidelines including ethics. The insights across various dimensions show that data sharing is not only a technical issue but a societal one that necessitates **coordination, trust and long-term institutional change**.

4.4 Conclusions from Literature-based Research

Throughout the literature, several mechanisms, principles and effects of data sharing recur, mainly in relation to the **public sector and research**, while the private sector remains comparatively under-represented. The potential benefits of data sharing depend strongly on **contextual conditions such as governance frameworks, trust, social factors, and ethical safeguards**. While expectations regarding its benefits are high, empirical evidence remains fragmented and uneven across sectors, reflecting the early maturity of the field and the need for longitudinal and comparative studies. These impacts span multiple dimensions—societal, ethical, organizational, policy-related, environmental, and cultural—illustrating the interconnected nature of data ecosystems.

The review highlights several persistent **misconceptions** surrounding data and data sharing that require critical reflection. First, **data are not neutral** but reflect social and institutional biases and contexts. Second, data sharing is not a purely technical process but one **shaped by social and political relations**. Third, **openness is not inherently “good”** but must be evaluated within its specific context, as it can introduce challenges for privacy and fairness. Fourth, data sharing does **not automatically create value**; rather, value must be actively produced through collaboration, trust, and context-sensitive governance.

The literature identified several **widely cited benefits**, including enhanced transparency, accountability, and democratic participation; improved knowledge generation, innovation, and interdisciplinary collaboration; collective data use for societal benefit; and indirect economic gains through efficiency and better resource management. Conversely, **major risks** include privacy violations and re-identification despite anonymization; bias and discrimination embedded in or amplified by shared data and AI systems; misuse, misinterpretation, and decontextualization of data; and the proliferation of societal inequalities leading to mistrust toward data holders, particularly where power asymmetries persist.

Trust emerges as a central factor—both a prerequisite for and a result of responsible data sharing. It must be cultivated through transparent governance, participatory structures, and ethical safeguards, developing gradually through consistent and responsible practice. Acknowledging the social embeddedness of data sharing by balancing privacy, transparency, and public interest is therefore critical. Effective data governance should ensure accountability, inclusiveness, and fairness while avoiding an over-reliance on technical fixes. In terms of research, more systematic and interdisciplinary studies are needed to connect technical, legal, ethical, and societal perspectives.

In short, data sharing can be a powerful driver of innovation, transparency, and social good—but only under conditions that ensure ethical responsibility, privacy protection, inclusivity, and contextual awareness. It is not inherently beneficial; its outcomes depend on how, by whom, and for what purposes it is implemented.

To ensure **responsible data sharing**, a **broad range of principles** have been proposed in the SSH literature, including: (1) **societal benefit and public value**; (2) **equitable distribution of risks, benefits, and burdens**; (3) **respect for individuals and groups**; and (4) **public trust and engagement** (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019). Concretely, this entails ensuring fairness in benefit-sharing with data-contributing communities (Emmons *et al.*, 2023), enabling agency and consent in data use decisions (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020; Emmons *et al.*, 2023), maintaining responsible research conduct (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019), and providing adequate resources and capacity for ethical governance (Cheah *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, it calls for rethinking consent, access models, and governance mechanisms to balance openness with accountability (Cheah *et al.*, 2015).

These conclusions provide a solid conceptual framework for understanding data sharing as a **socially embedded practice**. They informed the empirical analyses presented in the following

chapters, ensuring that the DATAMITE foresight approach builds upon both theoretical insights and real-world practices.

5 Empirical Insights from Pilots: Investigating, Capturing and Validating against Real-world Practices

Building on the foresight methodology described above, the following section presents the empirical insights gathered from the DATAMITE pilots, focusing on how data sharing practices are perceived, implemented, and evolving across sectors as well as how they estimate the future perspectives of data sharing beyond monetization and technology.

5.1 Semi-structured Interviews

5.1.1 Organisational Shifts in Practice: How do Practices Change within Organisations due to the (planned) Introduction of Data Sharing?

The weak signal analysis addressed current and potentially changing practices within organisations due to data sharing. This analysis revealed that data sharing is no longer an emerging topic but rather has found its way into strategic considerations of organisations hoping for direct or indirect monetisation (for strategies to monetise different data sharing strategies, see D4.1). However, exploring implementation potentials for organisations still largely lies in the **responsibility of enthusiasts and task forces**, as illustrated by the interviews (Interviews01-06). This indicates that challenges of data sharing, e.g., regarding required efforts for implementation, as well as uncertainties regarding regulation and potential adverse impacts (e.g., loss of reputation and trust) remain (Interviews01-06).

Interview partners considered themselves and their role within their companies as ‘trailblazers’ or ‘pioneers’, usually as part of specific teams like ‘research and development’ (Interview03: 27-27, 38-38, 47-48, 51-51, 55-55) or ‘task forces’ that **explore data sharing and aim at promoting it within their organization** (Interview06: 17-18, Interview04: 42-42, Interview02: 17-17, Interview06: 15-16). One person even considered himself an “*evangelist of data sharing, relevance, and data-driven companies*” (Interview02: 57-57). At the time of the interview, only one pilot had experiences with a specific data sharing strategy (here: an open data portal). However,

depending on the sector, **external conditions** already encourage or demand data sharing, e.g., for enhancing transparency (Interview02: 40-55), either on a voluntary basis (Interview02) or legally obliged (Interview05).

In terms of established sharing practices, some sectors require pilot partners to share data with regulatory bodies, providers, or other organizations on behalf of the government, e.g. for planning regional development by law (Interview06: 25-26). Yet, these forms of data sharing differ from public open data strategies (Interview05: 5-5) or data sharing as addressed in the DATAMITE scenarios (Interview06: 18-18). Some pilot partners promoted pro-active approaches to data sharing due to perceived changes in current conditions like shifts in legislation or a strengthened ‘paradigm of transparency’ in public administration; yet these perceptions were not always shared by all of the organization (Interview02: 140-50).

Obviously, most organizations of DATAMITE pilots prepare for (increased) data sharing and consider the activities of their organizations as pathbreaking for other organizations within their group or wider networks in general, to lead the transformation towards data sharing (Interview03: 43-46, Interview02: 32-32, Interview06: 8-8, 9-11). Here, DATAMITE was considered crucial to restructure company workflows through data sharing processes (Interview02: 28-28). This assessment indicates that although building established processes, practices and business models (Interview04: 51-52, Interview01: 26-26), data sharing implies a deep transformation of organizations’ mindsets, workflows, resource spending and collaborations.

5.1.2 Shifting Mindsets

All pilots addressed the importance of **organizational mindsets and culture** when thinking about introducing data sharing practices. As a first step, knowledge and awareness raising about data and their potential value for monetization or beyond (non-monetary benefits) (Interview04: 60-61, 82-82) was considered a precondition to recognize potential opportunities and benefits (and risks, authors’ note) (Interview04: 47-47, 50-50). However, this varies between (management) levels of organizations, with higher/strategic management being rather aware of potential benefits (Interview04: 48-48) while most employees remain rather unaware (Interview04: 38-40). Moreover, people inclined to promote data sharing need to take existing concerns seriously as ‘(open) data sharing is a scary thing, especially for a utility company’, including issues of safety and data quality (Interview05: 30-38).

Understanding data sharing as a **continuation of established practices** of analyses (Interview04: 31-31, 33-33, 35-37, 51-52) or business models (Interview01, 26-26), as most interview partners did, may support this process of changing mindsets.

This expectation was confirmed by one organization who had already introduced a specific data sharing strategy for sharing its data publicly and addressed strategic as well as practical implications. First, they emphasized that the decision on which data to share, and how, remains strategic and selective irrespective of strategic approaches and technical solutions available (Interview05: 10-10). **Technical solutions for sharing data still need to follow strategic decisions**, rather than the other way round. Second, they disclosed that the introduction of an open data portal allowed to replace a hitherto existing process, i.e., *ad hoc* data sharing on demand (Interview05: 7-7). While the external data requirements indicate their usefulness for external stakeholders (here: to accelerate energy transition), open data sharing allowed to strengthen and systematize internal processes (Interview05: 7-7). Thus, data sharing practices do not constitute something completely new but rather a **continuation of responding** to previous requests, allowing for a **shift in terms of scale rather than quality**, e.g. in relation to geographic extension or transfer to different companies within the same group (Interview05: 13-14, 49-49). However, **technically speaking, data sharing requires new solutions to ensure safety**. Their emerging abundance, together with positive use cases, created new opportunities to share additional data sets and indicated a fundamental shift in the organization's mindset: *"We've received numerous requests from colleagues suggesting datasets or dashboards for the open data portal. The shift in the company's data culture is growing, and there's a stronger internal propensity to share data"* (Interview05: 38-38). Thus, the organizations' culture moved from a strict 'no' to a weighing of benefits and risks (Interview05: 23-23).

Therefore, one pilot emphasized the importance of managing the cultural shift towards data sharing actively, i.e., by showcasing positive use cases. This *"allows the company to see the value in sharing data (...) It has to be tailored by the data owners, as they know the data best and are responsible if issues arise"* (Interview05: 23-23).

5.1.3 Shifting Workflows

For organizations, the expected increase of sharing data with external stakeholders constitutes **an opportunity to improve internal processes** regarding data quality and process efficacy (Interview06: 34-34):

„Right now there's been made a permanent company regulation that tries to automate, or to settle things how to provide data to third parties, I mean to outside parties, to clear everything up: Who's responsible? What can I do? Who's going to confirm? Who's going to provide? Who's going to reply? So having this set up will be a major improvement in the processes in the company, both for our benefit and both for the benefit of the consumers that are going to have the data ready in a better quality, but sooner, maybe in a much easier process for them through the portal” (Interview06: 34-34).

This was confirmed by experiences in dealing with external requests for data, illustrated by the increased numbers and use cases (Interview05: 48-48): “Instead of pulling data from internal systems, we can now direct stakeholders to the open data portal” (Interview05: 37-37).

At the same time, **new processes** need to be established, such as a **risk assessment** procedure to frequently assess legal risks, security concerns, data quality and reputation risks on a case-by-case basis for individual data sets (Interview05: 22-22). Also, external scrutiny and visibility considerably **improved processes for data quality** (Interview05: 30-38): providing high quality data is crucial as low-quality standards eventually affect the organizations' reputation among stakeholders and collaboration partners as well as the public (Interview05: 33-33, 37-37). Accordingly, new data sharing mechanisms (e.g., open data) may serve as an external/public control of data quality. **Training opportunities** need to address employees' new roles regarding data sharing (e.g., data governance, specialist data stewards, business owners, data owners, etc.) (Interview06: 40-40, 41-41), as well as technical support for businesspeople to use tools such as DATAMITE (Interview04: 31-31, 42-42) without burdening them with technical background. Yet, these trainings were also expected to address the employees' mentality (Interview04: 31-31, 33-33, 35-37).

5.1.4 Shifting Resources

Pilot partners confirmed that **positive impacts** of introducing data sharing tools (i.e., an open data portal) in terms of efficiency became visible quickly (Interview05: 39-42). They emphasized spill-over effects within the company (Interview05: 11-11), i.e., increased internal efficiency: one example related to sharing grid data with electric vehicle charging point operators which resulted in more efficiently planning of charging point locations by saving time in the process (less iterations). Another example involved sharing data about the location of cables and substations. Originally aimed at academic purposes, this self-service approach reduced data requests by local developers considerably (Interview05: 16-19).

However, data sharing tools still come at **costs**, which often remain hidden, usually **technical and human resources**. The former comprises challenges like data harmonization, integration, standardisation and so on. The latter includes engaging stakeholders about their information needs to allow for target data sharing since *“sharing the wrong data can be worse than sharing no data at all”* (Interview05: 25-26), as well as required shifts in workflows (e.g., defining internal policies, integrating additional sources of data into existing services etc.) (Interview01: 30-30) (Interview06: 38-38). Not least, concerns need to be addressed continuously and the decision to share data need to be renewed which requires considerable resources (*“starting from the beginning”* (Interview05: 56-57)). For individuals, where concerned, clear incentives are crucial to justify efforts related to data sharing. On a technical level, ready-to-use tools may facilitate processes and help the savings on integration (Interview01: 15-15).

5.1.5 Shifting Collaborations

New opportunities and contracts to adhere to a **new ‘paradigm of transparency’** were considered one incentive of data sharing (Interview02: 81-82). Another pilot argued that when introducing a standardised approach to data sharing (open data portal), they experienced an increased collaboration with external stakeholders. In addition to sharing data for academic purposes, territorial studies, or public policies (Interview05: 6-6), new collaborations have been established: *“For example, large renewable investors have become heavy users of our open data, helping them assess the suitability of locations for new projects.”* (Interview05: 28-29). To provide useful, i.e., targeted, information, this requires close collaboration with stakeholders to identify their needs:

“For example, when we initially considered sharing data from secondary substations, we discovered that stakeholders wanted neighborhood-level consumption patterns to support the installation of photovoltaics. Instead of sharing substation data, which isn't granular enough, we now publish consumption patterns by municipality, parish, and ZIP code” (Interview05: 25-27).

Therefore, new practices of data sharing may not only indicate shifts in practices, but also prove **non-monetary benefits**, like increased stakeholder collaborations, may be a **fast return** on investments (rather than focusing on efficiency or monetization only).

5.1.6 Conclusions on Shifting Practices of Organizations due to Data Sharing

As outlined in this chapter, (the anticipation of) increased data sharing induces shifts in organizations workflows to facilitate this transition. While these shifts largely remain incremental, the effort of inducing these shifts must not be underestimated. **Inducing a cultural shift** in organizations, i.e., changing management's and employee's mindsets regarding data sharing and preparing these shifts remained the main issue from pilot's perspective. Besides, one pilot had two recommendations for introducing data sharing: first, to not underestimate non-monetary benefits like new collaborations or efficiency of operations as positive impact for the company; and to refrain from providing 'open data by default', and rather aim for a selection based on case-by-case assessments (Interview05: 53-53, 59-59).

Building on the qualitative insights from the semi-structured interviews, the next step aimed to **validate and quantify** the observed patterns across all DATAMITE pilots. To achieve this, a structured survey was conducted to systematically assess how different sectors perceive the benefits and risks of data sharing. This complementary quantitative approach provided a means to compare sectoral perspectives, confirm recurring themes identified in the interviews, and highlight potential divergences in priorities or expectations. The combined analysis of qualitative and quantitative data thus strengthened the reliability of findings and provided a more comprehensive understanding of non-monetary impacts within the DATAMITE framework.

5.2 Perceived Impact of Data Sharing: Assessment of Expected Impacts

To complement the qualitative data set, a structured **questionnaire-based assessment** was conducted with stakeholders from the DATAMITE pilot teams. Participants were asked to evaluate the expected benefits of data sharing in their respective sectors using a 1 – 6 Likert scale (removing a neutral middle point and force a lean toward agreement or disagreement), where 1 indicates no expected benefit and 6 represents very high expected benefit.

The results presented in (Figure 2) are visualized using a radar chart, which provides a **comparative view** of how each pilot perceives the relevance and strength of 11 key benefit dimensions associated with future data sharing. The figure presents aggregated results from the DATAMITE pilot survey, showing how participants rated the perceived impacts of data sharing across 11 non-monetary dimensions (scale 1 – 6; resulting in 6 sectors with 6 points maximum each, i.e. 36). Higher values represent stronger perceived benefits or relevance of each dimension.

Figure 2: Expected benefits of data sharing in different dimensions for pilot partners from ‘no benefit’ to ‘very high’ benefits

The radar chart reveals both shared priorities and sector-specific expectations, highlighting how the perceived value of data sharing is shaped by contextual needs and strategic outlooks.

The results of the analysis clearly rank the anticipated advantages of data sharing. With an average score of 30 out of a theoretical maximum of 36, the **customer and business-related** dimension achieves the highest value. It is assumed that because this dimension is directly related to operational effectiveness, service quality, and data-driven decision-making, pilots perceive the greatest and most immediate value here. Thus, it emphasizes the business lens of partners on data sharing, even when asked about non-monetary values.

Benefits to the **environment** come in second with 29 points. This illustrates the widespread understanding across industries that improved resource utilization, more precise forecasting, and advancement toward sustainability objectives are all facilitated by shared data. Improved data flows reduce waste and increase resilience, even for pilots who do not prioritize the environment. **Organizational benefits** receive a high score of 27.5 points. Pilots expect gains in coordination, process clarity and internal alignment. Although they are less obvious from the outside, these advantages promote more stable operations and lessen organizational fragmentation.

In general, pilots acknowledge the strategic importance of ecological and organizational advantages while giving priority to benefits that yield tangible operational improvements.

Cultural benefits (15.5 points) and **ethical benefits** (18 points) are perceived as least relevant across pilots. These dimensions are seen as indirect and long-term, with limited immediate operational impact. While actors recognise their general importance, they do not expect short-term gains from data sharing in these areas. The low scores indicate that pilots focus primarily on benefits that are concrete, measurable and closely tied to their core activities.

5.2.1 Perceived Risks

In addition to exploring potential benefits and opportunities, the anticipatory foresight study included an **evaluation of perceived risks** associated with data sharing. Understanding these perceptions is crucial because foresight does not only aim to envision desirable futures but also to identify potential obstacles, unintended consequences, and points of resistance that may hinder progress. Risks such as data misuse, privacy breaches, unequal access, or loss of competitive

advantage can significantly shape stakeholder attitudes and influence the feasibility of future scenarios. By systematically assessing these concerns, the study ensured a balanced and realistic perspective on data sharing, acknowledging that trust, governance, and ethical considerations are as decisive for sustainable implementation as technological and economic factors. Integrating risk perception into the foresight process thus strengthened the anticipatory dimension of the analysis and supported the formulation of actionable, responsible, and socially robust recommendations.

Figure 3: Expected risks of data sharing in different dimensions for pilot partners from ‘no risks’ to ‘very high’ risks

The radar chart highlights the multifaceted nature of data-sharing challenges by showing the distribution of perceived risks across sectors. The level of concern for each impact dimension is reflected in the scores. A higher perceived risk is indicated by higher values. Although technical risks are prevalent in all industries, the risk landscape is dominated by **security and governance**

factors, as the figure illustrates. The least expected risk dimension is the societal one. Due to the industry's exposure to privacy, compliance, and cross-border governance issues, **telecommunication exhibits the broadest risk profile**, especially in ethics, societal, policy, security, customer and business and regulatory dimensions, and organizational dimensions. Internal governance and data protection continue to be crucial bottlenecks for decentralized or multi-actor ecosystems. Urban services and agriculture exhibit intermediate risk levels, with prominent concerns in the regulatory, consumer, business, and security domains. On the other hand, the energy industry (which includes both Portuguese and Greek pilots) poses concentrated risks in terms of security and ethical integrity, where the accuracy of predictive models and sensitive operational data present serious difficulties. The lowest overall risk profile is found in meteorology, which primarily operates under a public-service model. However, moderate exposure in security and policy indicates that continued vigilance is necessary to strike a balance between transparency and public accountability. Overall, the graphic emphasizes how governance, organizational coordination, and regulatory clarity are the key elements influencing risk perception and management in developing data ecosystems, even though technical risks are prevalent across industries.

5.3 Future Visions

THIS CHAPTER SUMMARIZES THE FINDINGS FROM THE PILOTS' FUTURE VISIONS. FOR THE DETAILED ANALYSIS SEE ANNEX E.

Each pilot in the DATAMITE project co-created a **sector-specific vision** for how trusted, value-generating data sharing could evolve over the next 5–10 years. Visioning is a powerful strategy for validation as it encourages stakeholders to reflect on dimensions such as societal, ethical, and governance, most relevant in shaping desirable data-sharing futures. By grounding abstract concepts in sector-specific scenarios, visioning enhances the contextual relevance and practical applicability of the SSH framework.

The results of the visioning process **varied significantly across the pilots**, reflecting differing goals, regional contexts, and stakeholder priorities. Some visions focused on technological innovation and competitiveness, while others emphasized social cohesion, environmental

sustainability, or local empowerment. This diversity underscores the importance of pluralistic perspectives in generating context-sensitive frameworks, though it also presents challenges in achieving broader alignment and integration.

5.3.1 Cross-Pilot Synthesis

The Cross-Pilot synthesis revealed both converging priorities and sectoral divergences:

5.3.1.1 Communalities and Convergences

Despite the diversity of sectors, organizational missions, and regional contexts, a clear set of communalities and convergences emerged across the developed visions for future data sharing and collaboration. These shared priorities reflect a growing consensus on the foundational role of data in enabling innovation, enhancing societal impact, and fostering trustworthy collaboration across domains.

Secure, Scalable, and Flexible Data Infrastructures

A recurring theme across all visions is the need for advanced and scalable data infrastructures capable of managing large, complex, and rapidly growing datasets. CINECA, for example, highlights the challenge of handling petabyte-scale meteorological data, while GIDI emphasizes the development of a unified data architecture to streamline processes across its operations. Similarly, OTE, E-REDES, and others stress the importance of building efficient and secure infrastructures as enablers of effective cross-sectoral collaboration.

Commitment to Data Quality, Interoperability, and Accessibility

Ensuring the availability of high-quality, complete, and interoperable data is another common priority. Many organizations, CINECA, PSNC/WODR, and E-REDES among them, acknowledge that reliable data is a prerequisite for innovation, especially in areas such as AI-driven services. At the same time, there is a strong push to broaden data access. Institutions like CINECA and E-REDES actively pursue open-access strategies, while GIDI and PSNC/WODR integrate data sharing into their core business strategies and engage users to ensure transparency and usability.

Trust, Transparency, and Ethical Considerations

Building trust is widely acknowledged as essential for fostering a data-sharing culture. Across sectors, visions reflect a commitment to transparency, secure data exchange, and ethical governance. GIDI and E-REDES are developing guidelines and tools to manage security and

privacy risks, while PSNC/WODR and OTE underline the challenges of establishing trust, particularly in traditionally cautious domains like agriculture, where concerns about ownership, security, and incentives remain substantial.

Collaborative Ecosystems and Cross-Sector Partnerships

All organizations emphasize the importance of collaboration across institutional, sectoral, and geographic boundaries. Whether through regional cooperation (CINECA, E-REDES), cross-departmental integration (GIDI), or EU-level platforms and projects (PSNC/WODR, UniKo), stakeholders view partnerships as vital for building shared capabilities, bridging knowledge gaps, and accelerating innovation. Collaboration is not only operational but also strategic, serving as a key enabler for long-term vision realization.

Innovation, Services, and Societal Impact

Data sharing is consistently framed as a catalyst for innovation and the development of new services and applications. Visions foresee diverse use cases ranging from improved customer experiences and predictive services (OTE, CINECA) to supply chain optimization and sustainability in agriculture (PSNC/WODR). Importantly, many organizations stress the non-monetary benefits of data sharing, such as public safety, research integrity, and societal well-being, often prioritizing them over immediate commercial gains.

Alignment with European Governance and regulatory Frameworks

Multiple stakeholders align their visions with ongoing European regulatory developments, notably the Data Governance Act, the European Strategy for Data, and sector-specific initiatives like the Common European Agricultural Data Space. This alignment not only facilitates compliance but also reinforces shared standards and cross-border interoperability, supporting the emergence of a coherent European data ecosystem.

Monetization Potential and Incentive Structures

While non-commercial benefits remain central, several visions acknowledge future opportunities for monetization. Examples include business models for premium data services (CINECA), passporting mechanisms in agricultural data markets (PSNC/WODR), and indirect benefits such as enhanced market positioning and cross-selling opportunities (OTE). These incentives may play an important role in sustaining long-term stakeholder engagement.

Organizational Change and Data Literacy

Finally, several visions recognize the need for internal transformation. This includes fostering a culture that values data sharing, investing in employee training, and embedding data strategies into organizational processes. E-REDES and GIDI, in particular, stress the importance of building data literacy and aligning internal operations with the broader vision of transparent and responsible data use.

In summary, while each vision reflects unique sectoral and organizational priorities, a strong convergence is evident around key principles: secure and scalable infrastructure, high-quality and accessible data, trust and ethical governance, cross-sector collaboration, and a shared commitment to societal impact. Together, these elements form the foundation for a common data-sharing future, one that balances innovation and inclusion, economic opportunity and public value, all within a European framework of trust, transparency, and compliance.

5.3.1.2 Differences and Divergences

The six DATAMITE pilot use cases developed distinct yet partially overlapping visions for future data sharing. While all emphasize trust, interoperability, and value creation, they differ in motivations, monetization approaches, technical priorities, addressed challenges, and the scope of sharing.

Motivations and Monetization

Pilots span a spectrum from societal impact to commercial incentive. CINECA emphasizes public value and environmental safety, with monetization seen as a future possibility. PSNC/WODR prioritize monetary incentives, proposing data marketplaces and passporting to support farmer engagement. GIDI combines business goals with ethics, seeing data sharing as a strategic asset. OTE balances operational efficiency with market benefits. E-REDES links data sharing to sustainability and performance, rather than profit.

Challenges Addressed

Visions are shaped by context-specific barriers. CINECA focuses on managing petabyte-scale data growth. PSNC/WODR stress cultural resistance and interoperability gaps in agriculture. GIDI targets security and reliability for critical infrastructure. UniKo seeks to improve research

reproducibility and collaboration. E-REDES tackles integration into business processes and data literacy. OTE highlights customer experience, fraud prevention, and internal silos.

Technical Priorities

Each use case outlines tailored technical goals. CINECA prioritizes scalable infrastructure for AI integration. GIDI develops unified architectures across its entities. PSNC/WODR emphasize semantic interoperability, referencing the Agriculture Information Model. OTE focuses on privacy-compliant infrastructures for cross-unit collaboration.

Scope of Data Sharing

Visions diverge between internal and ecosystem-oriented sharing. OTE and GIDI focus on intra-organizational data flows. In contrast, CINECA, E-REDES, UniKo, and PSNC/WODR advocate broader sharing, ranging from open meteorological data to cross-sector collaboration in energy, academia, and agriculture.

5.3.1.3 Non-Monetary Benefits as Core Drivers

Across the DATAMITE pilots, a wide array of non-monetary benefits was identified as central drivers of data-sharing strategies.

Non-monetary benefits are considered essential to a company's vision, particularly in the context of data sharing and its impacts. These benefits can significantly enhance an organization's efficiency, customer satisfaction, and innovation potential.

Key Non-Monetary Benefits Identified

- Improved Trust: Data sharing can lead to increased trust among parties
- Transparency: Enhanced transparency is a significant non-monetary benefit derived from data sharing
- Security: Improved security is also recognized as a crucial non-monetary benefit
- Public Safety: Non-monetary impacts can include contributions to public safety, such as advancements in flood and weather forecasting
- Enhanced Decision-Making: The development of tools to measure and manage these benefits can lead to improved company decision-making processes
- Long-term Strategic Goals: These benefits contribute to achieving long-term strategic objectives

- **Organizational Efficiency:** Non-monetary benefits can boost an organization's overall efficiency
- **Customer Satisfaction:** They can also lead to higher customer satisfaction
- **Innovation Potential:** The potential for innovation within an organization can be increased through these benefits

Measuring and Leveraging Non-Monetary Benefits

There is a strong emphasis on developing concrete, practical tools to measure and manage these non-monetary benefits, especially those related to transparency, security, and trust from data sharing. These tools are desired to be actionable, allowing for direct application across different departments, and contributing to strategic goals rather than remaining abstract. While the current focus is non-monetary, there is an acknowledgment of potential future monetization through premium features or charges for advanced data services.

In summary, non-monetary benefits encompass a range of advantages from improved trust and transparency to enhanced public safety and organizational efficiency, all of which are crucial for strategic development and operational improvement, with a clear vision for their measurement and leverage. Thus, non-monetary benefits are not only intrinsic values but also strategic assets. Their recognition and operationalization are viewed as essential steps toward building resilient, responsible, and future-ready data-sharing environments.

5.4 Recommendation and Likelihood of Happening

This collection of recommendations derives from **sector-specific evidence**, each pilot identifying feasible actions to enhance data sharing in general, quality, traceability, and collaboration within its context. Together, they highlight a common European trajectory toward more resilient and ethically governed data infrastructures, where sustainable innovation depends not only on technological readiness but also on SSH alignment like stakeholder trust, environmental impact or the capacity to translate data into shared value. A total of 49 recommendations were collected and analyzed. The recommendations also allowed to identify gaps and the need for further support actions.

5.4.1 Sectoral Recommendations for Data Sharing

This chapter outlines the recommendations for data sharing for different DATAMITE sectors.

5.4.1.1 Urban Services Sector (GIDI)

The GIDI pilot demonstrates the complexity of data sharing within **large, decentralized corporate groups**. Although subsidiaries operate under a single corporate brand, organizational silos and limited trust impede effective data exchange. The pilot's recommendations focus on strengthening security, traceability, and strategic alignment to enable safe, value-driven data use.

Key Recommendations:

- **Tiered Security and Controlled Access:** Introduce a multi-layered security framework granting selective access to sensitive datasets. Role-based controls foster trust and make data sharing operationally feasible (Feasibility: Very High).
- **Anonymization and Data Lineage:** Standardize anonymization processes and ensure full data lineage to enable accountability and reuse (High).
- **Balanced Monetization Models:** Reorient business strategies from direct data monetization toward innovation-driven sharing and internal efficiency gains (Low to Moderate).
- **Cross-Sectoral Investment:** Promote investment in shared data systems bridging public and private domains (Moderate).

Feasibility is highest for technical measures, security and anonymization, while lower for cultural and strategic shifts such as monetization and inter-sectoral collaboration. The pilot underlines the decisive role of trust, data governance, and leadership commitment in overcoming intra-corporate barriers.

5.4.1.2 Energy Sector (HEDNO & E-REDES)

Energy pilots reveal that **trusted data sharing can accelerate digitalization**, enhance system efficiency, and improve cross-stakeholder coordination. However, progress requires harmonized regulation, ethical safeguards, and organizational adaptation.

Key Recommendations:

- **Regulation and Interoperability:** Legislative frameworks should enforce interoperability and traceability, providing a regulatory backbone for lawful and transparent data exchange (High).

- Ethics and Cybersecurity: Ethical principles must guide the handling of personal and operational data; traceability and watermarking protect data integrity (Very High).
- Process Redesign and Governance: Internal processes must be realigned to match interoperability requirements and minimize duplication (Moderate).
- Data Quality and Energy Efficiency: Strengthen governance to improve data reliability and reduce energy waste in AI applications (Moderate).
- Infrastructure Robustness: Invest in the digital backbone of the energy system to enable scalable sharing (Moderate to High).
- Consumer Awareness and Industrial Engagement: Encourage behavioral change and industrial participation through better access to real-time data (Low to Moderate).
- Open Data and Scientific Research: Facilitate access for the research community to stimulate innovation and sustainability (Very High).

The sector's maturity depends on regulatory and ethical leadership combined with infrastructure modernization. High-feasibility actions relate to regulation and ethics; medium-feasibility measures involve organizational change and cultural adaptation.

5.4.1.3 Agriculture Sector (PSNC / eDWIN)

Agricultural data sharing is shaped less by technical readiness and more by **social trust, incentives, and regulatory support**. The eDWIN platform highlights the need for mindset transformation and coherent governance to unlock sustainable value.

Key Recommendations:

- Trust and Cultural Incentives: Foster farmer confidence through education and incentive schemes that stress indirect benefits of data sharing (Low).
- Data-Driven Innovation: Support new services for SMEs and small farms to demonstrate tangible advantages of sharing (Variable, Moderate to High).
- Environmental Datafication: Use digital tools and standards to link ecological objectives with data-based monitoring (Moderate).
- Data Security and Certification: Strengthen food safety through robust data protection and certification mechanisms (High for security, Moderate for certification).

- Regulatory and Funding Alignment: Tie subsidies and grants to data-sharing compliance to create strong economic incentives (Variable).
- Applied Research and Open Science: Encourage openness among applied research communities to accelerate innovation (High).
- Ecosystem Collaboration and SME Integration: Equip new actors with tools for digital participation and cross-platform cooperation (Moderate to High).

The pilot underscores that technological progress must be matched by **cultural change**, targeted incentives, and clear governance. Feasibility is highest where trust and funding align; lowest where behavioral resistance persists.

5.4.1.4 Telecommunications Sector (OTE Group)

In telecommunications, the OTE pilot identifies **organizational awareness and governance** as the primary enablers of data sharing. Technical barriers are secondary to strategic alignment and leadership engagement.

Key Recommendations:

- Awareness and Leadership: Build internal campaigns and designate sponsors or external consultants to promote data-sharing literacy (High).
- Transparency and Risk Management: Communicate risks and responsibilities clearly to enhance internal trust (Moderate to High).
- Process Optimization: Establish standardized playbooks for consistent, compliant data exchange (Very High).
- Sustainable Business Models: Develop ROI-driven business models supported by market analysis (High).
- Regulatory Compliance and Monitoring: Create dedicated teams to track and anticipate regulatory changes (High for monitoring, Moderate for compliance).

Organizational transformation and strategic communication are prerequisites for sustainable data ecosystems. The highest feasibility lies in enablement measures, awareness, process optimization, and strategic monitoring, whereas compliance is constrained by external regulation.

5.4.1.5 Meteorology Sector (CINECA / MISTRAL)

The CINECA pilot showcases how a **public infrastructure** can evolve into a **service-oriented data platform** supporting national resilience and innovation. Its goals focus on scalability, inclusiveness, and scientific utility rather than profit.

Key Recommendations:

- Resilient Big-Data Infrastructure: Maintain investments in distributed systems for reliable, high-volume data processing (High).
- User Base Expansion: Broaden participation beyond public agencies to include energy, logistics, and research stakeholders (Medium to High).
- Tiered Services and Monetization: Introduce differentiated access models within legal constraints to enhance sustainability (Medium).
- Data for AI Applications: Enable access to high-frequency datasets for predictive modeling and climate analytics (High).

The meteorological sector exemplifies public value creation through open, resilient data infrastructures. Success depends on sustained investment, flexible regulation, and strategic partnerships that extend beyond the traditional public domain.

5.4.2 Cross-Pilot Comparison

Across all pilots, **trust, governance, and institutional alignment** emerge as the central determinants of success in data sharing.

- Technical readiness (security, anonymization, and interoperability) is generally high and progressing rapidly.
- Cultural and strategic shifts, including monetization models, cross-sector cooperation, and behavioral change, remain the primary obstacles.
- Feasibility is strongest where measures align with existing governance frameworks or funding mechanisms; weakest where organizational or societal transformation is required.

Together, these findings reveal a European data-sharing landscape that is technically mature but organizationally uneven. Future policy should therefore prioritize trust frameworks, cross-sector

incentives, and sustained education, ensuring that data serves as a shared resource for innovation, efficiency, and public good.

Despite these commonalities, **several frictions** and sector-specific tensions were identified:

Public vs. Private Value Creation: Some pilots (e.g., GIDI, PSNC) struggle with finding a balance between open data sharing and monetization, especially in hybrid ecosystems where both public and private actors coexist.

Monetization Ambiguity: While monetization appeared in many discussions (OTE, GIDI, PSNC), it often clashed with other priorities like openness, scientific value, or regulatory constraints (as in CINECA). This tension points to the need for nuanced, sector-sensitive business models.

Technical Readiness vs. Organizational Willingness: In several cases (OTE, GIDI, PSNC), technical solutions were available, but cultural or structural inertia within organizations limited adoption. This underscores the importance of organizational readiness, not just digital capability.

Regulation as Enabler or Barrier: Some pilots (e.g., PSNC, OTE) viewed regulatory frameworks as necessary enablers, while others (CINECA) flagged that public funding rules can restrict flexibility, particularly in monetization or service innovation.

5.4.3 Likelihood of Recommendations

The DATAMITE participants also estimated the likelihood that the recommendations would be implemented in practice. The participants have diverse professional backgrounds, even though all of them work with data sharing in some capacity. Because their expertise varies across specific topics, the assessments may reflect differing levels of underlying knowledge. While no explicit confidence levels were collected, this variation was taken into account during analysis and interpretation. As a result, findings in areas with clearly uneven expertise were treated more cautiously, and conclusions were based on patterns that remained consistent across participants. Evaluating the **estimated likelihood of recommendations to be implemented in practice** serves to reveal dimensions that are hindering data sharing to a full extent. The analysis of sector-specific recommendations across eleven thematic dimensions provides critical insights for strategic planning and resource allocation in cross-sectoral development. Figure 4 outlines the

number of recommendations in each dimension per sector and the perceived likelihood of implementing these recommendations and actions necessary to make the vision a reality.

Figure 4: Average estimated likelihood of recommendations to be implemented.

Analysing by heat mapping (score 0-2: not very feasible; 3-4: moderately feasible and 5-6: very feasible) most recommendations were rated as highly feasible (n=20), 15 recommendations as feasible (scoring from 3-4), 5 as ‘not very feasible’ and 9 were not rated at all.

The feasibility ratings suggest a **generally optimistic assessment** by stakeholders regarding the ability of implementation of the proposed recommendations. The fact that the majority (n = 20) were rated as highly feasible (scores 5–6) likely reflects the strong alignment between these actions and existing organizational priorities, available resources, or current policy trends. Many of these recommendations may build on ongoing initiatives or address well-understood needs, making them appear both actionable and realistic in the short to medium term.

The 15 recommendations rated as moderately feasible (scores 3–4) could indicate proposals that, while relevant, require additional resources, stakeholder coordination, or regulatory support to be effectively implemented. These actions may be seen as valuable but conditional on overcoming known barriers such as limited capacity, fragmented data governance, or insufficient funding.

The smaller number of low-feasibility ratings (n = 5, score 0–2) likely corresponds to more ambitious or disruptive proposals, such as structural reforms, advanced technological deployment, or cross-sectoral alignment, which are perceived as more challenging due to technical, institutional, or political constraints.

The 9 recommendations left unrated, including 7 from the climate pilot, could point to uncertainty or lack of consensus among stakeholders. This may result from lower familiarity with the domain, insufficient detail in the recommendation, or limited participation from key actors during the feasibility assessment phase. It may also reflect the experimental nature of the climate pilot, where long-term impacts and implementation pathways are still being explored.

Overall, the pattern indicates a strong inclination toward pragmatic, actionable steps, while highlighting areas that require further support, clarification, or capacity-building to move from vision to implementation.

Some dimensions were **more frequently** mentioned than others:

- Dimension 5 (Monetization & Economic Value n= 10) was the most frequently referenced, indicating a strong cross-sector interest in how to capture and distribute the value of data.
- Dimension 1 (Trust and Willingness n=7) and Dimension 11 (Regulation & Ethics n= 8) were also widely cited, highlighting the central role of trust, legal clarity, and ethical safeguards.
- Dimensions 4 (Scientific Innovation n=3) and 8 (Transparency & Risk Awareness n=3) were the least mentioned, suggesting these are either less contested or already integrated in some sectoral practices.

Some recommendations were related to more than one dimension. Especially the recommendations are often highly linked to the respective topic of the pilot. For example, both energy sectors focus very much on recommendations that are targeted towards the organizational dimension.

5.4.4 Overall Learning and Empirical Insights from Recommendations

The collective recommendations from the six pilots suggest that enabling non-monetary value from data sharing requires more than just technology, it demands:

- Trust-building and cultural change, especially where privacy and competition prevail.

- Incentive structures, whether financial, reputational, or regulatory, to drive participation.
- Strong governance frameworks, including standards, certification, and accountability.
- Flexible business models, especially in publicly funded or hybrid ecosystems.
- Tailored sectoral approaches, acknowledging that context, stakeholder structure, and data types vary widely.

The foresight process not only identified desirable futures but helped align stakeholders around feasible, actionable steps, making it a powerful tool for shaping sustainable data-sharing ecosystems across Europe.

6 Reflection and Limitations

The DATAMITE anticipatory foresight study faced a couple of challenges and thus, limitations.

The main challenge concerns the **scope and characterization of the case studies** and the work of Task 4.4, as Task 4.4 differs from the scope of DATAMITE case studies. DATAMITE case studies revolve around technical challenges to be solved, while the work on Task 4.4 addresses sectors. Each of these sectors comes with specifics and details, also between countries. Therefore, case studies of Task 4.4 differ in relation to sectors, national legal and political contexts, as well as the data (sharing mechanisms) used. In addition, the sectors and the pilot partners within these sectors require different scopes of analysis: for example, the agri-food sector depends on various global and national stakeholders, while energy groups usually operate on a rather national level but are strongly involved with the public sector or government. Thus, while parts of these scopes have been met (also in combination with other tasks of WP4), the overall result remains limited in this regard due to the duration of the project. However, this diversity across stakeholders also challenges the implementation of practical activities.

First, the study's reliance on a systematic literature review, while comprehensive, may be limited by publication bias and the selection of peer-reviewed sources from 2013–2025. Emerging insights outside these parameters or grey literature may not be fully captured, which could affect the completeness of identified non-monetary benefit dimensions. Also, the strong emphasis on **academic and public sector contexts** is not unexpected, given the choice of databases, Google Scholar and Scopus, used for the literature search, both of which primarily index scientific and scholarly publications. Consequently, the findings reflect the discourse as it appears in formal academic literature and may underrepresent perspectives from industry, grassroots initiatives, or non-academic data intermediaries.

Second, stakeholder interviews and surveys - although critical for sectoral contextualization - are **based on a limited number of participants** (six interviewees) directly involved in the DATAMITE pilots. This relatively small and purposive sample introduces potential bias, including social desirability and selective emphasis on positive aspects, which may limit the representativeness of findings within and beyond the pilots.

Third, the participatory visioning and backcasting exercises reflect **early-stage, aspirational futures** rather than realized outcomes. While they offer rich foresight and strategic pathways, their inherently speculative nature means that identified recommendations and feasibility assessments remain provisional and contingent on evolving technological, regulatory, and organizational factors.

Fourth, the matrix-based thematic synthesis, while facilitating systematic cross-case comparison, depends on the **quality and consistency of coding and interpretation**. Differences in sectoral contexts, organizational maturity, and national policy environments may influence the comparability of findings, requiring cautious extrapolation of broader conclusions.

Finally, the overall timeframe of the DATAMITE project constrains longitudinal assessment. The study primarily captures **short- to medium-term perceptions and strategic intents**, limiting insights into the sustainability, long-term impact, and actual implementation of data-sharing ecosystems.

Despite these limitations, this study offers empirically grounded, practice-oriented insights that advance understanding of how trusted, interoperable, and sustainable data ecosystems can be co-created and operationalized across diverse European contexts.

7 The Future of Data Sharing Beyond Economic Value

The DATAMITE foresight process aimed at providing a broad picture on impacts of data sharing, including, but going beyond, the context of the pilots involved in the project. Based on literature review, interviews, explorative polls, vision analysis and feasibility assessments, the process allowed a comprehensive reflection on data sharing beyond economic value in different (practical) contexts. In the light of responsible innovation, DATAMITE included continuous and iterative reflection processes accompanying the infrastructure development.

7.1 Cross-section Synthesis

Several recurring patterns that cut across industries and methodological approaches are revealed by the triangulation of data from literature reviews, stakeholder interviews, pilot surveys, and foresight workshops. First, the creation of (non-monetary) value from data sharing is universally facilitated by **trust, data governance, and interoperability**. Organizations understand that sharing data only benefits society or the environment when the underlying governance mechanisms are transparent and widely trusted, regardless of the domain. Second, **organizational and cultural change continues to be a major obstacle**. The willingness to share data is influenced by perceived risks (such as privacy concerns), competitive pressures, and uncertainty regarding value distribution, even though the technical capability to do so already exists or is being developed.

Third, there are **significant differences in sectoral maturity levels**. While agriculture and urban services are still in the early stages of institutional adaptation, domains like energy and (medical) research have some established sharing norms. Lastly, there is only a partial alignment between theory and practice; practitioners recognize many of the non-financial positive impacts (like inclusion, empowerment, or ethical accountability) that are highlighted in the literature of the social sciences and humanities, but they are rarely incorporated into operational strategies; broader, potentially negative societal impacts are frequently seen as being outside of their purview. When considered collectively, these observations demonstrate that data sharing is developing from an

abstract idea into a distinctive practice, where advancement is at least as dependent on culture and governance as it is on technology.

7.2 Meta-level Reflection

Combining the theoretical research with the empirical findings, the DATAMITE foresight process itself provided valuable lessons about the important factors for data sharing in the near future. Bringing together the DATAMITE pilot stakeholders from diverse sectors revealed that perceptions of data sharing are shaped not only by technical readiness but even more by factors such as organizational cultures and disciplinary traditions. The DATAMITE foresight approach, combining structured evidence with participatory reflection on potentials and recommendations, proved particularly effective in bridging these perspectives. It enabled participants to articulate shared long-term goals while also exposing differing assumptions about control, responsibility, and benefit distribution. At the same time, the process emphasized the heterogeneity of the pilots, thus the high interdependence to the specific sectors. Nevertheless, this multi-method design fostered a high degree of mutual learning, turning the research process itself into a practical exercise and insights of responsible data collaboration. In this sense, the foresight exercise did not only anticipate future developments but also enacted the collaborative and reflexive practices it advocated.

The notion of value “beyond the economic” gained new depth through this triangulation of DATAMITE research. Across all phases, participants and evidence confirmed that the worth of data sharing cannot be captured solely through market indicators or monetization potential. Instead, value manifests through **trust, transparency, collaboration, and societal benefit**, dimensions that strengthen the legitimacy and resilience of data ecosystems. Recognizing these non-economic impacts **shifts attention from what data is worth to what data does** within a social framework. It reframes data sharing as a **collective good** rather than a transactional exchange, emphasizing reciprocity, fairness, and shared responsibility among actors. For policymakers, this perspective underlines the importance of designing governance frameworks that measures and incentivizes contributions to public value in the form of monetary benefits. For organizations, it highlights that sustainable competitiveness increasingly depends on their capacity to demonstrate ethical integrity, openness, and contribution to societal goals. In this way,

“beyond economic value” becomes not an alternative to growth, but an integrated pathway toward a more inclusive, trustworthy, and future-ready data economy.

Thus, non-monetary impacts of data sharing are a vast field. Therefore, we structured our research question about visions and their implementation in practice according to (a) impacts (i.e., benefits and risks); (b) changing practices in organizations; and (c) visions and feasibility in relation to data sharing to provide a comprehensive picture to capture the strategies and challenges, as well as the environments to be considered when thinking about adopting data sharing practices.

7.3 Recommendations

Despite sector-specific differences, several recommendations for policy and business can be formulated.

7.3.1 Policy Recommendations

Build Trust through Transparent and Inclusive Governance

- Establish ethical and participatory governance frameworks for data sharing.
- Ensure transparency, accountability, and fairness in how data is collected, managed, and used.
- Involve stakeholders, research, and civil society in decision-making to foster public trust.

Promote Context-Sensitive and Responsible Data Sharing

- Avoid “open data by default” mandates; assess risks, benefits, and fairness case-by-case.
- Promote sector-specific governance frameworks that take into account variations in value creation, stakeholder structures, and data sensitivity.
- Develop ethical safeguards and standards to prevent misuse, re-identification, and bias.

Strengthen Legal and Institutional Frameworks as well as SSH evaluation frameworks

- Align data sharing policies at the national and EU levels with transparent accountability systems.
- Establish compliance guidelines and certification programs for ethical data sharing.
- To strike a balance between openness, privacy, and justice, reconsider consent and access frameworks.

- Create assessment frameworks and metrics to gauge the non-financial effects of data sharing programs on society, ethics, and the environment.
- Encourage sector-wide harmonization of interoperability standards to enable legal, effective, safe, and international data exchange.

Support Equity and Benefit Sharing

- Make sure that the advantages of data sharing are distributed fairly, including monetary or social gains for communities and individuals who contribute data.
- Prevent underprivileged groups from being excluded or having their data exploited.
- Integrate fairness and justice into both public and private data-sharing regulations.

Ensure continuity through stable funding instruments and public-private investment models that sustain infrastructures beyond pilot phases.

- Enable Cross-Sectoral Learning and Collaboration: Encourage multi-sectoral partnerships (public, private, research, and civil society) to co-develop data-sharing ecosystems.
- Fund empirical, interdisciplinary research integrating technical, legal, and social dimensions of data governance.
- Invest in long-term capacity-building, professional training, and data stewardship skills to sustain responsible data sharing.
- Support empirical, interdisciplinary research to fill knowledge gaps on long-term societal and environmental effects of data sharing.

7.3.2 Business Recommendations

Develop Trust-Centred Data Strategies

- Recognize trust as a business asset, build it through transparency, security, and reciprocity.
- Implement ethical data management policies internally to align with broader societal expectations.

Create Incentive Structures for Participation

- Design non-monetary incentives such as reputation gains, access to shared insights, or collaborative innovation.

- Develop monetary incentives where appropriate, revenue sharing, efficiency gains, or data-driven service improvements.

Foster Organizational and Cultural Change

- Support data literacy and training programs to help staff embrace data-sharing mindsets.
- Adapt internal workflows and management practices to facilitate responsible data collaboration.

Innovate Business Models for Data Ecosystems

- Adopt flexible business models (e.g., data cooperatives, public-private partnerships) that reflect the diversity of data sources.
- Focus on non-monetary value creation, efficiency, innovation, and relationship building.

Embed Ethical and Governance Principles in Business Operations

- Integrate fairness, equity, and privacy safeguards into product design and data analytics pipelines.
- Use standards and certifications to signal responsible data practices to partners and consumers.

7.4 Further Forward-Looking Considerations

The insights generated through the DATAMITE foresight study point toward several directions for future action and policy development. In addition, there are some more considerations relevant for future development. First, there is a need to **translate non-monetary value dimensions into measurable governance indicators**, for instance, metrics for trust, inclusiveness, or ethical compliance that can complement existing economic performance frameworks. Developing such indicators would help business and policy makers systematically integrate social and environmental considerations into data strategies. Second, the findings indicate that a **continued capacity building and cross-sector learning** is needed to bridge differences in maturity and culture among sectors. Although data sharing is highly depending on the individual sectors, the creation of shared vocabulary, training resources, and communities of practice could support the scaling of responsible data-sharing models beyond individual pilots. Third, the foresight process underscored the importance of **institutionalizing anticipation**, embedding foresight and participatory reflection into regular policy cycles and corporate governance routines. This would

enable organizations and policymakers to continuously adapt to emerging trends, technologies, and societal expectations regarding data sharing policies and deriving practices. Finally, the DATAMITE approach demonstrates the **potential of combining empirical analysis with co-creative visioning** to inform European data policies. Building on this foundation, future initiatives could further align the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and the European Data Strategy, ensuring that the data economy evolves in a direction that is not only competitive but also socially trusted.

When combined, the DATAMITE foresight study's findings demonstrates that **social legitimacy and cooperative governance are just as important** as technological innovation to Europe's transition to fully utilizing data sharing for business and policy. Value creation encompasses trust, accountability, security, and the collective ability to use data for the public good in addition to economic return, as demonstrated by the integration of literature insights, stakeholder practices, and participatory visioning. These non-financial aspects will play a bigger role in defining the sustainability and competitiveness of data ecosystems as they develop. The process of foresight itself can serve as a catalyst for mutual learning, understanding, and proactive action, demonstrating how communication between practice, policy, and research can direct change in intricate socio-technical systems. The process of foresight itself can serve as a catalyst for mutual learning, understanding, and proactive action, demonstrating how communication between practice, policy, and research fosters direct change in intricate socio-technical systems. In the end, DATAMITE offers both proof and a strategy for how foresight can assist Europe in developing a data economy that is accountable, inclusive, and prepared for the future.

8 An Output for Practice: Enhancing Responsible Innovation through Reflection

8.1 Reflection Tool (DATAreflect)

During the pilot interviews (section 5.1) and the short poll in preparation for the foresight workshop in Aachen (section 5.2), a need for reflection was identified. Expectations related to the need (a) to better understand the possible benefits that can be used as additional added value while advertising their service; (b) for an introduction to benefits of data sharing beyond monetization to assist on data sharing culture change; and (c) to discuss the benefits and risks of data sharing, to accommodate internal data strategies to enhance internal and external data sharing. As solution, partners proposed a **guiding document for reflection/self-assessment** that could be used for a variety of sectors and consider the respective conditions of data sharing, including impact dimensions and related issues.

We drew inspiration from similar initiatives from a variety of sectors and application fields, such as Synthetic Biology⁶, or Trustworthy AI⁷. Thus, in addition to the general scope of the task, we developed a reflection tool for practice partners.

The tool – DATAreflect – is based on the foresight process conducted within the DATAMITE project. High-level categories and questions derived from the analytical categories of the literature review (eleven dimensions). In an iterative process, pilot partners (GIDITEK, OTE, E-REDES, HEDNO, WODR, CINECA) validated these categories and complementing mid-level questions and examples to ensure that the resulting aggregated questions remain valid and useful across different sectors. The tool can be found in Annex G.

⁶ Synthetic Biology Deliberation Aid: <https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/BBSRC-211221-SyntheticBiologyDeliberationAid.pdf>, listed as best practice example by RRI Prism project (<https://www.rri-prisma.eu/rri-tool/synthetic-biology-deliberation-aid/>) [18.12.2024]

⁷ Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment> [18.12.2024]

8.2 Reflection on the Issue of Gender Equality and Bias Awareness

Discrimination is a major issue in the discourse on artificial intelligence and automated decision-making. These applications are **potentially discriminatory** as societal perspectives on race and gender, including current discrimination, are inscribed these systems via technology development as well as data collection and systematization. Moreover, societal practice in relation to these applications plays a major role (Allhutter, 2019; Gebru, 2020; Mager, 2021), for example when as socioeconomically disadvantaged people tend to be discriminated against by these tools but are also more frequently subject to automated decisions and corresponding tools than people with better socioeconomic status (Gebru, 2020), or when social decisions are made based on automated recommendations by people not involved in their development (Allhutter, 2019; Mager, 2021).

For artificial intelligence and algorithms, **five types of discrimination** can be identified:

Negative biases may be reinforced by data-driven statements about race and gender. Here, a non-representative composition of developing teams may result in tools that do not meet real-world requirements and contexts. For example, automated recruitment processes that select job candidates based on characteristics derived from analyses may not correspond to real job requirements. As existing employees often failed these recruitment tests, such attempts have often been stopped.

Historic data may shape predictions and thus perpetuate existing social discrimination into the future. In the case of **automated recruitment processes**, tools were designed to predict the characteristics of suitable candidates based on historic data. Consequently, people facing historic discrimination, i.e., with characteristics underrepresented in the data pool (e.g., from certain regions, ethnic groups, women, people with disabilities, people from the LGBTQ+ community, or generally groups that were underrepresented in technology development) were further being discriminated against. Consequently, non-marginalized groups had better chances in the process, which, in turn, led to more distorted training data. In the case of ‘predictive policy’ (i.e., predicting who will commit crimes), these extrapolations of the future play a role as only some crimes that

had been committed had also been reported. Consequently, such tools reinforce existing inequality by primarily identifying areas where black people lived as crime hotspots.

Another example of potentially discriminatory decision-making based on historically biased data (categories) is the **automated recommendation system** of the Austrian Public Employment Service (AMS) ('AMS algorithm'). The AMS algorithm is designed to predict job seekers' chances on the labor market by sorting them into groups to receive access to different support measures depending on their predicted re-entering into the labor market in the short, medium, or long term. The AMS algorithm established correlations between the characteristics of job seekers (including age, citizenship, gender, education, care responsibilities, and health impairments, as well as past employment, contacts with the AMS, and the labor market situation at the place of residence) and their successful re-entry into the labor market. It used statistical methods to learn which characteristics were positively or negatively correlated with the short-term or long-term outlook and sorted job seekers accordingly into groups which were supposed to receive different education opportunities.

The expected benefits comprised an increased accuracy of the offers and increased efficiency in the counseling process by reducing the workload of the counselors, while critics argued that the system would perpetuate existing inequalities on the labor market. Here, the main problem was perceived to be the data basis and the underlying model of the algorithm, which represents a specific and highly simplified view of labor market opportunities as certain groups (e.g., women, older people, and people with disabilities) are generally predicted to have poorer prospects. Moreover, questions were raised about the selection of data that goes into such models and the question of whether historical data qualifies for making future predictions. The AMS algorithm also displays intersectional effects, emphasizing the political quality of the tool: if displaying several of the aforementioned characteristics, job seekers are classified worse, i.e., descent faster into groups receiving a reduced offer of support. Thus, the process of limiting opportunities reinforces itself. The AMS algorithm (based on statistical methods) does not provide any information about individuals, and thus, beyond group-level forecasts, doesn't show any causal relationships (only correlations). Moreover, events disrupting continuity in the job market (e.g., the COVID-19 pandemic) cannot be considered. Also, the application context of such applications matters, i.e., whether AMS employees advising job seekers are trained to use the AMS algorithm and whether they can change the automated classification. In principle, the grouping can be changed by AMS

employees since information about personal appearance, motivation, and other “soft skills” cannot be represented by the algorithmic model. However, this implies additional work – a contradiction to the efficiency considerations for applying the algorithm, and ignores the so-called automation bias (i.e., the fact that people tend to attribute a certain authority to automated systems, meaning that computer results are often not questioned because they appear ‘objective’).

Specific applications may be **inherently biased due to biased learning data**. For example, commercial classification systems frequently show systematic biases against skin types and gender, i.e., intersectionality, through higher error rates in recognition (light-skinned men: less than 1%, darker-skinned women: up to 35.5% (Buolamwini and Gebru, 2018). This indicates that social concepts of race and gender affect the design and use of AI systems.

Gender stereotypes may be reinforced as current social perspectives on race and gender are embedded in AI, illustrated by the example of generative adversarial networks (GANs/ML), which create pornography using photos of women available on the internet without their consent, or by automatic gender recognition systems for targeted advertising. The latter represent gender as a static concept without considering variations in representation, for example across different cultures. Since they are hardly trained with data on transgender or non-binary individuals, such individuals are often misclassified, resulting in consequences ranging from misgendering to public outings. Taking into account the high suicide attempt rates of misgendered individuals in the workplace (56%), these consequences entail serious effects on people’s lives⁸.

Power inequalities in (research) discourse may be reinforced by excluding marginalized groups due to the type of research that can interact with existing power structures. As a result, people from marginalized groups often remain excluded, while others (e.g., research) try to understand their perspective and speak ‘for’ them in discourse. Thus, issues of diversity, inclusion, or ethics need to be taken seriously from the perspective of those affected to avoid instrumentalizing their perspectives for large development companies or universities, and thus, ‘responsible washing’ of ICT.

⁸ National Transgender Discrimination Survey 2014: 56% of misgendered respondents in the workplace had attempted suicide.

Thus, as these examples show, **structural inequalities are encoded** by systematic errors and must be recognized as such. Moreover, the right to have a say must be reflected, e.g., by including marginalized voices in the development of AI systems, and by letting inclusive and diverse committees decide on their specific use.

In this sense, **gender** is one of the core dimensions for reflection of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) (Stilgoe, Owen and Macnaghten, 2013; von Schomberg, 2013; Owen, Von Schomberg and Macnaghten, 2021). As such, it played an important role in the DATAMITE project as reflected in the fairness tool developed as part of the DATAMITE framework. However, in the foresight process, the category of gender remained underrepresented. While the literature review addressed issues of discrimination in general, the issue was hardly addressed in discussions on non-monetary impacts. Considering that DATAMITE largely aimed at developing a data sharing infrastructure, rather than generating results based on specific data, this may not come as a surprise. Thus, reasons for this could be the high-resolution level and the broad range of data used by the DATAMITE pilots, which does not always include personal data. However, as downstream effects not rooted in personal data may arise, an active consideration of discriminatory issues (including gender) is key. Accordingly, the issue of discrimination (including gender) was included in the reflection tool (Annex G: Preliminary Version of the DATAMITE Reflection Tool ('DATAreflect')), especially since the issue of gender, and more broadly, of discrimination, has widely been discussed as major threat in relation to data sharing, and, eventually, artificial intelligence. Here, it is foremost the learning of algorithms and AI tools based on historic data that may lead to an amplification of discriminatory patterns from the past and extending them into the future or future decision-making (section 8.2).

On a consortium level, DATAMITE did not meet the requirement of a gender balanced consortium. To raise awareness on the issue of gender among pilot partners and to engage in-depths with the issue, Task 4.4 conducted an interactive workshop among project partners (section 5.2). In addition, more communication activities have been conducted and can be found on the DATAMITE Website (<https://datamite-horizon.eu/>).

8.2.1 Gender Equality and Bias Awareness Activity as part of the CM in Bilbao (M28)

As part of the DATAMITE project's efforts to increase awareness of gender bias and data fairness, a **short interactive quiz** was organized during the Consortium Meeting in Bilbao on 12th of April 2024 using the Kahoot platform. The session involved 40 participants from the project consortium and focused on recognizing key concepts related to gender bias in data collection, analysis, and digital tools. The quiz served both as an awareness-raising activity and as a diagnostic tool to assess the group's current understanding of gender-related issues in data-driven contexts.

8.2.1.1 Activity Description

The Kahoot consisted of seven questions addressing core topics such as:

- The definition of gender bias and gender data gap
- Examples of bias in real-world datasets (e.g., AI recruitment tools, medical research, voice recognition)
- The concept of intersectionality
- Historical impacts of gender bias across sectors like healthcare, transportation, and AI
- A contextual question about gender balance within the DATAMITE project (“What was the ratio between men and women in the last DATAMITE meeting?”)

8.2.1.2 Results and Insights

Overall accuracy across participants was 47%, with an average completion time of 12 minutes. The most challenging question, answered correctly by only 10%, was the one related to the gender ratio at the last DATAMITE meeting. This indicates limited awareness of gender balance within the consortium itself, suggesting that awareness in practical life remains low.

8.2.1.3 Participant Feedback and Ideas

After the quiz, participants could suggest ideas to further explore fairness and bias topics. Contributions included:

- Using the BIAS Project tools (<https://www.biasproject.eu/>)
- Applying a fairness tool to datasets
- Extending work on the fairness model

- Analyzing public data with fairness and bias tools and publishing the results

These ideas demonstrate an interest in linking awareness activities to practical applications, such as integrating fairness assessments into datasets and AI models used in DATAMITE.

8.2.1.4 Conclusion

The activity successfully engaged participants and highlighted both conceptual understanding and internal awareness gaps. Future actions should combine educational elements with applied exercises, e.g., piloting fairness tools within DATAMITE use cases and reporting on gender balance indicators. This would transform awareness into measurable progress toward inclusive and bias-aware data practices.

9 Ethics, Consents and Use of AI

Formal ethical approval was not required for this study because it did not involve sensitive personal data, vulnerable groups, or experimental interventions. All participants gave written informed consent before taking part in this research. The consent process included a full briefing on the purpose of the research, the use of their contributions, and the measures in place to protect their privacy. Consent was obtained with the clear understanding that all data would be anonymised by the ‘Safe Harbour’ method⁹. Participants were informed that they could withdraw their data at any stage by submitting a written request to the corresponding author.

Quotations and findings have been reported in a way that safeguards the identity of individuals and organizations involved. Ownership of co-created knowledge and data was managed under the terms of the project’s Consortium Agreement, which specifies rights and responsibilities for data use and dissemination.

An AI-based language model (ChatGPT, OpenAI) was used to condense selected text sections, improve phrasing and perform an English language check. To support the extraction of vision elements of E-Redes, Scispace was used. All material was reviewed and validated by the authors, and no personal or sensitive data were entered.

⁹ HIPAA Privacy Rule available under <https://www.hhs.gov/hipaa/for-professionals/special-topics/de-identification/index.html#standard> [21.11.2025]

10 References

- Allhutter, D. (2019) “AMS-Algorithmus am Prüfstand.” ITA-Dossier 043. Institute of Technology Assessment of the Austrian Academy of Sciences. Available at: <http://epub.oeaw.ac.at/ita/ita-dossiers/ita-dossier043.pdf>.
- Arvidsson, A. and Hällgren, D. (2023) “The Use of Open Government Data in Swedish Municipalities. In Relation to Creating Environmental Values.” Degree Project. Linnaeus University, Sweden. Available at: <https://lnu.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1772670/FULLTEXT01.pdf>.
- Bak, M.A.R. *et al.* (2023) “Towards trust-based governance of health data research,” *Medicine, Health Care and Philosophy*, 26(2), pp. 185–200. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11019-022-10134-8>.
- Bareis, J. and Katzenbach, C. (2022) “Talking AI into Being: The Narratives and Imaginaries of National AI Strategies and Their Performative Politics,” *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 47(5), pp. 855–881. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/01622439211030007>.
- Borgerud, C. and Borglund, E. (2020) “Open research data, an archival challenge?,” *Archival Science*, 20(3), pp. 279–302. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10502-020-09330-3>.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) “Using thematic analysis in psychology,” *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77–101. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>.
- Buolamwini, J. and Gebru, T. (2018) “Gender Shades: Intersectional Accuracy Disparities in Commercial Gender Classification,” in *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pp. 1–15. Available at: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v81/buolamwini18a/buolamwini18a.pdf>.
- Cheah, P.Y. *et al.* (2015) “Perceived Benefits, Harms, and Views About How to Share Data Responsibly: A Qualitative Study of Experiences With and Attitudes Toward Data Sharing Among Research Staff and Community Representatives in Thailand,” *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*, 10(3), pp. 278–289. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1556264615592388>.

- Colonna, L. (2020) “Privacy, Risk, Anonymization and Data Sharing in the Internet of Health Things,” *Pittsburgh Journal of Technology Law & Policy*, 20(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5195/tlp.2020.235>.
- D’Agostino, M. *et al.* (2016) “Social Dialogue and Scientific Production on Big and Open Data in Health: From Facilitating Surveillance and Preventing Disease to Fostering Behavioral Changes,” *International Journal of Public Health Research*, 4(3), pp. 14–22. Available at: <http://www.openscienceonline.com/journal/archive2?journalId=718&paperId=3255>.
- Dawes, S.S., Cresswell, A.M. and Pardo, T.A. (2009) “From ‘Need to Know’ to ‘Need to Share’: Tangled Problems, Information Boundaries, and the Building of Public Sector Knowledge Networks,” *Public Administration Review*, 69(3), pp. 392–402. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2009.01987_2.x.
- Destro Bisol, G. *et al.* (2014) “Perspectives on open science and scientific data sharing: an interdisciplinary workshop,” *Journal of Anthropological Sciences*, (92), pp. 179–200. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4436/JASS.92006>.
- Elbe, S. (2021) “Bioinformational diplomacy: Global health emergencies, data sharing and sequential life,” *European Journal of International Relations*, 27(3), pp. 657–681. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/13540661211008204>.
- Emigawaty, E., Adi, K. and Rochim, A.F. (2023) “Societal Impacts of Open Government Data Use,” *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 43(03), pp. 185–192. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.14429/djlit.43.03.18523>.
- Emmons, K.M. *et al.* (2023) “Data sharing in the context of community-engaged research partnerships,” *Social Science & Medicine*, 325, p. 115895. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2023.115895>.
- Etchegary, H. *et al.* (2023) “Public attitudes towards genomic data sharing: results from a provincial online survey in Canada,” *BMC Medical Ethics*, 24(1), p. 81. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-023-00967-0>.
- Funtowicz, S.O. and Ravetz, J.R. (1993) “Science for the post-normal age,” *Futures*, 25(7), pp. 739–755. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-3287\(93\)90022-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-3287(93)90022-L).

- Fusi, F., Zhang, F. and Liang, J. (2023) “Unveiling environmental justice through open government data: Work in progress for most US states,” *Public Administration*, 101(3), pp. 1088–1114. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12847>.
- Gebru, T. (2020) “Race and Gender,” in *The Oxford handbook of ethics of AI*. Oxford: Oxford University Press (Dubber, Markus D., Pasquale F., Das, S. (eds)), pp. 253–269. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190067397.001.0001>.
- Gessa, A. and Sancha, P. (2020) “Environmental Open Data in Urban Platforms: An Approach to the Big Data Life Cycle,” *Journal of Urban Technology*, 27(1), pp. 27–45. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10630732.2019.1656934>.
- Gunasekera, D. (2018) “Bridging the Energy and Meteorology Information Gap,” in A. Troccoli (ed.) *Weather & Climate Services for the Energy Industry*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 1–12. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-68418-5_1.
- Haberer, B. and Schnurr, D. (2020) “Open Government Data for Digital Services: Effects on Innovation, Competition and Societal Benefits,” *SSRN Electronic Journal* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3743648>.
- Hansen, H.S. and Schröder, L. (2019) “The Societal Benefits of Open Government Data with Particular Emphasis on Geospatial Information,” in A. Kö et al. (eds.) *Electronic Government and the Information Systems Perspective*. Cham: Springer International Publishing (Lecture Notes in Computer Science), pp. 31–44. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27523-5_3.
- Harmon, S.H., Caulfield, T. and Joly, Y. (2012) “Commercialization versus open science: Making sense of the message(s) in the bottle,” *Medical Law International*, 12(1), pp. 3–10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0968533212441887>.
- Harrison, T.M., Pardo, T.A. and Cook, M. (2012) “Creating Open Government Ecosystems: A Research and Development Agenda,” *Future Internet*, 4(4), pp. 900–928. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi4040900>.
- Hassan, L. et al. (2020) “A deliberative study of public attitudes towards sharing genomic data within NHS genomic medicine services in England,” *Public Understanding of Science*, 29(7), pp. 702–717. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662520942132>.

- Heacock, M.L. *et al.* (2020) “Sharing SRP data to reduce environmentally associated disease and promote transdisciplinary research,” *Reviews on Environmental Health*, 35(2), pp. 111–122. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1515/reveh-2019-0089>.
- Heumann, S. (2019) “Daten für alle, Innovation für wenige?,” *interface*. Available at: <https://www.interface-eu.org/archive/publications/2522> (Accessed: November 18, 2025).
- Hicks, D.J. (2023) “Open science, the replication crisis, and environmental public health,” *Accountability in Research*, 30(1), pp. 34–62. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2021.1962713>.
- Hodonu-Wusu, J.O., Noorhidawati, A. and Abrizah, A. (2020) “Malaysian researchers on open data: The first national survey on awareness, practices and attitudes,” *Malaysian Journal of Library & Information Science*, 25(2), pp. 1–20. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.22452/mjlis.vol25no2.1>.
- Huang, V.G. and Lyu, Y. (2022) “The interactive field of open government data: inter-administrative dynamics, trans-local networks, and local geopolitics of environmental data activism in China,” *Information, Communication & Society*, 25(16), pp. 2427–2446. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2022.2128848>.
- Kaaniche, N., Laurent, M. and El Barbori, M. (2014) “CloudaSec: A Novel Public-key Based Framework to Handle Data Sharing Security in Clouds,” in. *11th International Conference on Security and Cryptography (SECRYPT)*., Vienna/ Austria, pp. 1–14. Available at: [10.5220/0005010600050018](https://doi.org/10.5220/0005010600050018).hal-01263351.
- Kalkman, S. *et al.* (2019) “Responsible data sharing in international health research: a systematic review of principles and norms,” *BMC Medical Ethics*, 20(1), p. 21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-019-0359-9>.
- Ledvina, V.E. *et al.* (2022) “How open data and interdisciplinary collaboration improve our understanding of space weather: A risk and resiliency perspective,” *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, 9, p. 1067571. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspas.2022.1067571>.
- Liu, Z., Yu, Y. and Lei, Y. (2024) “Enhancing local governments’ environmental attention through open government data: evidence from China,” *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 31(12), pp. 18494–18511. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-024-32202-7>.

- Mager, A. (2021) “How fair ist the AMS Algorithm?” ITA-Dossier 052. Institute of Technology Assessment of the Austrian Academy of Sciences. Available at: [10.1553/ita-doss-052en](https://doi.org/10.1553/ita-doss-052en).
- McGuirk, P.M., O’Neill, P.M. and Mee, K.J. (2015) “Effective Practices for Interagency Data Sharing: Insights from Collaborative Research in a Regional Intervention,” *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 74(2), pp. 199–211. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8500.12098>.
- Miles, I. (2008) “From futures to foresight,” in L. Georghiou et al. (eds.) *The handbook of technology foresight. Concepts and practice*. Cheltenham [et al.]: Edward Elgar, pp. 24–43.
- Mohammadi, M., Rawassizadeh, R. and Sheikhtaheri, A. (2022) “A consumer-centered security framework for sharing health data in social networks,” *Journal of Information Security and Applications*, 69, p. 103303. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisa.2022.103303>.
- Nowotny, H., Scott, P. and Gibbons, M. (2001) *Re-Thinking Science: Knowledge and the Public in an Age of Uncertainty*. Cambridge: Polity Press (ISBN: 978-0-7456-2607-9).
- Owen, R., Macnaghten, P. and Stilgoe, J. (2012) “Responsible Research and Innovation: From Science in Society to Science for Society, with Society,” *Science and Public Policy*, 39(6), pp. 751–760. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scs093>.
- Owen, R., Von Schomberg, R. and Macnaghten, P. (2021) “An unfinished journey? Reflections on a decade of responsible research and innovation,” *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 8(2), pp. 217–233. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2021.1948789>.
- Parker, M. and Bull, S. (2015) “Sharing Public Health Research Data: Toward the Development of Ethical Data-Sharing Practice in Low- and Middle-Income Settings,” *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*, 10(3), pp. 217–224. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1556264615593494>.
- Pavone, P. et al. (2024) “A Literature Overview on Data-Driven Value and Accountability: Connecting the Private and Public Dimensions,” *Public Integrity*, 26(3), pp. 285–304. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10999922.2022.2163049>.
- Pawelke, A., Fetic, L., and Bertelsmann Stiftung (2020) “Daten teilen, aber wie?: Ein Panorama der Datenteilungsmodelle.” Available at: <https://doi.org/10.11586/2020079>.

- Polanin, J.R. and Williams, R.T. (2016) “Overcoming obstacles in obtaining individual participant data for meta-analysis,” *Research Synthesis Methods*, 7(3), pp. 333–341. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1208>.
- Popper, R. (2008) “Foresight methodology,” in L. Georghiou et al. (eds.) *The handbook of technology foresight. Concepts and practice*. Cheltenham [et al.]: Edward Elgar (ISBN: 978 1 84844 810 0), pp. 44–88.
- Prainsack, B. (2019) “Logged out: Ownership, exclusion and public value in the digital data and information commons,” *Big Data & Society*, 6(1), p. 2053951719829773. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951719829773>.
- Prainsack, B. (2021) “The meaning and enactment of openness in Personalised and Precision Medicine,” *Science and Public Policy*, 47(5), pp. 647–654. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scaa013>.
- Prainsack, B. and Leonelli, S. (2018) “Responsibility,” in B. Nerlich et al. (eds.) *Science and the politics of openness: Here be monsters*. Manchester: Manchester University Press, pp. 97–106. Available at: 10.7765/9781526106476.00013.
- Rahimzadeh, V., Knoppers, B.M. and Bartlett, G. (2020) “Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues (ELSI) of Responsible Data Sharing Involving Children in Genomics: A Systematic Literature Review of Reasons,” *AJOB Empirical Bioethics*, 11(4), pp. 233–245. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23294515.2020.1818875>.
- Roche, D.G. et al. (2020) “Open government data and environmental science: a federal Canadian perspective,” *FACETS*. Edited by T. Love, 5(1), pp. 942–962. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1139/facets-2020-0008>.
- Schattner, E. (2015) “Precision Medicine Will (Eventually) Lower Cancer Care Costs,” *Forbes*. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/elaineschattner/2015/10/01/precision-medicine-will-eventually-lower-cancer-care-costs/>.
- von Schomberg, R. (2013) “A Vision of Responsible Research and Innovation,” in R. Owen, J. Bessant, and M. Heintz (eds.) *Responsible Innovation: Managing the Responsible Emergence of Science and Innovation in Society*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd., pp. 51–74. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118551424.ch3>.

- Slobodova, O. (2020) “Motivations of civil society actors to reuse open data. Case study of discrete actors in Lyon,” *Bitácora Urbano Territorial*, 30(3), pp. 55–70. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15446/bitacora.v30n3.80740>.
- Stilgoe, J., Owen, R. and Macnaghten, P. (2013) “Developing a framework for responsible innovation,” *Research Policy*, 42(9), pp. 1568–1580. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.05.008>.
- Timms, P.D., Hillier, J.K. and Holland, C.P. (2022) “Increase data sharing or die? An initial view for natural catastrophe insurance,” *Geography*, 107(1), pp. 26–37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00167487.2022.2019494>.
- Udesky, J.O. *et al.* (2020) “Perceived Risks, Benefits, and Interest in Participating in Environmental Health Studies That Share Personal Exposure Data: A U.S. Survey of Prospective Participants,” *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*, 15(5), pp. 425–442. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1556264620903595>.
- Van Der Burg, S., Wiseman, L. and Krkeljas, J. (2021) “Trust in farm data sharing: reflections on the EU code of conduct for agricultural data sharing,” *Ethics and Information Technology*, 23(3), pp. 185–198. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-020-09543-1>.
- Waind, E. (2020) “Trust, security and public interest: Striking the balance: A review of previous literature on public attitudes towards the sharing, linking and use of administrative data for research,” *International Journal of Population Data Science*, 5(3). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v5i3.1368>.
- Waterman, L. *et al.* (2021) “A Mixed-Methods Investigation into Barriers for Sharing Geospatial and Resilience Flood Data in the UK,” *Water*, 13(9), p. 1235. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13091235>.
- Welle Donker, F. and van Loenen, B. (2018) “Societal costs and benefits of high value open government data: a case study in the Netherlands,” in. *21th AGILE International Conference on Geographic Information Science: Geospatial Technologies for All*, Lund/Sweden. Available at: https://pure.tudelft.nl/ws/portalfiles/portal/51431803/147_AGILE_2018_short_paper_147_SC_BA_of_HV_OGD_final.pdf.

- Zaghloul, E., Li, T. and Ren, J. (2019) “Security and Privacy of Electronic Health Records: Decentralized and Hierarchical Data Sharing using Smart Contracts,” in. *International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC): Cloud Computing and Big Data*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCNC.2019.8685552>.
- Zhang, A. *et al.* (2021) “Who will benefit from big data? Farmers’ perspective on willingness to share farm data,” *Journal of Rural Studies*, 88, pp. 346–353. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.08.006>.
- Zhou, B. *et al.* (2021) “ESCORT: Fine-Grained Urban Crime Risk Inference Leveraging Heterogeneous Open Data,” *IEEE Systems Journal*, 15(3), pp. 4656–4667. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSYST.2020.3023762>.
- Zhou, B. *et al.* (2022) “Dynamic road crime risk prediction with urban open data,” *Frontiers of Computer Science*, 16(1), p. 161609. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11704-021-0136-z>.
- Zuiderwijk, A., Shinde, R. and Janssen, M. (2019) “Investigating the attainment of open government data objectives: is there a mismatch between objectives and results?,” *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 85(4), pp. 645–672. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020852317739115>.

Annex A: Methods in Detail

This section describes the steps of the DATAMITE anticipatory foresight study in detail.

Explorative Stakeholder Workshop (M6)

During the DATAMITE plenary meeting in Athens (M6), Task 4.4 conducted a workshop (1 hour) with pilot partners and non-technical consortium partners. This workshop served to collect highly relevant non-monetary impacts of data sharing in the DATAMITE project. Based on a *Brainwalk*¹⁰ method, partners reflected on non-monetary impacts of data sharing in general, as well as in relation to their own organization and provided feedback on the proposed seven impact categories of data sharing (macro-economic, broader societal, customer-oriented, scientific, ecological, security impacts; risks).

Systematic Literature Review

To establish a solid conceptual foundation, a systematic literature review was conducted, addressing the following research questions:

- *What overarching non-monetary impacts (benefits and risks) of data sharing are identified across different domains, in particular in literature from social sciences and humanities?*
- *What specific impacts (benefits and risks) are observed within sectors, including those relevant to the DATAMITE pilots (telecommunication, energy, urban services, weather, agriculture)? Are there additional impact dimensions of data sharing to be identified in the literature and warrant inclusion in further analysis?*

Corpus of Literature

The search targeted peer-reviewed publications between 2013 and 2025 in Google Scholar and SCOPUS. It focused on literature from social sciences and humanities (e.g., critical computers studies) to avoid a too technical focus (i.e. focusing on technical feasibility, solutions and challenges) and to broaden the perspective beyond feasibility, system architectures or

¹⁰ Individual reflection on issues presented on flipcharts; partners added and commented via post-its.

infrastructure challenges. While some may consider this as a limitation, this selection ensured that the review did not merely reproduce technical visions or promises surrounding data sharing, but instead supported a more balanced and impact –oriented assessment.

To construct the search queries, we used an adapted version of the PICOC methodology (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes, and Context) as follows:

- *Population* refers to the specific group of individuals or subjects under the interest of the study. In the context of this study, we used specific sectors for representing stakeholders involved in data sharing – urban, manufacturing, retail, media, entertainment, finance, banking, energy, weather, agriculture, telecommunication, cultural, health, medicine, government, transport insurance, public services.
- *Intervention*: The intervention refers to the approach or technique applied in the empirical study. Here, the intervention involves applying specific impact dimensions to the analysis, leading to the use of keywords such as macroeconomic, environmental, scientific, societal, security, and risk.
- *Comparison*: The comparison component involves differentiating methods, processes, or strategies. Since there is no clear classification or relation between dimensions for data sharing no established classification or hierarchy of data-sharing benefit dimensions exists, making a comparative structure premature at this stage.
- *Outcomes*: Since empirical approaches or comparisons are not considered, no specific outcomes are defined in this component.
- *Context*: In our study, we considered the mechanism of data sharing as context, indicated by keywords such as non-monetary, open data or data sharing.

By combining the results from the PICOC approach, the different keywords for the initial queries were built (Table 3).

Google scholar	allintitle: ("macroeconomic" OR "Environmental" OR "Scientific" OR "Societal" OR "Security" OR "Risk")("Non-Monetary" OR "Open Data" OR "Data Sharing")("Data")("Urban" OR "Manufacturing" OR "Retail" OR "Media" OR "Entertainment" OR "Finance" OR "Banking" OR "Energy" OR "Weather" OR "Agriculture" OR "Telecommunication" OR "Cultural" OR "Health" OR "Medicine" OR "Government" OR "Retail" OR "Transport" OR "Insurance" OR "Public Services")
SCOPUS	TITLE (("macroeconomic" OR "Environmental" OR "Scientific" OR "Societal" OR "Security" OR "Risk") AND ("Non-Monetary" OR "Open Data" OR "Data Sharing") AND data AND ("Urban" OR "Manufacturing" OR "Retail" OR "Media" OR "Entertainment" OR "Finance" OR "Banking" OR "Energy" OR "Weather" OR "Agriculture" OR "Telecommunication" OR "Cultural" OR "Health" OR "Medicine" OR "Government" OR "Retail" OR "Transport" OR "Insurance" OR "Public Services")) AND PUBYEAR > 2013 AND PUBYEAR < 2025
SCOPUS	TITLE-ABS-KEY (("macroeconomic" OR "Environmental" OR "Scientific" OR "Societal" OR "Security" OR "Risk") AND ("Non-Monetary" OR "Open Data" OR "Data Sharing") AND data AND ("Urban" OR "Manufacturing" OR "Retail" OR "Media" OR "Entertainment" OR "Finance" OR "Banking" OR "Energy" OR "Weather" OR "Agriculture" OR "Telecommunication" OR "Cultural" OR "Health" OR "Medicine" OR "Government" OR "Retail" OR "Transport" OR "Insurance" OR "Public Services")) AND PUBYEAR > 2013 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "COMP") OR EXCLUDE (SUBJAREA , "CENG") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "SOCI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Data Sharing") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "International Cooperation") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Open Science") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Data Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Information Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Access To Information"))

Table 3: Keywords for queries

The search results were refined manually in a group effort to avoid a selection bias: a core team of four people screened the search results for indications for relevance in title and abstract. This ensured consistency in selection and reduced the likelihood of missing relevant SSH perspectives. Thus, from an initial pool of over 253 records, 40 studies were selected based on methodological rigor and relevance.

Literature Analysis

To provide a comprehensive overview on the selected literature, different analyses (quantitative and qualitative) were applied.

Column-based analysis

Moreover, the selected articles were read and summarized by all members of the core team. These summaries served as the basis for a structured coding process. Using **thematic analysis** (Braun and Clarke, 2006), the review expanded the initial framework of six impact dimensions (societal, ecological, security-related, scientific, business-related, and macroeconomic) to eleven (in addition: policy, ethics, law/regulation, organizational, technical, and cultural impacts; for more

details on regulation and technical aspects see the respective deliverables of DATAMITE). The selected studies were assigned to **different categories** (e.g., dimensions, sectors, target group of paper, data users, benefits, or risks and challenges), whereas multiple assignments were possible both within and between categories. A column-based content analysis was used to organize and synthesize the coded information to analyze the **co-occurrence of different topics** across the literature (see Annex B: Grid Charts/ Column Analysis). This task was carried out by one team member and iteratively refined through group discussions.

This final selection of dimensions informed subsequent interviews and visioning exercises, serving as a reference framework for stakeholder validation and scenario development, as well as the development of the reflection tool.

Qualitative content analysis

In addition, we conducted a qualitative content analysis on the summaries of the articles. In addition to the deductive coding categories outlined above, we strengthened the inductive element of our coding strategy by integrating additional codes. These codes provided more detailed insights in argumentations, contradictions and additional aspects not covered by the initial codes of the quantitative analysis, including topics such as assumptions shaping data sharing practices (see Annex B: Assumptions on Data Sharing), scope of studies (e.g., starting from social practices rather than technical pathways and solutions), or recommendations and best practices on how to share data in a responsible way (e.g., principles of responsible data sharing).

Semi-structured interviews with Pilot partners (M12-24)

Following the literature review, ZSI conducted semi-structured interviews with all pilot partners to validate the findings from the literature, and to identify weak signals in relation to data sharing practices of organizations.

Thus, the research question was (also see section 3.1):

- *How do practices change within organizations due to the (planned) introduction of data sharing?*

Hence, questions covered the organization's current and expected future practices of data sharing and their impacts on organizations' practices in general, as well as past and current consideration of non-monetary impacts and project-related aspects, e.g., motivation to participate in DATAMITE

and expectations for Task 4.4. To validate prior results, the interview questionnaire (Annex D: Interview Questionnaire) also covered questions about non-monetary impacts of data sharing in the respective sector.

The interviews were conducted online between August and October 2024 (one in December 2024) with pilot partners or other representatives in their organization and lasted between 30 and 60 minutes. The interviews were recorded and transcribed and a qualitative content analysis was conducted. The interviews were coded with MaxQDA and comprised codes related to categories above but included practice-related codes related to context of organizations, current practices and expected changes and lessons learned regarding data sharing.

Explorative Poll of Pilot Partners (M23)

As a next step, Task 4.4. validated the identified impacts (benefits and risks) in the extended circle of pilot partners by sending out a short questionnaire (Microsoft form) and discussed the results in a collaborative meeting with WP5 partners.

After having indicated their pilot study, the questionnaire consisted of three short questions: a rating of expected benefits and risks in different dimensions (derived from the literature review) on a 6-point Likert scale from very low to very high, and expectations of pilots for Task 4.4 (Table 4).

Poll for Pilot Partners on nonmonetary impacts and requirements for T4.4						
How high do you expect BENEFITS of data sharing in the following dimensions?						
	Very low	Low	Rather low	Rather high	High	Very high
Societal						
Ecological						
Security						
Scientific						

Macro-economic						
Customer and business-related						
Policy						
Ethics						
Cultural						
Organizational						
Regulatory						

How high do you expect RISKS of data sharing in the following dimensions?

	Very low	Low	Rather low	Rather high	High	Very high
Societal						
Ecological						
Security						
Scientific						
Macro-economic						
Customer and business-related						
Policy						

Ethics						
Cultural						
Organizational						
Regulatory						
What do you hope to gain from T4.4 for your daily work in your company? (Open Question)						

Table 4: Poll on impacts of data sharing in different dimensions for pilot partners

Backcasting, Recommendations and Feasibility Assessment (M23)

In preparation for the backcasting workshop, pilot partners wrote¹¹ short visions (timeframe: 5-10 years) outlining trusted, value-generating data sharing in their sector. Together with the results of the explorative poll (see Annex Annex D: Interview Questionnaire), these visions served as a starting point for the project-wide backcasting workshop, which brought together approximately 48 participants representing all pilots (and WPs). Participants collaboratively worked backward from their desired futures to identify:

- concrete actions and systemic interventions;
- structural enablers (e.g., policy reforms, capacity building) via recommendations;
- anticipated feasibility of recommendations.

Each group generated a set of strategic recommendations. Subsequently, participants estimated the likelihood of implementation of these actions using a 6-point Likert scale ('very low' to 'very

¹¹ Due to practical issues, the vision on meteorology was deduced from the interviews and validated by partners.

high’) supplemented by qualitative justifications, enabling critical reflection on both desirability and practical achievability within their contexts.

Annex B: Literature Basis - What are Impacts of Data Sharing in General and in Different Sectors?

The growing policy momentum behind data sharing - which encourages voluntary, non-remunerated data provision through trusted mechanisms - has significantly shaped the need for a deeper understanding of its practical implications. Against this background, a literature review was conducted as part of the DATAMITE foresight process to explore the **benefits, risks, and contextual dependencies** of data sharing across various sectors.

Rather than focusing narrowly on technical infrastructures or purely economic outcomes, this review seeks to capture the **broader landscape of data sharing practices**. It identifies patterns of expected and observed impacts and aims to situate these within the specific application areas most relevant to DATAMITE, such as telecommunication, energy, urban services, weather, and agriculture. It also examines how the **non-monetary effects** of data sharing - such as trust, transparency, inclusiveness, and empowerment - are discussed and evaluated in the literature. These dimensions are particularly relevant when considering *responsible* data practices, public engagement, and long-term societal value creation.

To support this aim, the review systematically maps not only the perceived advantages and disadvantages of data sharing, but also the **conditions under which its benefits are realized or fail to materialize**. This helps provide a nuanced foundation for the identification of dimensions relevant for the DATAMITE pilots and beyond.

Therefore, the literature review aims at responding to the following research questions (also see section 3.1):

- *What are non-monetary impacts (i.e., benefits and risks) of data sharing in literature, in particular literature from social sciences and humanities?*
- *What overarching non-monetary impacts (benefits and risks) of data sharing are identified across different domains, in particular in literature from social sciences and humanities?*

- *What specific impacts (benefits and risks) are observed within sectors, including those relevant to the DATAMITE pilots (telecommunication, energy, urban services, weather, agriculture)? Are there additional impact dimensions of data sharing to be identified in the literature and warrant inclusion in further analysis?*

General Overview on the Review

The literature reviewed largely assumes that data sharing holds significant potential for positive impacts if certain conditions are met (see Annex B: Assumptions on Data Sharing). Often, non-monetary benefits provide a general rationale for data sharing or are used to contextualize specific studies (e.g. attitudes on data sharing), and therefore, they are commonly found in the introduction and conclusion of articles. The review reveals a substantial number of studies addressing public awareness and implementation of data sharing in research contexts, but empirical investigations examining the **non-monetary benefits** of data sharing are scarce. Specifically, there is a notable lack of empirical studies that assess non-monetary impacts of data sharing systematically at a general level (RQ1). Rather, most publications center around specific topics, disciplines, or domains (related to RQ2 and RQ 3). However, this could be an artifact of the databases we used: we refrained from including technical databases such as IEEE, which may have offered cross-sectoral perspectives related to technical aspects (e.g., infrastructure or data used).

At the same time, this fragmentation indicates the maturity of the discourse on data sharing, which has moved from a general discussion to more focused discourses addressing specific areas.

Literature largely distinguishes between *different types of data* (e.g., medical, personal, geospatial), each carrying their own implications for privacy and data governance; accordingly, papers were assigned to different (*research*) *areas*. Much of the recent literature engages with *broader movements and specific phenomena* such as Open Data, Open Science and Open Government Data (OGD), or focuses on specific data holders or institutions (e.g. public authorities). Focusing on *areas* allows for a more granular understanding of benefits, risks and challenges.

Most prominently, *privacy* emerges as a dominant concern, alongside the need to avoid discrimination and to ensure fair distribution of risks and benefits of data sharing among different stakeholders. Privacy concerns depend on the data to be shared (e.g., genomic data, personal

data, etc.) and since some areas are linked to specific kinds of data, they require specific levels of privacy (for example medicine/health are always concerned with sharing genomic/personal data; agriculture is usually concerned with sharing geospatial/personal data).

Beyond these sector-specific privacy and ethical considerations, the literature **rarely addresses broader societal consequences** or structural risks related to data sharing. Instead, discussions tend to remain aligned with established policy frameworks, particularly those related to data protection and research ethics.

To capture this complexity, the final coding system consists of the following categories: *areas* in which data was shared, *dimensions* of data sharing (both established and new ones), *target groups*, data users (if specified), *modes* of data sharing, *types data* to be shared, associated *benefits, risks & challenges, resource allocation, and additional codes* (i.e., interesting aspects that occurred during the inductive analysis). We conducted a plot analysis to investigate the co-occurrence of topics, in particular impact dimensions, specific impacts, and sectors. In addition, an inductive coding allowed to provide a more detailed analysis of the literature corpus (Annex A: Corpus of Literature).

Areas

In this review, the core sectors of the DATAMITE consortium (telecommunication, energy, urban/public services and government, meteorology, agri-food sector/agriculture) are represented. In addition, they were complemented by other sectors to better align with the EU competition policy¹², i.e., manufacturing and retail, transport, finance (including insurance), media and entertainment, medicine and health, and culture, particularly, cultural heritage. However, only a limited number of these sectors turned out to be represented in our review.

The most frequently addressed areas (Table 5: Number of papers according to sectors) were urban/public services/government, followed by medicine/health and science/research, while less papers addressed the areas of energy, meteorology or agriculture, and only a few addressed

¹² This selection aligns with the sectors of the EU competition policy: Agriculture, Food & Fisheries; Arts, Recreation, Education; Tourism & Sports; Energy & Environment; Financial services; Digital & Media; Manufacturing & Basic Industries; Drugs and laboratory; Pharmaceuticals & Health services; Professional and other services, and Transport. Source: https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/sectors_en [1.10.2024]

telecommunication and archeology/cultural heritage. A reason for these emphases may be that in these areas data sharing is perceived as particularly promising or implemented rather easily, e.g., due to easy data collection (e.g. public institutions), public funding, or an (assumed) overall mindset of sharing of the area (e.g., the scientific paradigm of knowledge sharing).

In the review, three areas stood out in particular: medicine/health, government and public services and science and research in general.

In the context of **medicine**, the sharing of personal data, and in particular genomic data, is heavily discussed. One best practice is the public sharing of genomic data to contribute to medical progress, i.e., placing the common good above potential profit. Also, environmental health/environmental disease (i.e., considering living and environmental conditions in medical histories) was expected to benefit from data sharing (and integrated analyses) due to the enormous data requirements and complexity of the field.

In the context of **public services**, the rather recent phenomenon of Open Government Data (OGD) was discussed, which allows to explore new data sources for better administration.

Regarding **science and research**, data sharing aligns with scientific paradigms while efficient data sharing is supposed to further progress in complex fields (e.g., environmental research).

Therefore, the hope for being able to conduct new and more complex analyses based on shared data seems to drive the trend for data sharing. Besides, a certain tendency to capitalize ‘public’ data (or data that is publicly paid for) occurred since most papers addressed sharing data from public sources, especially in context of OGD and public research. In comparison, data sharing between businesses remains underrepresented.

Sectors										
Urban/public service / Government	Manufacturing, retail and transport	Media & Entertainment	Finance / Insurance	Energy	Weather	Agriculture	Telecommunication	Archaeology/cultural heritage	Science/ Research	Medicine / Health
64	0	0	0	7	7	7	3	3	18	60

Table 5: Number of papers according to sectors

Dimensions

In examining the literature on data sharing, it becomes evident that impacts are discussed not only in terms of specific application areas (e.g. health, government, agriculture) but also through **cross-cutting dimensions** that reflect broader societal, institutional, and political effects (Table 6). These dimensions help to frame the value and implications of data sharing in more holistic and context-sensitive ways.

To structure the analysis, an initial set of impact dimensions was derived from the DATAMITE foresight workshop held in Athens (section Annex A: Explorative Stakeholder Workshop (M6)). These included:

- Societal impacts, such as public engagement, inclusion, and transparency;
- Scientific impacts, including improved research quality, collaboration, and innovation;
- Environmental impacts, often related to improved monitoring and sustainability;
- Security, particularly with respect to data protection and system resilience;
- Business-related impacts, including market opportunities and innovation; and
- Macro-/socioeconomic impacts, such as growth, competitiveness, and public value creation.

As the review progressed, additional inductively identified dimensions were integrated to reflect themes frequently addressed across the literature. These included:

- Policy impacts, such as the political framing of data sharing and its role in governance;

- Ethical aspects, including fairness, discrimination, and consent;
- Cultural factors, such as values, norms, and attitudes toward openness and sharing;
- Legal and regulatory dimensions, with particular emphasis on privacy and data protection (which are mostly addressed elsewhere in DATAMITE (D4.5));
- Organizational implications, including institutional readiness, workflows, and governance models;
- Technical dimensions, covering infrastructure, interoperability, and standards (which are addressed in DATAMITE work packages 1-3); and
- Economic considerations, referring to general economic benefits or challenges (excluding in-depth monetization, which is addressed in DATAMITE D4.1).

As some dimensions (technical dimension, legal and regulatory dimension, monetization aspects) are addressed elsewhere in the DATAMITE project, they remain largely excluded in the analysis below.

While many of these dimensions overlap, they provide important lenses through which the literature articulates both the **potential and limitations** of data sharing practices. For instance, the **ethical dimension** is often treated not as a broad philosophical concern, but through focused discussions on privacy, equity, and trust, indicating a shift toward practical, context-specific challenges.

The **policy dimension** captures data sharing as part of broader political strategies or institutional agendas, such as open government or digital transformation. Meanwhile, the **organizational dimension** sheds light on how data sharing can alter internal processes and responsibilities, often requiring shifts in culture, coordination, and resource allocation.

Frequency of discussion across these dimensions varied. The **societal** and **scientific** dimensions were most commonly addressed, reflecting both the prevalence of academic studies and the widespread emphasis on social value creation. **Policy, organizational, and legal** considerations were also frequently mentioned, while **environmental, macro-/socioeconomic, economic, cultural, ethical, and security** aspects appeared less prominently.

Overall, this dimensional approach reveals that **non-monetary impacts** are central to the data sharing discourse, yet often remain **fragmented across sectors and disciplines**. Understanding how these dimensions interact, and which are prioritized in different contexts, will be crucial for evaluating and guiding responsible data sharing practices within DATAMITE and beyond.

Impact dimensions												
Macro-/ Socioeconomic	Environmental	Scientific	Societal	Business-related	Security	Policy	Ethics	Law	Organizational	Technical	Cultural	Economic general
7	8	17	20	11	2	15	3	11	13	13	3	5

Table 6: Number of papers per impact dimension

Nature of Data

In the review, different kinds of data were addressed, although not all explicate the data they relate to (Table 7). Studies that specifically address **personal data** (16), **Open Government Data** (OGD; 12) and **geospatial data** (5), and usually relate to questions of privacy in different fields. Personal data are addressed in relation to the health sector (e.g. genomic data, health data, environmental data of patients); OGD (i.e., registry data) in relation to the public service sector; and geospatial data in relation to the agricultural sector, as it renders individual farmers identifiable and is feared to contribute to geographical stigmatization (e.g., in case of diseases or pests). Especially Open Government Data is discussed as a new kind of data to be explored.

Thus, specific kinds of data raise specific privacy concerns; wider consequences of data sharing beyond privacy and research ethics are hardly discussed. Rather, some areas are closely linked to specific kinds of data (health sector to personal data, agricultural sector to geospatial and registry data).

Nature of data		
personal data	geospatial data	OGD
16	5	12

Table 7: Number of papers per nature of data (if mentioned)

Process and Modes of Sharing Data

Likewise, there seems to be a correlation between certain areas and process of data sharing. In the review, we coded ‘non-monetary’ ways of data sharing, ‘data sharing’ in general and ‘open data’ (or open access respectively). The concept of Open Data emerges as a prominent theme (19 papers). These discussions largely reflect broader debates that have shaped the domains of Open Government Data and Open Science over the past decade.

Interestingly, approximately half of the reviewed articles **do not specify the particular mechanism** or mode through which data is shared. This lack of detail may indicate one of two possibilities: (a) the specific way of data sharing is irrelevant to the topic of the article, i.e. open data and data sharing are difficult to distinguish, or (b) they relate to more targeted ways of data sharing (as assumed for large parts for the area of health). In addition, we identified several references to ‘big data’ as a well-established approach to knowledge generation based on large amounts of data, partly generated by data sharing. However, these discussions may increasingly be replaced and outflanked by more recent debates on AI. In any case, the full impact of such approaches (i.e., big data) needs to be investigated by spanning the boundary between private and public sectors:

“Although there is an increasing interest in big data, current studies tend to focus separately on either the private or the public sector, but rarely capture the big data movement as a boundary-spanning phenomenon.” (Pavone et al., 2024, p. 14).

In this regard, the broad variety of pilot studies of DATAMITE may support such an endeavor and avoid fragmentation and overspecialization of problems such as value processes and accountability ecosystems.

Target Groups of Papers and Users

The selected papers are predominately authored by researchers and scientists, with the majority of articles addressing research and science (38 out of 40) and a significantly smaller subset addressed to practitioners (15; e.g., public administration, especially in case of Open Governance Data). In contrast, the business sector and other stakeholder groups (2) are hardly addressed, although many of the papers are written to an undefined audience, therefore, may as well include these actors (Table 8).

In contrast to ‘target groups’, which can be analyzed for all papers, ‘users of data’ (Table 9) refer to actors that are explicitly mentioned as users in the literature. Yet, most papers consider them in an unspecific way. If users are mentioned, most relate to research and practitioners, e.g. in health, (19), while other user groups hardly appear (policy makers: 5; private companies: 3, stakeholders: 2, citizens and others:1).

Target groups of papers					
Researchers	policy makers/ public authorities	Companies	NGOs (e.g. NGOs)	Media	Other
38	15	0	0	0	2

Table 8: Number of papers per target group

Data users							
Researchers	policy makers/ public authorities	companies	CSOs (e.g. NGOs)	stakeholders	citizens	everyone interested	other
19	5	3	3	2	1	4	1

Table 9: Number of papers mentioning data user groups

Grid Charts/ Column Analysis

The following paragraphs present the results of the analysis. Grid charts illustrate how often specific topics appear across the reviewed studies, showing the relationships between dimensions, sectors and estimated impacts (risks / benefits).

Values at intersections within the grid represent the counts of a specific topic at the overlap of publications. Multiple assignments are possible, so the total count of facets in the top right of the charts represent the total count of topics, not the number of manuscripts reviewed. The numbers in the first row and last column show the overall count of topics throughout the analysis.

Moreover, one needs to consider that the charts only include manuscripts explicitly addressing the aspects of interest; too general manuscripts, or manuscript not covering these facets, are not included in the tables.

To explore the question of which dimensions and impacts relate to which sector, we first look at the intersection of **impact dimensions** of data sharing and **sectors** to address the question of the specificity of impacts of data sharing related to sectors (Figure 5). In general, among impact dimensions, societal impacts revealed the highest interest (16,3%), followed by scientific (11,7%) and business-related impacts (10,7%) before policy and technical impacts (10,2%). The high interest in societal impacts can be attributed to the vivid discussion on using hitherto non-available data and new ways of data sharing in the context of urban services and government, i.e., Open Governance Data, discussing new and evolving opportunities of data analysis. This is underpinned by the almost equal interest in policy impacts of data sharing (14,7% compared to 17,3%). Although the second prevalent sector was medicine, and societal impacts there ranked high (22,2%), research impacts of data sharing showed more frequently (27,8%). However, this may also relate to the debate on responsibility and safety of sharing medical *research* data, in particular genomic data, and the deriving impacts on people's lives, strengthened by links to other (newly evolving) research fields such as environmental health. The otherwise rather even distribution of impact dimensions across sectors underlines the specificity of impacts (and, related, kinds of data) once more, resulting in a fragmented picture of impacts of data sharing. However, the frequent references to sectors such as urban/public services and government,

medicine and health, science and research, energy or agriculture indicate the ongoing deep transformations, digital and otherwise, that these sectors are currently undergoing.

Figure 5: Cross-analysis sectors and dimensions

Second, when looking at impacts in more detail, i.e., specific benefits and risks, in relation to impact dimensions (and across sectors), this fragmented picture remained. Overall, benefits related to the societal (15,2%), scientific (14,7%), and policy (12,5%) impact dimension showed

most prevalently, followed by benefits related to the technical and organizational (9,9%), regulatory (8,0%) and business-related (7,6%) dimensions. This underlines previous findings underlying the dominant role of Open Government Data, medicine, and research more generally in the discourse of data sharing. Yet, governance-related benefits top the list, especially increased participation of citizens and stakeholders, empowerment and democratization (9.7%) and transparency (9,6%). Increased innovation in business (7,5%), accountability (7,1%), and collaboration among research together with an increased contribution to public interest and greater good (6,9%) follow, indicating diverse expected benefits across sectors. Interestingly, benefits of distributing resources rank the lowest (i.e., allocating costs 2%, saving costs: approx. 3,9%), indicating a low priority in the whole discussion on data sharing. This could also indicate the difficulty of monetizing data (cf. DATAMITE D4.1). Likewise, the consistently low number of benefits associated with security (i.e., 0,8%) indicates that data sharing needs conscious balancing between benefits and risks¹³.

Like benefits, risks appear relatively evenly distributed, yet mostly perceived as societal (16,5%), scientific (12,8%), policy-related (12,2%) or organizational (11,4%), followed by technical risks (9,1%). Lowest perceived risks are related to law (1,7%) and security (1,9%). In terms of specific risks and challenges, privacy dominates by far (24,7%), followed by issues of bias and discrimination (15,6%).

The fact that benefits outnumber risks and challenges in this analysis by far, this indicates a bias towards benefits in the literature corpus and gives rise to the assumption that the (scientific) exploration of (benefits of) data sharing serves as a preparatory act for *practices* of data sharing. In this light, it seems plausible that the discussion of risks and challenges largely remains on a general level (11,4%) or undefined (25,6%) as the focus of most publications lie elsewhere.

¹³ Risks have analyzed separately in more detail; therefore, the general line of risks remains blank here.

Figure 6: Benefits in relation to dimensions

Figure 7: Risks and challenges in relation to dimensions

Second, looking at **benefits and risks** in relation to sectors (across dimensions) strengthens the fragmented picture. Here, most benefits are identified in relation to urban/public services and government (32,5%) and medicine and health (29,7%), strengthening previous findings, and followed at a considerable distance by science and research (12,7%) and energy and agriculture (6,5%). Thus, for the sectors of urban/public services and government and medicine and health, the publications allow for more elaborate discussions. In the sector of urban/public services and government, benefits of increased transparency (11,8%) precede increased benefits of

participation, empowerment and democratization (11,2%), business innovation (8,8%), and accountability (8,1%), followed by access/accessibility, strategic use of data sharing, and benefits contributing to public interest/greater good (6,6%).

In relation to **risks and challenges**, the picture repeats itself, with discussions focusing on urban/public services and government and medicine and health. While privacy concerns account for 27,9% and undefined risks account for 22,5% of the risks altogether, 63% (and 61% respectively) of these relate to these two sectors; other risks and challenges remain rather sparse and wider implications of data sharing like potential shifts in economic structures are hardly addressed at all (3,8%).

Figure 8: Benefits in relation to sectors

Figure 9: Risks and challenges in relation to sectors

Research Gaps and Conclusions according to Impact Dimensions¹⁴

Macro- and socio-economic dimensions

We have classified the findings into four key areas of application: economic focus over societal objectives, mismatch between objectives and outcomes, challenges in engaging civil society, and barriers to cross-sectoral data sharing.

¹⁴ This analysis has been supported by UCC.

Economic focus over societal objectives highlights how OGD initiatives, despite their intended goals of fostering transparency and public engagement, predominantly deliver economic and operational benefits. In the study from the Netherlands, it is clear that while societal benefits are emphasized in policy discussions, the actual impact often favors private sector innovation and economic returns (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018). A similar finding is reported in another study, where open geospatial data has been used for economic gains, particularly in infrastructure development, with societal objectives remaining secondary (Hansen and Schrøder, 2019). This trend underscores the tendency of OGD initiatives to lean towards economic incentives, even when the societal goals are clearly stated.

Mismatch between objectives and outcomes emerges as a recurrent issue in OGD initiatives. Many programs cite goals like increasing transparency and promoting public participation, but the actual outcomes tend to favor operational improvements rather than societal benefits. This is particularly evident in a study that shows while many OGD initiatives achieve enhanced data accessibility, the expected societal outcomes such as greater public engagement and accountability often remain underdeveloped, especially at the local level (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019). This disparity between the goals and realized outcomes suggests that OGD initiatives need to better align their strategies with their broader societal objectives.

Challenges in engaging civil society further complicate the effectiveness of OGD platforms. Research from Lyon reveals that civil society actors, despite having the expertise to use open data, often struggle to connect meaningfully with OGD platforms. This disconnect limits the potential societal impact of OGD initiatives, as local communities' needs and motivations are not fully integrated into the platform's design or execution (Slobodova, 2020). This highlights a broader trend where many OGD projects fail to effectively engage civil society, diminishing the overall societal value that these initiatives can deliver.

Barriers to cross-sectoral data sharing represent a significant obstacle to the success of OGD initiatives. Research in the energy sector identifies critical barriers to data sharing across sectors, such as the lack of standardized communication protocols and technical constraints. These issues hinder effective collaboration, not only within the energy sector but also across other sectors where open data needs to be shared between public, private, and civil actors (Gunasekera, 2018).

Addressing these barriers is crucial for realizing the full potential of OGD in fostering collaboration and delivering both economic and societal benefits.

Environmental dimensions

We can classify the contribution of the non-monetary data within the environmental dimension into four key areas: transparency and environmental governance, civic engagement and environmental activism, challenges in data utilization and analysis, and environmental value creation through OGD.

Transparency and environmental governance remain a critical area where OGD is making an impact. In particular, the case study from China highlights how OGD improves environmental governance by increasing transparency and allowing for public scrutiny of local governments' environmental actions. This scrutiny ensures that governments are more accountable for their environmental performance, particularly in regions with active online political participation (Liu, Yu and Lei, 2024). Additionally, research from the Netherlands supports the idea that the availability of high-value datasets can encourage government transparency and lead to better environmental outcomes as policymakers respond to public pressure for openness (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018).

Civic engagement and environmental activism is another significant application of OGD, where open data empowers citizens and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to participate actively in environmental advocacy. In China, OGD has facilitated grassroots activism by giving NGOs the data they need to monitor environmental policies and hold the government accountable for its actions. This interactive dynamic between state and non-state actors allows NGOs to pressure local governments into improving environmental data disclosure, contributing to more sustainable governance (Huang and Lyu, 2022). In Sweden, OGD also enables local citizens to engage with municipal authorities on issues such as waste management and infrastructure planning, promoting more collaborative and transparent decision-making processes (Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023).

Challenges in data utilization and analysis present a major barrier to the successful application of OGD in environmental governance. Gessa and Sancha (2020) discuss the difficulties in transforming raw data into actionable insights for urban planning and climate change mitigation. Despite the availability of vast amounts of environmental data, its practical application is limited

due to challenges in data integration and the lack of tools to process and analyze this data effectively (Gessa and Sancha, 2020). Similarly, issues related to the sharing of flood resilience and geospatial data in the UK demonstrate the technological, privacy, and cultural barriers that hinder the effective sharing and utilization of OGD, which impacts its ability to contribute to environmental solutions (Waterman *et al.*, 2021).

Environmental value creation through OGD is a significant outcome where OGD has proven beneficial in driving sustainability. In Swedish municipalities, OGD has facilitated improvements in infrastructure planning, air quality monitoring, and waste reduction, illustrating the potential of open data to create substantial environmental value (Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023). Furthermore, research shows that OGD can stimulate innovation in environmental technologies and solutions by providing businesses and citizens with access to critical data, as seen in studies analyzing the digital markets and how open data drives competition and innovation for environmental purposes (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). OGD contributes to environmental sustainability by helping local governments and businesses make informed decisions that lead to better environmental outcomes.

In addition, studies show that in the agricultural sector, open data has enabled farmers to make better environmental decisions by sharing data related to farm inputs and outputs. This has contributed to sustainable practices and helped address climate challenges in agriculture (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). By facilitating the sharing of environmental data, OGD creates value not only for governments and businesses but also for local communities seeking to implement more sustainable practices.

Scientific dimensions

We can classify the contribution of the non-monetary data within the scientific dimension into five key areas of application: Open Data and Interdisciplinary Collaboration, Government and Institutional Policies on Data Sharing, Ethical and Privacy Concerns in Data Sharing, Societal and Environmental Impact, and Barriers and Incentives for Data Sharing.

Open Data and Interdisciplinary Collaboration emphasizes the power of open data in bringing different scientific disciplines together. When researchers from diverse fields like genomics, environmental studies, and health sciences share their data, they can solve bigger problems more effectively. This theme is clear in studies about space weather, where combining knowledge from

different fields leads to better predictions and solutions (Ledvina *et al.*, 2022). It's also evident in precision medicine, where data sharing across disciplines helps push forward personalized healthcare (Prainsack, 2021). The key to progress here is not just having access to data but ensuring that it is well-organized and interoperable, as highlighted in studies discussing FAIR data principles (Rahimzadeh, Knoppers and Bartlett, 2020).

Government and Institutional Policies on Data Sharing illustrates how governments and institutions are laying the groundwork for open data. Canada's push for open government data is a notable example, showcasing how policies are designed to make publicly funded research more accessible (Roche *et al.*, 2020). However, implementing these policies can be challenging. For example, at local and regional levels, it's often hard to see if the expected benefits, like increased transparency, are being fully realized (Mohammadi, Rawassizadeh and Sheikhtaheri, 2022). In Sweden, there's ongoing work to improve the coordination and infrastructure necessary to handle open access research data (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). It's a long journey from creating a policy to seeing the actual societal impact.

Ethical and Privacy Concerns in Data Sharing remain at the heart of the conversation about sharing sensitive data, especially when it involves personal health or genomic information. There are always questions about how to protect individual privacy while still making valuable data accessible for research. For example, sharing genomic data can lead to breakthroughs in healthcare, but it also comes with significant privacy risks. These concerns are particularly important when it comes to healthcare data, where ethical issues like informed consent and privacy protection are critical (Hassan *et al.*, 2020). Researchers must navigate these concerns carefully, as seen in several manuscripts discussing how to balance the benefits of open data with the responsibility to protect individuals (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019; Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020).

Societal and Environmental Impact shows how open data can bring about real-world benefits, particularly in public health and environmental issues. By making environmental and health data available, researchers and policymakers can make better decisions to improve public health and tackle environmental challenges like pollution and climate change (Heacock *et al.*, 2020; Rahimzadeh, Knoppers and Bartlett, 2020). For example, open data on environmental exposures helps researchers understand how pollution affects health outcomes, which in turn informs policy

changes (Udesky *et al.*, 2020). In lower-income regions, sharing public health data can improve the response to major health challenges, as long as it's done ethically and transparently (Parker and Bull, 2015).

Barriers and Incentives for Data Sharing explores the difficulties that prevent researchers from fully embracing open data. Privacy concerns and fears about misuse are big hurdles for many scientists, who may worry about losing control over their data or not receiving proper credit for their work (Kaaniche, Laurent and El Barbori, 2014; Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020). In some parts of the world, researchers face additional challenges, like limited access to resources and technology, making data sharing even more difficult (Mohammadi, Rawassizadeh and Sheikhtaheri, 2022). However, there is hope that creating clearer guidelines and offering incentives for responsible data sharing can help overcome these barriers (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).

Societal dimensions

We have defined the collaborations into two key areas of application: societal benefits, innovation, and economic impacts and public trust, accountability, and barriers to data sharing.

Societal Benefits, Innovation, and Economic Impacts

This cluster involves the role of open data in driving social progress, fostering transparency, and contributing to economic growth through innovation. Open Government Data (OGD) initiatives often focus on public welfare, promoting transparency and enhancing public services. Donker and van Loenen discuss how the availability of high-value datasets in the Netherlands promoted both transparency and innovation, resulting in improved public services and citizen engagement (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018). Fusi *et al.* highlight the role of OGD in environmental justice, showing that access to government data can help address disparities in environmental health risks, contributing to more equitable policymaking (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023). In public health, D'Agostino *et al.* underscore the value of OGD in fostering transparency and public dialogue, which is crucial for behavioral change and enhancing public trust in health data (D'Agostino *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, Slobodova's study emphasizes the role of open data in empowering civil society by providing access to information that supports decision-making and citizen participation (Slobodova, 2020). While societal benefits are often cited as key motivations, Zuiderwijk *et al.* note that these objectives are not always fully realized, with operational and technical benefits

more frequently achieved (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019). Waterman et al. add to this by discussing the importance of transparency in flood resilience data sharing, which enhances public understanding and decision-making in disaster-prone regions (Waterman *et al.*, 2021).

In terms of economic impacts, non-monetary data valuation fosters innovation across sectors. Welle Donker and van Loenen show how the release of government datasets in the Netherlands led to innovative applications of geospatial data, contributing to both economic growth and improved public services (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018). Haberer & Schnurr discuss how OGD can stimulate competition and innovation in digital markets by providing access to valuable public sector information that supports data-driven business models (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Fusi et al. further demonstrate how OGD in environmental justice initiatives can lead to innovative solutions for addressing environmental disparities (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023). Data sharing also holds significant economic value, as shown by Timms et al., who highlight its importance in industries like natural catastrophe insurance, where it enhances risk modeling and operational efficiency (Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022). Haberer & Schnurr further emphasize the role of OGD in fostering economic innovation by enabling businesses to develop new products and services in digital markets (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020), a sentiment echoed by Hicks, who shows how open science and data sharing help address the replication crisis in environmental health research (Hicks, 2023).

Public Trust, Accountability, and Barriers to Data Sharing

This cluster addresses the importance of building public trust, ensuring accountability in data-sharing processes, and overcoming the various barriers to effective data exchange. Public trust is a key element in supporting data-sharing initiatives, especially when dealing with sensitive data. Waind et al. stress that trust in these initiatives depends on maintaining both privacy and transparency, particularly in the context of health data research (Waind, 2020). Fusi et al. also argue that OGD initiatives in environmental justice must prioritize accessibility and usability of data to build trust among affected communities (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023). Similarly, Pavone et al. highlight the need for trust in data governance, particularly in cross-sector data sharing between public and private entities (Pavone *et al.*, 2024). Etchegary et al. reveal public concerns about genomic data sharing, particularly regarding privacy and unauthorized access by government and commercial entities (Etchegary *et al.*, 2023), while Udesky et al. emphasize that

privacy concerns remain significant even among those generally willing to share environmental health data (Udesky *et al.*, 2020). Pavone *et al.* reiterate that public trust is essential for the successful implementation of data-sharing policies, especially when personal or sensitive data is involved (Pavone *et al.*, 2024).

However, several barriers prevent effective data sharing. Waterman *et al.* discuss challenges related to geospatial and flood resilience data, highlighting privacy concerns, technological limitations, and organizational barriers as key obstacles (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). Pavone *et al.* identify the lack of harmonized standards between public and private sectors, along with concerns over data privacy, as significant barriers that hinder collaborative innovation (Pavone *et al.*, 2024). Emmons *et al.* focus on the need for community engagement to address concerns around data ownership and privacy, ensuring that data-sharing benefits are equitably distributed (Emmons *et al.*, 2023). Borgerud & Borglund add to this by discussing how archival challenges and a lack of standardized frameworks for data preservation complicate research data sharing (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). Parker & Bull highlight governance and ethical issues in sharing biomedical research data, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where infrastructural and regulatory barriers are prevalent (Parker and Bull, 2015). McGuirk *et al.* identify governance, risk management, and legal complexities as further obstacles to interagency data sharing in regional government interventions (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015). These studies collectively emphasize the importance of overcoming these multifaceted barriers to achieve the full potential of data sharing.

Business dimensions

We have defined the classification into five key areas of application: Open Government Data (OGD) for societal and business use, Data Sharing in Public and Private Sectors, Value in Big Data and Data-Driven Business Models, Accountability and Public Value, and Technological Barriers to Data Sharing.

Open Government Data (OGD) for societal and business use has been further explored through various manuscripts. OGD aims to enhance transparency, participation, and innovation, but research suggests that the outcomes often differ from these objectives. For example, a study found that the benefits of OGD initiatives often align more with operational and technical improvements rather than societal or economic goals (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).

Another perspective emphasizes that while OGD is framed as a tool for societal transformation, its benefits are more often reflected in improved government efficiency and data accessibility, not in fostering widespread innovation or public trust (Emigawaty, Adi and Rochim, 2023). Additionally, the challenge of fully realizing the intended transparency is underscored by the gap between the objectives and the actual benefits observed.

Data Sharing in Public and Private Sectors continues to be a critical area for collaboration. The energy and meteorology sectors, for example, illustrate how data sharing can enhance operational efficiency, especially in managing climate variability and optimizing energy production. The sharing of weather data is essential for mitigating risks from extreme weather events and improving the integration of renewable energy sources (Gunasekera, 2018). However, significant barriers remain, such as the proprietary nature of data and confidentiality concerns, which complicate the balance between transparency and protecting commercial interests (Gunasekera, 2018). In the insurance industry, especially for natural catastrophes, the ability to share risk and loss data is crucial for resilience planning, but regulatory and commercial obstacles often prevent effective collaboration (Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022). Similarly, in flood resilience efforts, participants from both public and private sectors face challenges in sharing sensitive geospatial data due to governance constraints, despite the potential benefits for improving community resilience (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). Another manuscript underscores the global health sector, where data sharing during health crises, such as pandemics, is hampered by ethical, legal, and logistical challenges, hindering rapid response efforts (Elbe, 2021).

Value in Big Data and Data-Driven Business Models is a recurring theme, particularly in industries like agriculture and energy. In agriculture, the aggregation of farm data holds great potential for enhancing efficiency and sustainability, but there are ongoing trust issues between data owners (such as farmers) and data aggregators. Stakeholders need to perceive clear value and fairness in the exchange of data for these collaborations to succeed (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). Similarly, the energy sector relies heavily on big data from meteorological sources for optimizing real-time energy production and distribution, but challenges arise due to the necessity for trust and transparency between private companies and data providers (Gunasekera, 2018). The development of data-driven business models is contingent on fostering strong collaboration across sectors, where stakeholders must trust that they are receiving fair value from their data contributions.

Accountability and Public Value has been reinforced by insights from the various manuscripts. The role of OGD in enhancing public accountability is well-documented, but there remains skepticism about its actual impact on transparency and public trust (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019). In research settings, open access to research data is seen as a means of promoting transparency, but infrastructural, organizational, and policy barriers limit the extent to which this is fully realized (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). Moreover, the push toward open data governance models, particularly within public research institutions, faces significant practical challenges. While the concept of making data accessible holds public value, these initiatives often fall short due to inadequate resources and policy ambiguity.

Technological Barriers to Data Sharing are consistently cited as a limiting factor across sectors. From energy to agriculture, the inability to standardize data formats and integrate diverse datasets hampers effective collaboration. In the energy sector, for instance, enhancing data-sharing practices between meteorological services and energy providers is crucial for improving efficiency and forecasting accuracy, but technical and regulatory challenges prevent seamless data flow (Gunasekera, 2018). Similarly, in the context of OGD, the lack of standardized data-sharing platforms and systems hinders the broader goals of transparency and collaboration, limiting the societal benefits of such initiatives (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019). In other sectors, like natural catastrophe insurance, the technical challenges of integrating and sharing diverse datasets further compound the difficulty of creating a more resilient risk management framework (Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022).

Security dimension

After analyzing the provided manuscripts, we identified three key areas of application: security data sharing, sector data exchange, and emerging trends and solutions for data collaboration.

Security data sharing emphasizes the importance of sharing sensitive information, especially in situations where global threats demand coordinated efforts. Despite its value in preventing crises, data is often withheld due to political and economic concerns, which can slow down response efforts. The non-monetary value of sharing critical data lies in its ability to save lives and manage crises effectively, showing how delays can significantly impact global security (Elbe, 2021).

Sector data exchange focuses on the growing necessity for real-time data sharing within industries to ensure smooth operations and risk mitigation. Sharing operational or environmental

data becomes crucial for sectors that rely on timely information to adapt and respond to changing conditions. This exchange holds non-monetary value by enhancing stability, improving efficiency, and reducing risks across various industries (Gunasekera, 2018).

Emerging trends and solutions for data collaboration highlight the shift towards secure, regulated frameworks that enable smoother sharing of valuable data. These new models ensure that contributors maintain control and recognition, while addressing concerns like intellectual property and competitive disadvantage. Platforms with structured data access agreements help overcome barriers, fostering trust and more efficient exchanges, particularly during crises when fast data flow is critical (Gunasekera, 2018; Elbe, 2021).

Policy dimension

we have defined the collaborations into three key areas of application: environmental management and governance, societal engagement and transparency, and economic value and innovation. The incorporation of new manuscripts adds depth to these categories, ensuring that all relevant data are included.

Environmental management and governance emerge as a critical area where Open Government Data (OGD) is actively enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of environmental policies. In multiple case studies, the utilization of OGD has helped local and national governments align their actions with global environmental goals. For example, in China, OGD has contributed significantly to raising environmental awareness at the local government level, demonstrating that the implementation of national environmental strategies can be directly tied to the effective use of open data systems. This has resulted in improved local policy frameworks and governance systems that prioritize environmental protection and resource management (Liu, Yu and Lei, 2024). Similarly, in Sweden, the municipalities have used OGD to support sustainable urban planning, resource minimization, and waste management, which directly ties into broader environmental goals such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The municipalities' ability to monitor environmental conditions and engage with stakeholders shows the important role OGD plays in facilitating real-time decision-making (Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023). The use of OGD in managing flood resilience in the UK further highlights how data-sharing initiatives enhance disaster response and urban planning, allowing better governance and environmental protection (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, the Spatial Data Analysis Project in Australia

illustrates how interagency collaboration using spatial data can effectively address social vulnerability and environmental challenges, reinforcing the importance of data-sharing protocols in enhancing governance (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015).

Societal engagement and transparency are another key area where OGD initiatives show a transformative impact. The opening up of data has fostered greater civic participation and enhanced transparency between governments and citizens. This is particularly evident in countries like the Netherlands and Indonesia, where OGD platforms have empowered citizens to participate in the policymaking process by providing access to critical government data. In the Netherlands, this increased transparency has led to better governance outcomes, as citizens are more informed and engaged in discussions around public policies and environmental protection (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018). In Indonesia, the use of OGD has significantly promoted public engagement, enabling citizens to be part of decision-making processes, especially in areas concerning socio-economic development and public services (Roche *et al.*, 2020). These examples underline the growing importance of transparency and civic empowerment as governments increasingly rely on OGD to involve the public in shaping policies. However, research shows that there are challenges in achieving these societal benefits, particularly at the local level, where the mismatch between objectives and outcomes is evident, with many OGD initiatives failing to meet their intended transparency goals (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).

Economic value and innovation is the third key area of application where OGD is driving significant changes. Governments worldwide have recognized the economic potential of open data in spurring innovation and fostering competition in the digital economy. For instance, studies from the EU and Canada highlight how OGD can unlock new business opportunities by providing free access to valuable public sector data that can be reused by businesses, particularly small and medium enterprises (SMEs), to innovate and create new products and services (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020; Roche *et al.*, 2020). This trend is further evidenced in Sweden, where the reuse of open environmental data has helped foster innovation in sustainable business models and public service improvements (Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023). Additionally, in the field of healthcare, open data sharing has been pivotal in driving innovations such as precision medicine, where personal and clinical data sharing enhances healthcare delivery (Prainsack, 2021). However, these developments are not without challenges, as privacy concerns and data

protection issues need to be carefully managed. In particular, the tension between maximizing the economic potential of OGD and ensuring that data privacy is maintained presents a significant policy dilemma (Udesky *et al.*, 2020).

Ethical dimension

we have defined the collaborations into three key areas of application: societal benefits and value, trust and engagement, and community involvement.

The first area, **societal benefits and value**, emphasizes the role of data sharing in advancing public health outcomes. Data sharing should prioritize collective societal benefits rather than merely serving institutional objectives. This perspective highlights the importance of community-engaged approaches that ensure research yields tangible benefits for the communities involved (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019).

In the second area, **trust and engagement**, fostering trust within the data governance framework emerges as crucial. The critique of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) indicates that stringent compliance may destabilize trust relationships among researchers and the public. Establishing public trust is essential for the success of data-sharing initiatives, necessitating transparency and ethical practices that encourage stakeholder involvement (Bak *et al.*, 2023).

The third area, **community involvement**, signifies a shift towards inclusive research practices. Engaging communities in the research process is imperative, as they should have a voice in determining how their data is used. This approach ensures that research outcomes reflect the interests and needs of the communities contributing data, advocating for respect for individual and group rights (Emmons *et al.*, 2023).

Regulatory dimension

Privacy Concerns and Data Sharing

Across the manuscripts, privacy emerges as a key concern, particularly with the rise of data-sharing initiatives. Bak *et al.* discuss the GDPR and its impact on health data research, highlighting that while the regulation strengthens privacy protection, it can also create barriers to research when data is overly restricted (Bak *et al.*, 2023). This is echoed in Colonna's examination of the risks involved in anonymization, particularly within the healthcare sector, where there are still significant challenges in preventing re-identification (Colonna, 2020).

In the context of open government data, Haberer and Schnurr note that while open data initiatives aim to increase transparency and foster innovation, there are often privacy trade-offs, particularly concerning personal data from the private sector. They emphasize the importance of legal safeguards to protect individuals while allowing the public sector to open its data (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Similarly, Waterman et al. focus on geospatial and flood resilience data in the UK, pointing out how privacy and security concerns inhibit data sharing between public and private sector organizations (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). The balance between accessibility and privacy is a recurring theme, where privacy concerns are seen as a hindrance to the broader use of non-monetary data, especially in sectors that rely on sensitive information.

Ethical and Legal Frameworks for Data Use

The legal and ethical considerations around data use are central to discussions in these manuscripts. The GDPR remains a cornerstone of the regulatory framework, as highlighted by Bak et al., who observe that data protection regulations can lead to a bureaucratic focus that overshadows substantive ethical reflection in health data governance (Bak *et al.*, 2023). Rahimzadeh et al. provide further insights into the legal and ethical complexities of genomic data sharing, especially involving children, stressing the need for robust consent mechanisms to safeguard against the misuse of sensitive data (Rahimzadeh, Knoppers and Bartlett, 2020).

In the open government data space, Haberer and Schnurr emphasize that policy initiatives, like the EU's Open Data Directive, have been instrumental in shaping the legal landscape for data reuse. However, they caution that without clear legal structures to define the use of different data domains, such initiatives could lead to unintended consequences, such as stifling competition or innovation (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Zuiderwijk et al. add to this discussion by highlighting the mismatch between the objectives of open government data initiatives and their actual outcomes, suggesting that legal frameworks need to be better aligned with the practical goals of transparency and accountability (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).

In the context of flood resilience data, Waterman et al. point out that legal and technological barriers often prevent effective data sharing. They argue that more robust legal frameworks are needed to enable the sharing of critical geospatial data between organizations without compromising privacy or security (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). This is consistent with Timms et al., who discuss how regulatory frameworks in the insurance industry must adapt to enable better

data sharing while protecting commercially sensitive information (Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022).

Organizational dimension

We have categorized the key areas of non-monetary data valuation in the organizational dimension into four core areas: data sharing and collaboration, technological integration, privacy and ethical concerns, and barriers to data management and sharing.

Data sharing and collaboration remains a central theme across various organizational dimensions, particularly when institutions work toward common goals. Several manuscripts, including those analyzing open government data (OGD) initiatives, emphasize that organizations increasingly adopt data-sharing frameworks to enhance transparency, accountability, and interagency cooperation. For example, the Spatial Data Analysis Project (SDAP) underscores how dialogue between agencies and the establishment of communities of practice are essential for fostering effective interagency data sharing (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015). Furthermore, the use of OGD in initiatives to promote collaboration, as outlined in global case studies, demonstrates the potential benefits for transparency and participation in government processes (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019). However, while operational and technical benefits are most frequently realized, challenges in achieving societal benefits, such as enhanced public trust and transparency, remain significant (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).

Technological integration is essential in maximizing the potential of data within organizational contexts. Smart city initiatives, for instance, rely on big data technologies to optimize urban governance and sustainability efforts (Gessa and Sancha, 2020). Similarly, in public health and agricultural sectors, the integration of big data tools has proven critical for aggregating large datasets to enhance decision-making and operational efficiency (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). The integration of technology into organizational systems is a recurring theme, particularly in digital agriculture and smart governance, where technological tools are essential for managing and leveraging data efficiently. However, technological barriers, such as outdated systems and insufficient infrastructure, still hinder many organizations from fully integrating advanced data management tools (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). In the context of open government data, initiatives often face technological challenges, where the mismatch between objectives (such as

transparency and innovation) and results is tied to inadequate technological infrastructure (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).

Privacy and ethical concerns are pervasive in the discussion of organizational data management, particularly regarding sensitive and personal data. Many manuscripts discuss the delicate balance organizations must maintain between promoting data sharing and ensuring privacy. In agriculture, for example, farmers are reluctant to share data unless clear privacy safeguards are in place (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). In public health, privacy concerns around personal health data remain a significant barrier, despite the recognized value of shared data for broader societal health outcomes (Zhou *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, interagency collaborations in the public sector face challenges in protecting sensitive information while promoting data sharing, particularly in contexts where institutional trust is fragile (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015). This tension is also evident in the case of open government data, where the goals of transparency and public engagement often conflict with privacy regulations and ethical concerns (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).

Barriers to data management and sharing continue to pose significant challenges for organizations, as highlighted in the provided manuscripts. Organizational silos, legal restrictions, and political barriers are frequently cited as obstacles to effective data sharing. For instance, interagency collaboration in Australia, discussed in the SDAP, reveals the complexities involved in overcoming these barriers through the creation of shared protocols and communities of practice (McGuirk, O'Neill and Mee, 2015). Additionally, legal and policy frameworks surrounding data sharing, particularly in research-driven and public sector organizations, often lag behind the growing need for more flexible and collaborative data-sharing practices (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). The mismatch between the objectives of open government data initiatives and the actual results further highlights the need for better alignment of policy frameworks with organizational practices (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).

Technical dimension

We have classified the insights into five key areas of application: Data Infrastructure and Accessibility, Data Interoperability and Standards, Data Analytics and Integration, Technological Barriers and Solutions, and Privacy and Security in Data Sharing.

Data Infrastructure and Accessibility continues to be a dominant theme. The Canadian biodiversity data initiatives emphasize how data systems need to be structured to make environmental data readily accessible to researchers and decision-makers alike. They highlight the need for technical advancements in open data platforms that improve real-time accessibility for monitoring biodiversity and supporting conservation efforts (Roche *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, the Dutch government has implemented a national open data agenda, where infrastructure is key to supporting the publication of machine-readable datasets in the public sector, fostering innovation by making government-held data more accessible (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018). This reinforces the critical role infrastructure plays in data usability across multiple sectors, especially in large-scale environmental projects and governmental initiatives. The analysis of urban data in smart cities, as mentioned in Gessa and Sancha (2020), further underscores the importance of technical systems in streamlining data access and its efficient use in urban planning.

Data Interoperability and Standards is another critical challenge, as highlighted by the difficulties in integrating data from multiple sectors, such as environmental monitoring and public governance. Flood resilience studies in the UK have demonstrated how discrepancies in data standards can lead to inefficiencies in data sharing between different stakeholders, inhibiting effective decision-making and disaster preparedness (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, the exploration of interoperability in environmental health research reveals the pressing need for uniform data formats across datasets to facilitate smoother integration across disciplines (Colonna, 2020). In cases like the European geospatial data system for flood management, technical advancements in ensuring compatibility across platforms and regions have been slow, exacerbating the technical challenges associated with data harmonization (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018). The analysis of natural disaster risks by insurance companies also depends heavily on data interoperability to model risks accurately, as seen in the growing interest in the use of standardized environmental and geospatial data in the insurance industry (Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022).

Data Analytics and Integration are crucial in maximizing the value of non-monetary data. Many manuscripts discuss the integration of various data types, especially in fields like environmental health and public sector governance. For example, machine learning techniques and big data analytics are increasingly being applied in space weather prediction, combining environmental, atmospheric, and solar data to improve the accuracy of disaster prediction models (Ledvina *et al.*,

2022). Similarly, in the health sector, data integration allows for a comprehensive understanding of environmental exposures and their effects on population health, where advanced algorithms help identify patterns in vast datasets (Ledvina *et al.*, 2022). The insurance industry has also begun integrating climate and geospatial data into their risk models to better understand the potential impacts of climate change on their portfolios (Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022). Advanced data analytics and integration techniques, therefore, play a pivotal role in extracting actionable insights from complex datasets across these sectors.

Technological Barriers and Solutions are frequently highlighted in the manuscripts, particularly in relation to outdated systems that impede effective data sharing. In the UK flood resilience case, legacy systems and outdated digital tools are significant obstacles, preventing the efficient use of geospatial and environmental data for disaster preparedness (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). In the context of open data portals, several manuscripts point to the need for more advanced technical systems to handle the increasing volume and complexity of data, particularly as open data initiatives expand globally (Gessa and Sancha, 2020). For example, the European geospatial data-sharing system must overcome technical hurdles to provide real-time data access for disaster preparedness and response (Heacock *et al.*, 2020). These barriers indicate that further investments in technical systems and solutions are necessary to enable efficient data sharing and utilization.

Privacy and Security in Data Sharing emerges as a significant technical concern, especially when dealing with sensitive data such as health records and personal data. The Internet of Health Things (IoHT) highlights the ethical and technical challenges involved in sharing personal health data while ensuring adequate protections for user privacy (Colonna, 2020). Open data initiatives, particularly in Europe, face challenges related to balancing data accessibility with privacy protections, as some datasets carry the risk of re-identification if not properly anonymized (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019). In the insurance industry, privacy concerns are heightened when using customer data for risk modeling, leading to the development of new anonymization and aggregation techniques to protect sensitive information while still enabling broader data use (Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022). Privacy-by-design frameworks and cryptographic techniques are essential to addressing these issues from a technical perspective, ensuring that data sharing systems are both secure and privacy-compliant.

Cultural Dimension

we have defined the collaborations into three key areas of application: Cultural Resistance to Data Sharing, Cultural Perceptions of Openness, and Cultural Influence on Trust in Technology.

Cultural Resistance to Data Sharing emerges as a deep-seated issue rooted in long-standing institutional and societal practices across sectors. In the context of flood resilience, the reluctance to share data can be traced back to entrenched institutional silos and a history of competitive behavior between private and public entities. This is not a recent development but one that has been shaped over time by the need for organizations to protect their autonomy and market positions. The cultural norm of maintaining control over proprietary data is a result of historical organizational behaviors that prioritize competitive advantage over collaboration, even in cases where collective action might benefit society as a whole (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). Similarly, in academia, the cultural practice of viewing research data as intellectual property is deeply ingrained. Historically, the academic system has rewarded individual achievement, and this has fostered a cultural reluctance to share data openly, as researchers fear losing ownership and control over their intellectual contributions. This cultural resistance is rooted in long-standing practices of valuing individual academic success over collective scientific progress (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020).

Cultural Perceptions of Openness reflect a long history of balancing transparency with control. The ideal of openness in sharing data, especially in academia and healthcare, is not a new concept but one that has evolved over time as technological advancements have made data more accessible. However, the cultural perception of data as something that must be controlled and guarded continues to persist. In academic circles, despite recent shifts toward open access, there is a long-standing cultural resistance rooted in the fear of losing intellectual ownership. Historically, knowledge and data were viewed as personal or institutional assets, and this has created a cultural barrier to the full embrace of open data practices (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). In healthcare, the cultural emphasis on patient privacy has developed over decades, reinforcing the notion that personal health data should remain strictly controlled. This cultural value of privacy complicates efforts to promote openness, even when the potential benefits of sharing data for public health or medical research are evident (Prainsack, 2021). The tension

between openness and control reflects deeper cultural narratives around ownership, privacy, and the ethical use of data that have evolved over time.

Cultural Influence on Trust in Technology highlights how historical experiences and long-standing cultural beliefs shape the trust in and acceptance of new technologies. In sectors such as flood resilience, where data-sharing technologies could improve outcomes, there is a cultural hesitation born from past experiences with data misuse or institutional competition. Over time, organizations have developed a cautious approach to adopting new technologies, driven by a historical need to protect their interests and maintain control over sensitive information (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). In academia, the cultural reluctance to trust open data platforms can be traced back to long-standing concerns about recognition and ownership. The fear that shared data may not be properly credited is rooted in the traditional academic culture that places a high value on individual recognition, and this has led to hesitancy in adopting open data technologies fully (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). In healthcare, the cultural resistance to trusting technology with personal data stems from decades of placing a high value on patient privacy and ethical standards. This long-term cultural emphasis on confidentiality has made it difficult to fully trust digital platforms and data-sharing technologies, even when the technology offers substantial benefits for patient care and medical research (Prainsack, 2021).

Assumptions and Impacts in Detail

In addition to the quantitative analysis, a qualitative content analysis allowed to analyze cross-dimensional aspects, and in-depths analysis of first, assumptions of data sharing; second, expected benefits; and third, risks and challenges.

Assumptions on Data Sharing

In relation to impacts of data sharing, the literature revealed **four common assumptions** that need to be discussed when thinking about benefits and risks of data sharing, yet often go overlooked. These assumptions are: (a) the inherent interconnectedness of data sharing, openness and goodness; (b) data neutrality (including issues of bias and discrimination); (c) the relational character of data sharing; and (d) the equivalence of data sharing and value creation.

Assumption 1: Data is *neutral*

Social science literature clearly points out that data – contrary to common perception - is shaped by historical and social contexts. Thus, especially the assumptions and interpretations going into data sets need further explication (Prainsack and Leonelli, 2018). Accordingly, data transfers conditions of their generation and processing:

“One could argue that insufficient benefit was generated for the community, and inequities were entrenched. Current data sharing principles assume that data are value-neutral and free of historical and social context, when in fact data are constructed through the choice of the research framework, methods, and instruments that often reflect institutional power and concretize inequity. A solution to this issue is to ensure that groups and communities who are contributing shared data have a voice in its use” (Emmons et al., 2023, p. 3).

In that sense, data contains **subtle normative judgments** and perpetuates the **relational nature of data production and collection**, e.g., a **limited agency** of individual data subjects that causes social informational harm. Unease about data sharing sometimes indicated “shifting power relationships that the digital technologies (and the companies that make them) affect in the social network surrounding farms, raising questions about fair and equitable distribution of benefits and responsibilities within that network” (Zhang et al., 2021, p. 2; referring to Van Der Burg, Wiseman and Krkeljas, 2021).

Moreover, **contextual information** (in relation to data sharing) generates more valuable insights and information, especially when pooled and linked to other data (e.g., in genetic research or precision medicine (Hassan *et al.*, 2020; Udesky *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, patients are inherently linked to their environment, promoting comparison as a key feature of personalization, which may contribute to exclusion and bias, as articulations of similarity draw harder boundaries around the reference population by obscuring whose data is missing.

This implies that **bias and power relations** need to be addressed when talking about data (sharing), e.g. by assessing the risk of bias associated with different data types (Heacock *et al.*, 2020; Slobodova, 2020) or by explicitly addressing the issue of contextuality through concepts such as ‘data structures’ which highlight how design choices, sorting processes and dimensions of digital space perpetuate specific conditions of data for knowledge production (Elbe, 2021).

Assumption 2: Data sharing is about *technical* relations

These considerations of biases, contextuality and inherent (potential) discrimination of data emphasizes the **effects of political contexts and social relations** on practices of data sharing. These include personal and institutional reluctancies to share data, as well as tensions or sustained (or newly arising) conflicts between actors. Thus, looking at data sharing **from a social point of view** may support a smoother implementation in real-life settings as technical solutions may never succeed in overcoming political and institutional obstacles:

“A core message from the literature is that technical cleverness and rule-driven agreements will never be enough to overcome such obstacles [...] Importantly, engineering the necessary shifts starts from recognizing that interagency working is a social process involving ‘sociotechnical interactions embodied in work processes, organizational forms and institutional contexts’ (Dawes, Cresswell and Pardo, 2009, p. 401); and from understanding how information is developed and circulated” (McGuirk, O’Neill and Mee, 2015, pp. 200–201).

Accordingly, data sharing is conceptualized as a complex and non-linear process, balancing between lines of conflict and cooperation and thus requires mediation to avoid that its benefits become easily clouded (McGuirk, O’Neill and Mee, 2015).

Assumption 3: Data sharing equals *openness equals 'good'*

Despite assumptions to the contrary, the usefulness of 'openness' is by no means self-evident. Rather, it functions as a **strongly normative stance**, as Prainsack and Leonelli (2018) put it:

“Governments, software, and even humans are furnished with the adjective ‘open’. And this adjective is not a quiet and modest bystander, but it entails a demanding cluster of requirements: To be open is typically associated with being transparent, responsible, accountable, inclusive. In other words: To be open is to be good.” (Prainsack and Leonelli, 2018, p. 97; Prainsack, 2021, p. 648).

Moreover, the **automatic equation of 'data sharing' and 'openness' need to be scrutinized**: issues of openness may either not be of priority (e.g., replication crisis in environmental health), or not to be solved by data sharing (Hicks, 2023). Although 'openness' is omnipresent as a (political) requirement in context of data (sharing), it does not resolve the tension between transparency and privacy, as neither constitute ends in themselves: on one hand, data sharing may even contradict transparency by concealing what is withheld or absent (Prainsack, 2021); on the other, openness comes at a risk of ignoring people's right to control what others know about them. At the same time, shifts in power concentration can move power and responsibility away from democratically legitimized actors towards private institutions only accountable to their shareholders (Prainsack, 2021). Thus, literature calls for a more **nuanced social debate on requirements of openness**, especially in the context of medicine (Prainsack, 2021).

Assumption 4: Data sharing implies *automatic value creation*

While some studies claim that benefits of data sharing, and especially open data, are well-documented, e.g. regarding controlling emerging viruses, or sharing information management in the cultural sector (Destro Bisol *et al.*, 2014), others offer a more cautious perspective, arguing that benefits are by no means guaranteed. This literature emphasizes **contextualized assessments of pros and cons** (an approach also considered useful by DATAMITE pilots). For example, combining different research approaches to evaluate data sharing practices empirically revealed that *“effective, informal, sharing practices and barriers to sharing that are widespread in a particular research field, rather than necessarily being prescribed by funding bodies and institutions, and may assist in establishing the most effective data sharing strategies.”* (Destro Bisol *et al.*, 2014, p. 186).

Other papers explicitly **warned against risks of overestimating** open data's potential (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Open data seems to rarely deliver greater efficiency of government or external problem-solving capacity and resources (both 37%) (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019). Accordingly, data did not possess any value per se as “[...] *access to large-scale datasets does not automatically lead to insights. So, there is still uncertainty about how to define data usefulness in terms of public interest.*” (Pavone *et al.*, 2024, p. 3). From an economic perspective, pricing of data remains challenging and usually involves a **trade-off** between different pricing regimes (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Thus, a **more nuanced approach** to evaluate economic and societal benefits of data sharing, and in particular OGD, was needed: *“In fact, recent research indicates that initial objectives of OGD initiatives are often not indicative of the actual outcomes”* (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019; Haberer and Schnurr, 2020, p. 2). Reasons for this mismatch are manifold and include: missing consensus of evaluating management of private and public goods and services; missing gains compared to other statistical methods; a lack of harmonization and standardization (Gessa and Sancha, 2020); challenges in processing/interpreting raw data, i.e., missing information on usefulness and quality of the data (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023; Pavone *et al.*, 2024); economic trade-offs (especially between innovation and competition goals; (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020)); the need for safeguarding data sharing (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020); and missing innovation networks and respective skills (Slobodova, 2020).

Thus, data sharing and open data should **not be equated with automatic value creation**: a paradigm of ‘the more the merrier’ must be rejected, as it does not reveal much about usefulness and quality of data (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023). To create value from (open) data, different actors need to actively participate in different roles:

“Many researchers conclude that published datasets will not automatically attract economic actors to create new services, unless there is a vibrant ecosystem of actors having various skills and different interests, collaborating, negotiating and exchanging knowledge such that societal goals are being achieved in a mutually beneficial manner (Harrison, Pardo and Cook, 2012)” (Slobodova, 2020, p. 61)

Moreover, the success of (open) data sharing tends to increase when value creation builds on established practices:

“These two opposing views on the effectiveness of OGD [useful/not useful] to promote public interest goals can be reconciled, when OGD is viewed to rather reinforce existing efforts and incentives of public institutions, as opposed to fundamentally change their intentions and outcomes. In this sense, the quality and scope of OGD is indicative of a public agency’s willingness to provide transparency and accountability“ (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020, p. 29).

Despite great hopes in data sharing, its **socio-economic benefits are still contested** (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020), depending on the conditions of the respective field. Regarding **economic** factors, data sharing could potentially benefit SMEs, yet only under specific conditions, i.e., when substituting data generated within big groups; yet complementation of (existing) data would imply outrunning SMEs due to economies of scale and data-driven network effects (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). **Technically** speaking, the volume of data remains the greatest challenge for sharing, next to the lack of well-defined technical standards and sensitive copyright questions, especially in the context of developing nations (Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020). Regarding **social factors, the limited transformation of data into actionable knowledge** and the lack of consensus on evaluation parameters of effectiveness of open data for management in context of open data platforms remain an issue (Gessa and Sancha, 2020). Moreover, evaluations of objectives and delivered benefits of open government data initiatives indicated a certain mismatch as benefits turned out to hardly be affected by their initial motivation; instead, economic and societal benefits follow operational and technical benefits, often unrelated to their objectives. Besides, conditions to reap benefits, like skills for data analysis or users often remain under researched (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019).

Thus, benefits of data sharing don’t occur automatically, but need to be targeted and carefully evaluated according to each setting.

(Expected) Benefits in Detail

The core of the literature review lies on the analysis of impacts, i.e., benefits and risks of data sharing in general or for specific sectors (Table 10). Literature identifies a **wide range of non-monetary benefits** associated with data sharing, many of which are framed in terms of contributions to the **public interest** or the pursuit of the greater good (18 out of 40), in terms of **democratic governance or knowledge generation**. The prevalence of these non-monetary

benefits reflects a focus on publicly funded domains, particularly health and medicine, scientific research, and public services. The emphasis on public sector data and open-access initiatives reinforces the idea that data sharing is primarily seen as a tool to advance collective goals rather than as a purely economic instrument.

In addition to contributing to the “greater good” as a main motivation for sharing data, sharing is frequently associated with **democratic governance** and here, with transparency (30 papers); Participation, empowerment, and democratization (27); accountability (20); and improved management and better information for policy (15).

These findings reflect the growing importance of data in supporting **evidence-informed governance**, fostering **citizen and stakeholder engagement**, and increasing the **legitimacy of public institutions**.

The second cluster of benefits pertains to the **production and dissemination of knowledge**. Here, data sharing is seen as enabling collaboration across disciplines and institutions (21 papers); reuse, replication, and verification of research results (21); innovation (21); and generation of new insights (18). Additionally, a smaller subset of studies highlights improved data quality and more robust analytical approaches (6).

Beyond these two clusters, the literature also discusses broader **strategic and operational advantages** of data sharing. These include using data to enhance efficiency and maximize return on public investment (18); improve data accessibility (17); and strategic usage of data sharing (20).

A core topic evolves around the role of **trust** for data sharing. Rather than being treated solely as a **prerequisite** for data sharing, trust is increasingly conceptualized as an **emergent quality**, developed through the ongoing **practice** of sharing data (17 papers). This perspective highlights the **relational and iterative nature** of trust-building processes, which extend beyond technical mechanisms to include social, organizational, and communicative dimensions.

Finally, the frequently cited benefit of efficiency gains (10) is often tempered by concerns about the costs and burdens of data sharing (11), particularly for individual researchers or institutions. These include time and resource commitments, technical challenges, and potential opportunity costs. As a result, questions regarding cost-efficiency and resource allocation (5) remain highly

context-dependent and often unresolved, underscoring the need for case-specific evaluations of when, how, and for whom data sharing is beneficial.

Expected benefits																
accessibility	accountability	transparency	improved management/ better inform policy	(business) innovation (technical, processes etc)	scientific advantages, new findings	maximising investments/ efficiency	cost-saving (and costly)	allocating resources	reuse/ replicability/ verification	strategic use of data (sharing)	public interest/ greater good	(in scientific or policy processes) enhancing trust	increased quality of data, support of AI and models etc.	participation / empowerment/ democratization	collaboration	other
17	20	30	15	21	18	18	10/ 11	5	21	20	18	17	6	27	21	1

Table 10: Number of papers according to expected benefits

Data sharing for the greater good

First, literature indicates that the **‘greater good’¹⁵ is a core condition** for the public’s support for and contributing to sharing data, alongside with privacy/security and trust/transparency (Rahimzadeh, Knoppers and Bartlett, 2020; Udesky *et al.*, 2020; Waind, 2020). Especially in health contexts, the motivation of ‘the greater good’ to improve knowledge, especially of the situation of people with the same condition is evident (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019; Borgerud and Borglund, 2020; Hassan *et al.*, 2020; Udesky *et al.*, 2020). This also applied when highly sensitive data (e.g., genomic data) was concerned:

“There was widespread support for using data as a collective resource for the GMS to draw upon when diagnosing and treating patients, other than themselves. The scenarios

¹⁵ Synonyms that were used: research altruism, altruistic motives, public interest; also: (moral) ‘duty to share’, ‘supporting learning’

provided described how the genomic data of patients with similar conditions or genetic profiles could be compared to aid diagnosis and treatment.“ (Hassan *et al.*, 2020, p. 709).

Financial profit was not perceived as a good enough reason for sharing data (Udesky *et al.*, 2020; Waind, 2020; Etchegary *et al.*, 2023); rather, research altruism turned out to be a major driver for the majority (>70%) of those who expressed IIP in the hypothetical studies (Udesky *et al.*, 2020). Thus, literature indicates that non-monetary benefits are not to be underestimated to gain the public's support for data sharing. These findings underscore that **data sharing is strongly legitimized when contributing to public benefit and responsibility**. Public support is more likely when data use is perceived as **servicing collective interests**, promoting **solidarity**, and contributing to **long-term societal well-being**, rather than yielding private or financial gain. Ultimately, the **normative appeal to the "greater good"** emerges as a crucial factor in building trust and encouraging participation in data sharing initiatives, especially where sensitive or personal data is involved.

Data sharing in the context of democratic governance

Second, benefits of data sharing and open data related to democratic, i.e. public, concerns. Data sharing is perceived as being able to enhance democracy and decision making in policy and beyond. This cluster comprises arguments of the importance of data sharing for affecting policies, for enhancing transparency and accountability, and for strengthening empowerment and participation, as well as democracy in a broader sense.

Data sharing affecting policy and research strategies

Strategically speaking, data sharing may affect policy and research strategies, e.g., in terms of **guiding government's attention** (e.g., towards environmental policy, including effects of government digitization, mitigating fiscal pressures, and increasing energy demand through data sharing) and **shaping policy formulation** (e.g., when formulating climate change mitigation actions (Gessa and Sancha, 2020)). In research policy, data sharing and open science may **strengthen the responsiveness** between science and society in the light of global challenges (Destro Bisol *et al.*, 2014) as they provide the basis for raising awareness, changing actions, or fostering collaboration (Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023).

Thus, data sharing can serve as a strategic instrument for shaping policy and research (policy) agendas, particularly in addressing complex societal and environmental challenges. By **enabling more informed decision-making**, guiding governmental focus, and enhancing public awareness, data sharing has the potential to amplify policy's responsiveness and societal engagement.

Thus, regarding democratic governance, data sharing may **enhance responsiveness, awareness and societal engagement** in different sectors. Yet, draw-backs (like an increased demand of energy) underscore the **need for balanced, context-sensitive strategies** that **account for unintended consequences** alongside intended benefits.

Ensuring transparency and accountability

Accountability and especially transparency appeared most frequently among the benefits of data sharing and open data (Gessa and Sancha, 2020). They are usually portrayed as mechanisms to prevent fraud and to **enhance traceability** of decisions in various contexts (e.g., policy, particularly OGD, research, or health practices), to **reduce information asymmetries** (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023) and to **justify** (bases for) decisions and funding (Slobodova, 2020). Thus, they are regarded as **precondition** for other (expected) benefits of data sharing, including **building trust** (Zhang *et al.*, 2021) or **value creation** (Pavone *et al.*, 2024). While accountability and transparency are often **strong individual motivations** in the context of pro-social agendas (Slobodova, 2020), data disclosure practices often remain reactive to requirements: *“In response, state agencies adjust and enhance their data disclosure practices, thus performing reactive data governance”* (Huang and Lyu, 2022, p. 2429).

Thus, overall, the literature highlights **transparency and accountability as foundational benefits and enablers** of data sharing, particularly in contexts of governance. These principles support **integrity and trust building** and underpin broader goals such as public legitimacy. However, the evidence suggests that data disclosure practices often remain **reactive rather than proactive**, pointing to the need for **more systematic and forward-looking governance approaches** to fully realize these benefits.

Strengthening democracy through empowerment and participation

Open data and data sharing practices are rooted in ideals of both economic and democratic freedom (Slobodova, 2020). Accordingly, agendas of economic efficiency and democratization

appear closely linked, especially with regard to competition (i.e., de-monopolization and democratic variety): *“In many areas, economic and democratic goals are mutually beneficial, since healthy competition and de-monopolization of power are as important for market economy, as they are for democracy”* (Slobodova, 2020, p. 60).

Thus, **strengthening democracy is one of the main (expected) benefits** of data sharing (Hansen and Schröder, 2019; Slobodova, 2020), e.g. through strengthening empowerment and participation. Data sharing has been assigned great potential to support vulnerable populations in policy or decision-making by enabling their participation in policy (Hicks, 2023) and to better advocate for their rights by holding institutions accountable, i.e., exert their civic rights (Slobodova, 2020). Especially OGD promises **more inclusive and better decision-making** to prevent exploitation of historically disadvantaged communities (Emigawaty, Adi and Rochim, 2023; Emmons *et al.*, 2023).

A second objective of data sharing is to allow people to make more knowledgeable decisions:

“It also encourages citizens to make more knowledgeable decisions by enabling people to contribute to policies that are better suited to their needs and to have more active relationships with their governments” (Emigawaty, Adi and Rochim, 2023).

Thus, data sharing, and OGD especially, are supposed to **enhance transparency and democratic control, public participation and self-empowerment**, in short: to strengthen democracy (Hansen and Schröder, 2019). Accordingly, **inclusiveness** has been highlighted in both policy and research. In research, ideas of inclusiveness fostered transdisciplinary approaches, e.g. to environmental or digitalization policies (Destro Bisol *et al.*, 2014; Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023). For some fields, inclusiveness was even considered the only way to advance research in an ethical way (e.g., genomics) as it grants affected populations the opportunity to inform policy, practice, and research (Slobodova, 2020). Consequently, data sharing sets out to allow organizations to empower individuals to participate in **decision-making processes**, and to foster **trust** between government and citizens by promoting open government practices and data transparency (Slobodova, 2020).

In sum, the literature emphasizes that data sharing, particularly through Open Government Data, holds significant **democratic potential** by promoting transparency, enabling participation, and empowering marginalized communities. While often entangled with economic agendas, its

normative foundation lies in **enhancing civic rights, democratic accountability, and inclusive decision-making**. Realizing this potential, however, requires deliberate efforts to ensure **accessibility, inclusiveness, and equity**, making data sharing not only a technical or economic tool but a **means of democratic strengthening and societal transformation**.

Enhancing trust (trust as result and precondition)

Trust is a complex topic and relates to data sharing in different ways: it may be conceptualized as a technical issue (data quality and credibility (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018; Colonna, 2020)), or as inter-actor or inter-institutional relations (e.g. as a precondition of data sharing, or as an effect of data sharing).

When perceived as a **benefit derived from data sharing**, enhancing trust manifests in relation to practices, results, institutions or collaborations of both science and policy (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019; Udesky *et al.*, 2020; Zhang *et al.*, 2021; Hicks, 2023). A technical strategy could then be data trust models to overcome commercial and cultural barriers (e.g., unwillingness to share specific data between stakeholders Waterman *et al.*, 2021). Yet, some empirical studies challenged the perceived increase of trust in the government through data sharing (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019) by arguing that its positive effects, i.e., enhancing trust, depend on conditions rather than the practice of sharing (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020): for example, authoritative data (e.g., OGD) is often considered trustworthy (Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018).

Perceived trust as a **precondition for data sharing** indicates conditional support for the practice of data sharing and emphasizes importance of social relationships prior to data sharing. Committees may offer a way to formalize such relations before sharing data (Etchegary *et al.*, 2023). These social relationships, e.g. data recipients, define people's willingness to share data in different sectors, like agriculture (where trust between farmers and stakeholders enabled exploring big data technologies for sustainable agriculture (Zhang *et al.*, 2021)) or health data research (where trust between different actors led to more effective governance structures and responsible research practices, which again, affect socio-economic aspects by fostering transparency, accountability, and public trust in research (Bak *et al.*, 2023)).

Overall, **trust emerges as both a foundational condition and an outcome of data sharing**, shaped by the perceived quality of data, the nature of institutional relationships, and the

transparency of practices. While data sharing can enhance trust in science, policy, and institutions, **its effectiveness largely depends on context** (i.e., the sector, type of data, and the social dynamics between data providers and users). These findings underscore the importance of **embedding data sharing initiatives within trustworthy frameworks**, supported by transparent governance, participatory structures, and ethical safeguards.

Data sharing for improving knowledge generation

Next to democratic governance, data sharing is also seen as a **driver of scientific and societal innovation**, enabling new insights and solutions through broader access to diverse datasets. It does so by **generating and promoting new ideas** and by **enabling collaboration in research** (and beyond).

Generating and promoting new ideas

Advancing scientific understanding and enabling **new discoveries** in basic and applied research emerged as one of the most important motivations for data sharing (e.g., Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020; Ledvina *et al.*, 2022). This view is often underpinned by the assumption that more data inherently leads to more or better scientific insights (Heacock *et al.*, 2020; Ledvina *et al.*, 2022) and more transparency, e.g., by allowing for a **reproducibility** of results (Parker and Bull, 2015; Haberer and Schnurr, 2020; Roche *et al.*, 2020; Prainsack, 2021). Motivated by altruistic motives and by fostering broader inclusion, data sharing may contribute to better community resilience (Waterman *et al.*, 2021), indirect benefits for (future) children, and promoting solidarity and collective benefits within the population (here: the pediatric population (Rahimzadeh, Knoppers and Bartlett, 2020), knowledge databases for future uses (Udesky *et al.*, 2020) and the development of interventions for diseases affecting the world's poorest people (Parker and Bull, 2015).

However, scientific advancement may relate to **either more specified or cross-cutting research** based on inter- and transdisciplinary research questions and approaches, as the following examples of health research indicate:

“Large-scale, government-funded genomic medicine initiatives are underway globally [...] Accessing and mining large genomic data sets is particularly beneficial for the study of human diseases, fostering tangible scientific discoveries and advances in medicine”
(Etchegary *et al.*, 2023, p. 2).

“Sharing and integrating datasets, regardless of the size, could help answer challenging questions about the role of environmental exposures, their interplay with biological response in human disease (e.g. resilience and susceptibility to exposures), and how to reduce those exposures to improve human health” (Heacock et al., 2020, p. 114).

Thus, data sharing sets out to **reduce barriers** to start research and generate new hypotheses, in short, is understood to ‘democratize’ science (Ledvina et al., 2022), e.g., by diminishing data asymmetries (Prainsack, 2021; Liu, Yu and Lei, 2024).

Beyond science, generating new ideas was mostly subsumed under ‘**innovation**’, i.e., value creation, in different fields (Huang and Lyu, 2022; Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023). By definition, i.e., broadly distributing and establishing new products, services, or approaches on the market, innovation is intrinsically tied to a capitalist paradigm, and automatically puts data sharing in the context of economic growth and competitiveness.

OGD especially was discussed as a way to unleash the hitherto hidden potential of data sharing, especially for SMEs, when complementary to data of the private sector even though a risk of crowding out small companies exists (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020).

Innovation also related to (expected) improvements in practices like **data governance and work practices** (Huang and Lyu, 2022; Emigawaty, Adi and Rochim, 2023), where it was expected to fundamentally alter established practices (e.g., concerning the division of labor and responsibility) (McGuirk, O’Neill and Mee, 2015).

To reduce research efforts, data sets are often subjected to secondary use, especially when new research questions could be addressed with ‘older’ data (e.g., pattern recognition etc.). However, especially regarding sensitive data, the public acceptance of secondary use can pose a considerable challenge (Hassan et al., 2020).

In sum, the reviewed literature strongly positions **data sharing as a catalyst for both scientific advancement and innovation**. It is associated with expanding research opportunities, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and accelerating the development of new ideas, products, and services. However, realizing these potentials depends not only on access to data but also on **appropriate infrastructures, governance models, and public trust**.

Enabling collaboration in research and beyond

Generating new ideas is largely linked to collaboration, i.e., knowledge exchange across different professional fields (sectors, organizations) and scientific disciplines. Collaboration is expected to create an innovative environment, relating to new scientific insights as well as innovations of products, procedures, policies or practices (Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020; Udesky *et al.*, 2020; Ledvina *et al.*, 2022). Besides, it may foster new research fields when problems are addressed in a multi- and interdisciplinary way (Cheah *et al.*, 2015; Borgerud and Borglund, 2020), as required by mode-2-science (Nowotny, Scott and Gibbons, 2001) and post-normal science (Funtowicz and Ravetz, 1993). To enable collaboration, the importance of trustful relationships with research subjects was emphasized (Bak *et al.*, 2023).

Thus, data sharing is perceived widely as a catalyst for collaboration across disciplines, sectors, and institutions, fostering both scientific discovery and practical innovation. By enabling knowledge exchange, it supports the development of new research fields and interdisciplinary approaches to address complex societal challenges. However, successful collaborations depend go beyond technical infrastructure and depend on building trustful relationships between actors.

Data sharing as a means of indirect monetization

Third, benefits of data sharing related to (indirect) monetization. Thus, from an **economic perspective**, two core arguments frequently cited in favor of data sharing are its potential to **improve management** and to **maximize (cost) efficiency**.

Improved management through data sharing

Improved management is often linked to different data strategies (e.g., OGD, open data), governance structures and decision-making in the private and public sector (Zuiderwijk, Shinde and Janssen, 2019; Gessa and Sancha, 2020; Roche *et al.*, 2020). While some approaches like big data hope to predict (social) phenomena with greater precision, an empirical evaluation of effects and parameters, especially regarding 'better management of public and private goods, in particular environmental management' remains unclear (Gessa and Sancha, 2020; Pavone *et al.*, 2024).

Maximizing (cost) efficiency

Likewise, an empirical evaluation of maximizing (cost) efficiency empirically remains a challenge (e.g., Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018), despite high hopes in this regard. In research, open data and data sharing are supposed to reduce the **unnecessary duplication (of results)**, to support **prioritizing** options and to **make better use of resources** through targeted results from data-based decision-support - in short, to maximize return of investments and public research money. Some research fields even integrate this goal into their vision, as shown by the example of precision medicine:

“[...] the idea of making medicine more precise by using more layers of data to render patient stratification ever more granular is a commitment that has emerged in different domains of medical research and practice. It is also very closely wedded to rhetoric of healthcare facing a cost crisis where Personalised and Precision Medicine are portrayed as a way to a more rational and economic approach to healthcare (Schattner, 2015)“
(Prainsack, 2021, p. 648).

Thus, data sharing is perceived to increase indirect monetization by improving management and boosting cost efficiency. Yet, empirical evidence confirming these benefits, especially in public goods management and research, is still limited. While promising examples, like precision medicine, highlight its potential, further research is needed to clearly demonstrate and realize the economic gains of data sharing.

Risks and Challenges in Detail

The review revealed a broad range of potential risks and challenges (Table 11), yet the three most frequent issues were: privacy, bias/discrimination, and mistrust. Regarding these three main topics, privacy concerns featured most prominently (30), as object of in-depths investigation as well as ‘casually mentioned’ risks. Considering the public and legislative discourse in the last couple of years (e.g., GDPR, AI Act, the Data Governance Act, the Data Act etc.), this is little surprising (for a detailed overview on respective regulation in relation to DATAMITE please see Deliverable D4.5). Bias and discrimination relate to issues such as discrimination based on race, gender, genetic material etc. (cf. data sharing in genomic research), topics that feature in almost 50% of the articles (19 out of 40). Despite not dealing with sensitive health data, questions of discrimination and bias remain important for the DATAMITE pilots and infrastructure. While

addressed on a technical level through the **Fairness Tool of the DATAMITE infrastructure**, wider questions of discrimination through data sharing need to be considered case-by-case when exploring data sharing infrastructure or building AI tools whose learning is based on shared data. The third most frequent risk turned out to be mistrust against the one who shares data, i.e., the fear of misuse by people who share data or whose data is being shared (12). Accordingly, trust needs to be considered a precondition for as well as a result of data sharing, as discussed separately (see Annex B: The Issue of Trust).

Risk and challenges						
Privacy	Bias & discrimination	Mistrust	Shift in economic structure	provide data individual effort to	other	generally mentioned
30	19	12	5	10	23	9

Table 11: Number of papers according to risks and challenges

Especially sharing personal data (e.g., for medical research) requires sufficient information about the intended use of data, as recipients affect the willingness of participants to share data. At the same time, incentive structures for individual efforts to share data remain missing. While data sharing may be of advantage in the long run, e.g., for the reputation of an institution, individual advantages are not always clear from the outset or sometimes can even have pending adverse consequences (e.g., regarding publications), for individuals and organizations.

A more qualitative analysis of the literature revealed a broad range of risks and challenges, including privacy; bias; decontextualization and misinterpretation of data; consequences of potential misuse of data; efforts to enable secure data sharing; and shifting economic structure(s) and social (in-)equality.

Privacy

In general, positions towards data sharing ground in different interpretations of personal data – as commodities or as fundamental rights –, which increasingly approximate each other (Pavone *et al.*, 2024). Privacy implies managerial aspects related to data processing (Colonna, 2020), as well as technical and financial resources necessary to implement tools that address concerns

around the release of data (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023). Thus, privacy related to **technical solutions (e.g., anonymization or de-identifying of data), legal aspects (GDPR), or political and social issues (e.g., security) in different sectors** (Cheah *et al.*, 2015; Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). Some sectors raise specific privacy issues, e.g., in relation to undesired information disclosure (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020) and increased complexity of public data sharing of OGD (compared to sharing data between businesses) (Colonna, 2020), or to aggregated farm data (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). Privacy in relation to **business** data addresses issues of re-identification, misuse due to misunderstanding of quality or meaning, the exposure of commercially sensitive data and deriving reputational damage (Gunasekera, 2018). At the same time, OGD from the private sector may harm individuals by disclosing undesired information and processing, even when aggregated/anonymized data is used (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020).

Thus, privacy appeared as a **core value** in need to be considered and protected, especially in relation to personal data (Pavone *et al.*, 2024). The comprehensive debate on the issue on European and national level (cf. DATAMITE D4.5) indicates the political nature (and politization) of *data governance*, emphasizing the *conscious and value-based decisions* that privacy is grounded in (Bak *et al.*, 2023). Literature considered privacy as a main condition for sharing (administrative) data, together with public interest, and trust and transparency; notably, none of these conditions were considered sufficient in isolation (D’Agostino *et al.*, 2016; Waind, 2020). Accordingly, literature called for a balance between these principles:

“Ultimately, an appropriate balance must be struck to ensure the proposed benefit outweighs the potential risk, and this is dependent upon the specifics of any given project, including: the data being used; the questions being asked; the protections in place; and the institutions or individuals accessing data.” (Waind, 2020, p. 9).

In relation to privacy, the concept of **confidentiality** and the deriving reluctance to share data is crucial. In businesses and administration, confidentiality of information, potential exposure and deriving (public) scrutiny including increased tensions with stakeholders limit practices of data sharing (McGuirk, O’Neill and Mee, 2015) (e.g., in the context of energy models (Gunasekera, 2018) or OGD (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023)). Businesses refrain from sharing data as they fear the **reputational damage** related to the publication of **commercially sensitive** data due to custodian business confidentiality (Gunasekera, 2018). **Administrative** systems are reluctant to

share data due to **public criticism, increasing tensions** with stakeholders, shifting power to advocacy groups (e.g. by strengthening independent agency (Huang and Lyu, 2022), or concerns of undermining national security. As a result, traditional bureaucratic values, such as expertise, secrecy, and hierarchy, are upheld to the detriment of openness (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023).

In **research contexts**, past exaggerated requests for sensitive data (especially in the health sector) **deepened people's concerns about trust and privacy** (Emmons *et al.*, 2023), including data storage and unauthorized access (Hassan *et al.*, 2020; Etchegary *et al.*, 2023), especially when benefits (for themselves or others) remained unclear (Hassan *et al.*, 2020; Udesky *et al.*, 2020). Accordingly, in the medical sector, and especially in genomic research, ethical tensions remained between clinical benefits and the long-term threat of data breaches (Etchegary *et al.*, 2023) concerning medical aspects as well as personal repercussions (e.g., discovering 'new' familial connections or identification of human DNA donors) (Rahimzadeh, Knoppers and Bartlett, 2020). Thus, genomic data requires researchers to balance the right to full information against privacy rights (Destro Bisol *et al.*, 2014; Hassan *et al.*, 2020; Etchegary *et al.*, 2023), as it blurs the line between research and clinical care (Hassan *et al.*, 2020). Although a necessary requirement, compliance to open data and privacy requirements constitutes a challenge, e.g. in genomic research, for patients to understand concepts like broad consent, re-consent, anonymity, and right to withdraw samples (Etchegary *et al.*, 2023). Accordingly, **legal and ethical concerns** prevent researchers from publishing research data alongside articles (Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020) and from sharing data to protect patients' privacy to strengthen patients' rights.

To deal with privacy concerns, the review revealed two strategies and related challenges: (a) compliance to the GDPR and informed consent and (b) anonymization and re-identification.

The first one, compliance to the GDPR and informed consent, is crucial in relation to personal data (e.g., personal identifier, infrastructure etc.) (Colonna, 2020), although some literature discussed adverse effects of the GDPR, for example for using OGD (Hansen and Schrøder, 2019). In research, the trade-off between social benefits of studies and personal risks was addressed (Udesky *et al.*, 2020) as restrictions of sensitive data may increase the impact of incomplete datasets (Waterman *et al.*, 2021). In any case, valid consent is perceived to enact responsibility and to ensure the interests of research participants and communities (Cheah *et al.*,

2015; Parker and Bull, 2015). Accordingly, practices like *reusing* health data are considered ambiguous even when legally authorized (Hassan *et al.*, 2020).

The second one, **anonymization and potential re-identification**, has been promoted to avoid privacy breaches (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Yet, anonymization needs to be balanced against data utility (Parker and Bull, 2015; Colonna, 2020; Etchegary *et al.*, 2023). For example, for useful AI applications in medicine (e.g. for diagnosis or instructions), sensitive medical data was considered necessary, with a considerable loss in efficiency when data is de-identified (Colonna, 2020). Thus, while anonymized data may limit the usability of results, current approaches may still not guarantee to protect patients' privacy (Bak *et al.*, 2023). (Medical) data is difficult to control, 'once it is out there' and could be used in unforeseen ways (Hassan *et al.*, 2020). Anonymization still poses a lack of control for data subjects (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020) and reflecting the 'data environment' is required to avoid cross-over effects and data profiling (Destro Bisol *et al.*, 2014). Accordingly, it is crucial to evaluate the risk of **re-identification** (Parker and Bull, 2015; Colonna, 2020; Rahimzadeh, Knoppers and Bartlett, 2020). Identification is possible through linking different data sets, especially when sensitive data is shared outside the research team (Cheah *et al.*, 2015). Large-scale production of data increases the risk of re-identification due to cross-referencing data/identifiers (Cheah *et al.*, 2015), the use of data for purposes originally not specified (Bak *et al.*, 2023), or when cohort data is shared (Heacock *et al.*, 2020). Especially when using data across traditional boundaries between disciplines and analyzing larger data sets, especially genomic data, traditional processes of protection privacy may not suffice. Privacy is increasingly at risk when addressing small groups' datasets are combined (Waind, 2020). Regarding environmental health data, reidentified data of individuals or homes could be used similar to genetic or health information as a basis for discrimination by employers or insurers (Udesky *et al.*, 2020).

One (technical) strategy may consist of combining blockchain technology and smart contracts for a decentralized, secure and private record sharing scheme, allowing patients to selectively share their data (Zaghloul, Li and Ren, 2019). Moreover, working with synthetic data, i.e., fictitious data with certain identifiers, could allow us to consider contextuality in an anonymized way; yet it may still hold risks for subsets of a population (Colonna, 2020).

Addressing privacy challenges requires combining technical, legal, and ethical measures tailored to the data's context and sensitivity. Legal frameworks like GDPR and informed consent are essential but not enough alone; ethical and transparent governance is also needed. Anonymization is a key strategy to protect privacy, but it often reduces data usefulness and cannot fully prevent re-identification risks, especially with large or linked datasets. Together with specified use of data and principles of data minimization, new technical approaches like synthetic data and blockchain may offer potential improvements. However, the issue of privacy in relation to data sharing remains critical.

In conclusion, privacy remains a **fundamental and multifaceted consideration** in data sharing, requiring a delicate balance between enabling beneficial data use and protecting individual rights and sensitive information. The complexity of privacy spans **technical, legal, and socio-political dimensions**, demanding comprehensive governance frameworks that integrate robust protections with transparency, trust, and public interest. As data ecosystems continue to evolve, ongoing dialogue and adaptive strategies will be essential to uphold privacy while fostering responsible and equitable data sharing practices.

In summary, **concerns around confidentiality and exposure** significantly shape the landscape of data sharing, influencing organizational behavior and stakeholder relations. Balancing the benefits of openness with risks related to privacy, reputational damage, and national security remains a complex challenge. Effective governance frameworks must navigate these tensions carefully to foster trust, ensure transparency, and enable responsible data sharing without compromising sensitive interests.

Bias

Bias was considered a main risk that proliferates through data sharing, automatization or AI. **Sources of bias** are manifold and relate to *“how the data were produced or used, requiring descriptive metadata so that scientists can assess the risks of bias associated with each data type so that the risk can be incorporated into data analysis”* (Heacock *et al.*, 2020, p. 112). Accordingly, an **imbalanced approach** to information through open data initiatives were perceived as potentially hampering their public acceptance, e.g., when public knowledge is *“based on a prejudiced perspective”* (Slobodova, 2020, p. 58). As **a counter strategy** to bias deriving from data sharing, a technical and social strategies were proposed. From a technical

perspective, bias associated with each data type (Heacock *et al.*, 2020) should be assessed and certain meta-analysis should be conducted to decrease bias (Polanin and Williams, 2016); from a social perspective, community engagement to identify, address, and understand issues should be conducted since having a voice prevents exploitation, inequities and a loss of control of the respective communities (Emmons *et al.*, 2023). For more details regarding the challenge of bias from a social science perspective see section 8.2 on gender equality within DATAMITE.

In short, **bias pose significant risks** in data sharing, often amplified through automation and AI. Bias stems from how data is produced and used, underscoring the need for detailed metadata to assess and mitigate these risks. Imbalanced open data may undermine public trust and threaten the sustainability of data initiatives. To counteract bias, technical measures like bias assessment and meta-analysis are crucial, alongside social strategies such as community engagement to ensure fairness, prevent exploitation, and empower affected groups.

De-contextualization and misinterpretation of data

Some literature emphasized the importance of contextuality the effectiveness of data sharing depends on the consideration of local contexts and actor systems (Emmons *et al.*, 2023). Yet, contextual knowledge and effective community engagement imply that data sharing does not automatically promote replicability (Hicks, 2023), nor an alignment of perspectives (cf. Waterman *et al.*, 2021 for actor perspectives in the context of flood prevention).

Moreover, harm related to personal data potentially derives from **de-contextualization and misinterpretation** of data. This may result in proliferation of poor-quality data or of mistakes in scope and data interpretation. Moreover, it relates to the risk of alternative interpretations and unintended use of data, which were feared to fuel concerns of undermining the credibility of science in public perception.

Proliferating **poor-quality analyses and misinterpretation** of data through sharing indicates the difficulty of third parties to interpret and understand data correctly; consequently, these results and interpretations are prone to errors, and thus, limit data (re-)use (Cheah *et al.*, 2015; Borgerud and Borglund, 2020; for an example in crime mapping see Zhou *et al.*, 2021, p. 4666). Also, alternative interpretations through re-analysis of shared data may open questions of responsibility for data generation and custody, or drain resources from other programs (McGuirk, O’Neill and

Mee, 2015). Moreover, some papers even feared that open data may undermine the public's faith in the credibility of science due to the volume of *inadequately* scrutinized work (Hicks, 2023).

Thus, de-contextualization and misinterpretation of shared data risk producing and proliferating poor-quality analyses and alternative interpretations, some of which were feared to undermine scientific credibility by their sheer volume. These challenges highlight the need for careful data stewardship.

Consequences of potential misuse of data

Issues of trust (see section The Issue of Trust) are closely related to **anticipated misuse of data**, **unclear information on data privacy policy** and concerns regarding what others may do with researchers' data if it is made openly available, the fear of losing publication opportunity especially if another researcher uses data first (Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020). In the health sector, impeding misuse related to security issues of companies to safely store data (Fusi, Zhang and Liang, 2023), or plain misuse (of open data) by special interest groups (Hicks, 2023). Concerns in the context of genomic data related to data storage, sharing, and unauthorized access (Etchegary *et al.*, 2023), also in relation to potential changes in government, legislation or policy (Hassan *et al.*, 2020). Thus, the (potential) misuse of data is a major concern, related to **individual** (e.g., discrimination or stigmatization) as well as **professional** consequences (e.g., loss of competitive advantages in business or scientific contexts) and **national** level (Gunasekera, 2018; Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020; Huang and Lyu, 2022).

On an **individual level**, data sharing may reinforce biased data generation, and thus, lead to **stigmatization and discrimination** (e.g., in the design of medical technologies) (Emmons *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, issues of privacy and protection of study participants are crucial in research and beyond (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). If the scope of data collection is unbalanced, data sharing may well contribute to discrimination against individuals (Arvidsson and Hällgren, 2023) and even replicate automatism outside the scope of traditional public accountability, thus, strengthening stigmatization (Pavone *et al.*, 2024). The disclosure or misuse of genomic data for example includes stigmatization, abuse, potential discrimination in education, insurance employment contexts (Etchegary *et al.*, 2023). Accordingly, potential misuse of data is one of the reasons for commercial and cultural barriers to data sharing (Waterman *et al.*, 2021).

However, the issue of **stigmatization** is not data specific and concerns medical and non-medical data (e.g., ethnicity, GPS, patient addresses) as well as non-sensitive data (Cheah *et al.*, 2015). Eventually, the stigmatizing effect derives from a **combination of different data**, as illustrated by the field of **environmental health**. Here, collected data relates to geographic areas, housing characteristics, consumer product use, occupancy etc., of which especially location is critical since chemical exposures reveal residential histories, air quality, drinking water monitoring data etc. (Udesky *et al.*, 2020). None of this information is considered sensitive yet revealing in combination with genomic data (Udesky *et al.*, 2020). In addition, (adverse) consequences of environmental (health) data sharing are not equally distributed as some environments are of more interest than others (Udesky *et al.*, 2020). Accordingly, “consequences [of data sharing] could fall disproportionately on low-income, non-White communities” which are more often affected by polluting facilities and housing characteristics leading to higher levels of chemicals in homes (Udesky *et al.*, 2020, p. 426).

Moreover, the **collective quality** of data is crucial, and attention must be paid to the selective use of data and deriving biases and inequalities (Prainsack, 2021). In context of genomic data, potential legal discrimination (i.e., misuse) may harm patients *and* their communities (i.e., through identification and combination of data sets) (Cheah *et al.*, 2015; Etchegary *et al.*, 2023). Yet also non-personal data may contribute to discrimination, as illustrated by the description of an automated route recommendation:

*“These routes [depicted in the article] are crime risk-aware routes with longer distances. The reason behind this may be the homeless shelters in W 45th St, which helps provide temporary residence for homeless individuals. Some homeless individuals living in homeless shelters have many arrest records. The roads near W 45th St may have potential crime risk in active hours rather than the sleeping time. Note that our experiments were conducted based on the data in 2015. In 2017, the city Mayor announced a plan to close shelters, e.g., Aladdin Hotel, in W 45th St which brings many crime issues, such as violence and drug use” (Zhou *et al.*, 2021, p. 4665).*

Consequently, when thinking about incentivizing data sharing, focus on the individual level falls short; instead, issues of privacy need to be considered a **collective responsibility** as data about one person always reveals information about others, too (Prainsack, 2021).

On a **professional level**, negative returns entail **unintended use**, data **misinterpretation and loss** (i.e., security breaches), as well as **negative business consequences** (e.g., loss of competitive advantages) (McGuirk, O’Neill and Mee, 2015; Gunasekera, 2018). Risks of unintended use include confidentiality breaches, institutional exposure (McGuirk, O’Neill and Mee, 2015), state surveillance, companies denying insurance coverage (Bak *et al.*, 2023).

On a national level, concerns relate to security considerations and the risk of market monopolization (Gunasekera, 2018). Besides, data surveillance and accumulation involve power rivalries in local geopolitics, and hence, are easily perceived as a threat (Huang and Lyu, 2022).

To avoid the misuse of data and an increase in mistrust, **ethical data sharing practices** need to be ensured. Those include researchers respecting the intentions, **e.g., altruistic goals** of study participants (to speed up research, drive social change) and therefore, to refrain from potential commercial interests (Udesky *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, there may be potential differences in approach to those gathered on poorest populations and trustworthiness of data if ethical standards apply to protect low-income populations (Parker and Bull, 2015).

Potential misuse of data poses significant risks across multiple levels. At the individual level, data sharing can lead to discrimination, stigmatization, and privacy breaches, especially for marginalized communities and through networked data revealing collective information. Professionally, data misuse threatens competitive advantages, confidentiality, and institutional trust. Nationally, concerns include security risks and geopolitical power struggles. To mitigate these risks and build trust, ethical data sharing practices that respect participant intentions and protect vulnerable populations are essential.

Efforts to enable *secure* data sharing

Ensuring an **as secure as possible way of sharing data**, requires considerable efforts, both collectively and individually. The term *data friction* places emphasis on the challenges to be overcome to ensure data sharing: it *“acknowledges how, contrary to widespread perception, information does not always flow easily or naturally. Often a multiplicity of practical and political tensions has to first be overcome via concerted efforts (see also Jacobson et al., 2018); and data have to actively be made to move through a delicate patchwork of mechanisms, processes, incentives and infrastructures”* (Elbe, 2021, p. 667).

This includes **(considerable) costs of data sharing on multiple levels** (e.g., Welle Donker and van Loenen, 2018). Researchers remained critical in relation to data sharing due to “*potential harms to patients and communities, potential harms to researchers and research groups, and concerns about the availability of resources required for effective data sharing*” (Cheah *et al.*, 2015, p. 286), including regulatory (e.g., ownership over data, required anonymity of research participants, need to understand increased legal obligations), management (e.g., managing and archiving open data) and content-related concerns (e.g., difficulty to interpret data, especially by third parties, training needs for dealing with large data sets) (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020; Heacock *et al.*, 2020).

Currently, the scientific system does not necessarily hold advantages for data sharing and places the burden of sharing data and open data on individuals (in terms of available infrastructure, training, maintenance) (Hicks, 2023) as these practices demand additional efforts, e.g., (time) resources (Cheah *et al.*, 2015; Borgerud and Borglund, 2020) and skills to make data ready for reuse (Hodonu-Wusu, Noorhidawati and Abrizah, 2020).

In general, international networks facilitate data sharing. Yet, concerns about losing control and a lack of formal recognition remain (Slobodova, 2020). Missing acknowledgement could deprive “*original investigators of appropriate return of investment of time and expertise*” (Cheah *et al.*, 2015, p. 283). To avoid losing publication opportunities, researchers may not wish to share data rapidly, despite some data’s potential to develop lifesaving and commercially lucrative inventions (Destro Bisol *et al.*, 2014; Cheah *et al.*, 2015; Polanin and Williams, 2016; Elbe, 2021), especially in disciplines that are involved long-term with their data (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). In addition, in the race for **reputation and money** (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020), data sharing potentially holds the threat of being exposed to criticism (e.g., for methods and interpretations) (Borgerud and Borglund, 2020). **Disincentives for individual scientific careers** need to be addressed adequately (publication moratoria, managing conflicts of interests, balancing commercial involvement and proprietary claims, complaints related to data sharing) to ensure a fair distribution of risks/benefits/burdens and uncertainties/risks of research initiatives (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019). Potential **counter measures** (at least a first step) could be a proper **attribution** through authorship or acknowledgement for data curation and sharing (Cheah *et al.*, 2015; Parker and Bull, 2015; Kalkman *et al.*, 2019; Slobodova, 2020).

Beyond research, e.g. in the context of public administration, open data policy meets technical and cultural challenges. Also here, the increasing complexity requires a **higher allocation of resources**. Decentralized repositories may ease data sharing practices, but are difficult for discovery, integration, and reuse of data (Roche *et al.*, 2020).

In summary, the current scientific system often places the burden of data sharing on individual researchers without sufficient support, creating disincentives despite the societal value of open data. To foster more effective and fair data sharing, incentives like proper attribution, training, infrastructure, and policies balancing risks and rewards are essential. Similar challenges exist beyond academia, including in public administration, where technical and cultural barriers persist alongside diverse motivations for sharing data.

Shifting economic structure(s) and social (in-)equality

Data sharing may contribute to **shifting economic structure(s)** on a micro- as well as on a macrolevel. On a microlevel, consequences of data sharing may affect actors in various ways, from declining customer satisfaction (annoyed by targeted promotion) to the fact that disadvantageous credit scoring and higher intermediation costs may affect SMEs more than larger businesses (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). In general, it is likely that data sharing reinforces competitive advantages of data-rich incumbents in the public sector domain, while open data has the potential to crowd out innovation (if publicly subsidized data access undermines the viability of market-driven business models) (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020).

On a macrolevel, data sharing may lead to businesses using farm data of others, to influencing markets via product prices (Zhang *et al.*, 2021), or to economic displacement through new available data (Haberer and Schnurr, 2020). Here, regulators need to address the economic power of individual companies (Prainsack, 2021), as their rise to power (e.g., in the health care domain) requires public actors to protect privacy and social justice to take a stand against power imbalances (Prainsack, 2021). On a meta level, the circulation of the data (e.g., genomic data) may affect the economy, as well as power structures in terms of sovereign control over genetic resources and creating new diplomatic practices about how to handle sequence data in future global health emergencies (Elbe, 2021).

This is particularly important as data sharing and related processing of data (e.g., big data) have been accused of **increasing and manifesting existing social inequalities**. They have been

said to **strengthen the digital divide**, between different population groups (Zhang *et al.*, 2021) as well as between different professions (i.e., researchers and non-research) (Emmons *et al.*, 2023). In the context of the former, the value of data sharing as a process needs to be prioritized over its asset value if discrimination, inequality and multiplying negative effects through replicating automatism are to be avoided (Pavone *et al.*, 2024). Regarding the latter, the niche skills and conditions required by open science principles (including open data) foster existing inequalities in access (e.g., favoring researchers with institutional access to resources above communities) (Emmons *et al.*, 2023).

In terms of **global fairness**, data sharing holds the potential for facing global issues, e.g. health crises, by speeding up the development of (new) medication, while remaining highly intertwined in long-standing global health inequalities between high- and low-income countries (Elbe, 2021), indicating the interrelation between data sharing and **economic power relations**.

Thus, data sharing is reshaping economic structures at both micro and macro levels. It can disproportionately impact small businesses, reinforce advantages of data-rich incumbents, and disrupt existing markets and industries. On a broader scale, data circulation, such as genetic sequence data, alters power dynamics between nations, raising issues of sovereignty and equity in global health governance. These shifts highlight the urgent need for regulatory frameworks that address privacy, social justice, and power imbalances in data-driven economies.

Fairness in distribution of benefits and risks

Economic power shapes structure and defines new dependencies and constraints, including monopolization (Timms, Hillier and Holland, 2022). In relation to this, the **question of fairness in distributing the benefits and risks** of data sharing is crucial. Considering that specific population groups, e.g., socioeconomic disadvantaged people, tend to pay with data instead of money, we need a more nuanced debate of whose data should be open, and to protect the right to say ‘no’ to sharing data (e.g. for commercial goals or in case of undesirable side-effects) (Prainsack, 2021). Besides, the value created by sharing people’s (health) data *“needs to come back to the people who created and collected the data, and to the public who built or funded the instruments and infrastructures with which the data were collected, stored, or analysed.”* (Prainsack, 2021, p. 651). Accordingly, the debate of **who benefits** is crucial, especially as (past) histories of extortion (e.g. biopiracy) contributes to the unease of communities to share data (Elbe,

2021). Reducing risks of data sharing to ‘privacy’ issues does not capture such debates and authorities need to enact people’s right to refuse sharing data if side-effects or purely commercial advantages show (Prainsack, 2021).

Fairness in distributing benefits and risks among all who participate in data sharing (including the ones whose data is shared), i.e. the issue of reciprocity of data sharing, showed frequently in our literature review and is closely linked to questions of discrimination and bias (in generating, sharing and accessing data). One strategy was to incentivize community-based research (Emmons *et al.*, 2023), especially when specific communities are disproportionately affected (here: specific ethnic communities with specific socio-economic status (Udesky *et al.*, 2020); or people participate in different roles in data sharing (e.g., communities, researchers, secondary users, and funders (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019). This, however, implies a case-by-case assessment and a managed approach to data sharing instead of open data initiatives (Cheah *et al.*, 2015).

Currently, (fair incentivization of) data sharing is hampered by social factors like **authorization** from human subjects and **different policies** between data set repositories (homogenization/standardization) (Polanin and Williams, 2016). This indicates a need for **raising awareness on the obligations and duties** that come with the trust for sharing other people’s data, including a good consent practice, effective and trusted data governance and an assessment of potential harms to data subjects, data collectors as well as public trust (Cheah *et al.*, 2015).

In summary, data sharing is deeply intertwined with issues of access and equity, reflecting broader digital and global divides that risk reinforcing social inequalities. Access to data and open science often favors well-resourced researchers and high-income countries, while marginalized communities and low-income populations face barriers and disproportionate risks. Economic imbalances and monopolization further complicate who benefits from data sharing, raising critical questions about fairness, reciprocity, and the right to refuse data sharing, especially when commercial interests are involved. To foster responsible and equitable data sharing, governance must prioritize transparent, managed approaches that balance benefits and harms, respect community rights, and ensure that value returns to all contributors.

The Issue of Trust

The issue of trust and its role and relevance for questions of data sharing can be understood as **a cross-sectional issue** touching upon questions regarding data recipients, transparency, social

interrelations as a basis for technical solutions, mistrust against specific actors or general mistrust. Trust and transparency are among the **core conditions** for data sharing, next to public interest and privacy and security (Waind, 2020). Usually, data sharing is characterized as a **result** from enhancing transparency and accountability, i.e., the increased controllability of otherwise closed off activities by the public (i.e., decision-making in research and policy). However, conceptualizing data sharing **from social interrelations** rather than a technical perspective, trust may be considered a **precondition** for data sharing.

In health data research, trust is essential on individual, collective and systemic level. **Individually**, patients are asked to hand control over their data to the institutions collecting and using it (Destro Bisol *et al.*, 2014); here, the willingness to do so is low, but even lower when data is shared openly or in publicly accessible databases (Etchegary *et al.*, 2023). **Collectively**, trust and cooperation in medical research between researchers, research subjects, funders and oversight bodies are crucial to help mitigating challenges of health data research, and hoped to result in more effective governance structures and responsible research practices (Bak *et al.*, 2023). Here, awareness of the benefits of data sharing and collaborative partnerships and sharing practices is core (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019). Besides, principles and norms to strengthen social accountability are crucial: *“Social accountability arises from engagement of individuals in society, supported by organisations that communicate to individuals and society about the expectations and failures of data governance”* (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019, p. 9). **Systemically**, data sharing beyond a denoted circle requires profound trust in societal institutions like the GDPR to address and handle uncertainties (Bak *et al.*, 2023).

Considering the fundamental importance of trust, trust has been denoted a rational rather than an irrational act as “trusting may still be rational when aiming to minimise anxiety about uncertainty in situations of vulnerability“ (Bak *et al.*, 2023, p. 194). As a result, public explanations of policies, information and oversight mechanisms, as well as public deliberation of privacy and solidarity may create trust-tags and allow for more democratic decision-making (Bak *et al.*, 2023).

The issue of trust is especially illustrated by the fact that the willingness of actors to share data **largely depends on recipients**, i.e., other stakeholder groups. Actors showed a higher willingness to share data with some actor groups (e.g. farmers) while refusing to share with others (e.g. agrobusiness or government), conceptualizing data sharing as relational issue (Zhang *et al.*,

2021). This emphasizes the **context-dependency** of data sharing in a social sense. People's willingness to share data seems to largely depend on the purpose of data sharing and the recipients of data, as well as different approaches to data sharing. In general, sharing with research facilities was often approved, in contrast to access by commercial entities or governments (Etchegary *et al.*, 2023). Among intended recipients, research outranked governments and the for-profit sector as sharing genetic data for commercial profit was rejected completely (Etchegary *et al.*, 2023). Yet, even expanding access for researchers was considered a potential hazard, making patients more vulnerable to hacking or data being misused (Udesky *et al.*, 2020). Accordingly, altruistic motives (advancing science, better treatments etc.) related to genetic and health data had to outweigh risks for people to share data (Udesky *et al.*, 2020).

In the context of agriculture, research institutes and other farmers were perceived as least problematic, followed by industry organizations and government statistical agency, while technology and service providers were perceived as less trustworthy and suspected of shifting market structures and benefit distribution (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). Considering that the latter have been at the forefront of driving the digital transformation and big data application in agriculture (Zhang *et al.*, 2021), this may also indicate low familiarity with or a general resistance towards these developments.

Trust plays a fundamental, cross-cutting role in data sharing, not merely as an outcome but as a vital precondition, shaped by social relations, institutional context, and the perceived intentions of data recipients. Literature highlights that willingness to share data is highly relational and context-dependent, varying across actors and sectors. Especially in sensitive areas like health research, trust must be fostered at individual, collective, and systemic levels, through transparent governance, public engagement, and clear communication about the benefits and safeguards of data use. Regulatory trust (e.g., in GDPR), ethical oversight, and sustained interpersonal cooperation are crucial to support responsible data practices. Ultimately, building trust is a long-term, dynamic process that requires ongoing dialogue, institutional commitment, and responsiveness to public concerns.

Conclusions of the Chapter

This literature review analyzed impacts, i.e. benefits and risks of data sharing, in detail, including but not restricted to the sectors of pilot partners in DATAMITE (telecommunication, energy, urban

services, meteorology, agri-food sector). We found that issues of data sharing are hardly addressed in a general manner. Accordingly, we refrained from investigating general benefits and risks and focused on impacts in a sector-specific way. Yet, mechanisms and principles span across dimensions and sectors, relating to improving knowledge, oversight and control, or participation and collaboration in policy as well as science and research, while the private sector remained underrepresented.

Overall, we found that data sharing holds **potential but depends on context and conditions**, like governance frameworks, trust, social conditions and ethical safeguards. While expectations for benefits of data sharing are high, empirical evidence remains fragmented and often scattered across sectors. Therefore, sectoral differences in relation to data governance (including data sharing) are significant.

Moreover, **common misconceptions** of data and data sharing must be challenged. First, data is not neutral but reflects social and institutional biases. Second, data sharing is not a purely technical process, rather, it is shaped by social and political relations. Third, openness does not automatically equal ‘good’ but needs to be reflected in the respective context as it may hold challenges for privacy or fairness. Fourth, data sharing does not automatically create value, rather value needs to be actively produced through collaboration, trust, and context-sensitive governance.

The review revealed **major (expected) benefits**, including enhanced transparency, accountability, and democratic participation; improved knowledge generation, innovation, and interdisciplinary collaboration; support for the greater good through collective data use for societal benefit; and indirect economic gains such as efficiency and better management of resources.

In turn, **major risks and challenges** include privacy violations and risks of re-identification despite anonymization; bias and discrimination embedded in or amplified by shared data and AI systems; misuse, misinterpretation, and decontextualization of shared data; and proliferation of societal inequalities, hence mistrust toward data holders or sharing mechanisms, particularly when power asymmetries exist.

One core issue that emphasizes the **social nature of data sharing** is the issue of **trust**, which is both a **prerequisite for as well as an outcome** of data sharing. Trust must be cultivated through transparent governance, participatory structures, and ethical safeguards. It develops gradually through responsible sharing practices.

Thus, acknowledging the **social embeddedness** of data sharing by balancing privacy, transparency, and public interest is critical. Effective data governance should ensure accountability, inclusiveness, and fairness, avoiding over-reliance on technical fixes. In terms of research, more systematic, empirical studies and integrated approaches that connect technical, legal, ethical, and societal perspectives are needed.

In short, data sharing can be a powerful driver of innovation, transparency, and social good, but only under conditions that ensure ethical responsibility, privacy protection, inclusivity, and contextual awareness. It is not inherently beneficial, its outcomes depend on how, by whom, and for what purposes it is implemented.

To ensure responsible data sharing, a broad range of principles have been proposed, including: (1) societal benefits and value; (2) distribution of risks, benefits and burdens; (3) respect for individuals and groups; and (4) public trust and engagement (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019). More concretely, this includes principles of equity and fairness, e.g. in sharing economic benefits and financial gains with communities who share data (Polanin and Williams, 2016; Emmons *et al.*, 2023), having a say in its use when sharing data (especially by historically disadvantaged communities to avoid exploitation (Prainsack, 2021; Emmons *et al.*, 2023)). Moreover, papers list ensuring a responsible conduct of results (Kalkman *et al.*, 2019) as well as resources and capacity, rethink consent, governance, open and managed access (Cheah *et al.*, 2015) as important points for responsible data sharing practices.

Annex C: In-depth Recommendations Analysis of Pilots per Topics

Urban Services Sector (GIDI)

The GIDI pilot focuses on data sharing within a large, decentralized corporate group, where companies operate as independent units despite belonging to the same umbrella organization. The pilot aimed to create an internal platform enabling secure, flexible data transactions across subsidiaries. Key challenges revolved around trust, data security, lineage, and cross-sectoral investment incentives.

1. Data Security and Controlled Access (Dimension 3)

Recommendation: Implement a tiered security framework to enable selective access for higher-level stakeholders.

Rationale: Security is a primary enabler of intra-organizational data sharing, especially when sensitive operational or customer-related data is involved. Limiting access based on roles increases trust and enables controlled collaboration.

Feasibility rating: 6 (Very high)

2. Anonymization and Data Lineage (Dimension 11)

Recommendation: Enhance anonymization processes and establish clear lineage mechanisms for shared data.

Rationale: Proper data lineage supports traceability and accountability, particularly when building new services or products based on aggregated data. Current gaps in lineage pose a barrier to trust and reuse.

Feasibility rating: 5 (High)

3. Monetization Models (Dimension 5)

Recommendation: Shift focus from pure data monetization to also include data sharing as a catalyst for innovation and internal efficiencies.

Rationale: While monetization is a goal, overemphasis on direct financial gain can hinder openness. A balanced approach, acknowledging indirect value creation through shared services or process improvement, is needed.

Feasibility rating: 3 (Low to moderate – due to cultural and strategic inertia)

4. Investment and Public-Private Data Exchange (Dimension 6)

Recommendation: Stimulate cross-sectoral investment in shared data systems, especially between public and private actors.

Rationale: Sectoral silos limit the reusability of urban services data. Creating mechanisms for data exchange between similar systems across public and private domains can unlock value and efficiency.

Feasibility rating: 3 (Moderate – requires coordination, funding, and common incentives)

In short, the GIDI pilot reflects the unique challenges of intra-corporate data sharing where organizational silos exist under a common brand. High feasibility is linked to technical enablers like security and anonymization, while lower feasibility is observed for strategic and cultural shifts, particularly around monetization and inter-sectoral collaboration. The findings underscore the importance of trust-building and clear data governance within corporate ecosystems.

Energy Sector (HEDNO and E-REDES)

The HEDNO and E-REDES pilots explored how trusted data sharing and improved governance mechanisms can support the digitalization of energy systems, facilitate system planning, and enhance stakeholder collaboration. Recommendations from these pilots span regulatory, technical, organizational, and societal dimensions. Below is a synthesis of their key recommendations:

1. Regulation and Interoperability (Dimensions 7, 11)

Recommendation: Legislation should act as a catalyst for interoperability and data sharing by explicitly mandating cross-stakeholder data exchange frameworks and stewardship mechanisms.

Rationale: Regulation can provide the necessary enforcement mechanism to overcome inertia and mistrust between actors. Traceability of data sources, including copyright or watermarking, is crucial for enabling lawful data reuse and preventing misuse.

Feasibility rating: 5 (High)

2. Ethics and Cybersecurity (Dimensions 3, 8, 11)

Recommendation: Ethical considerations must accompany legislative developments, particularly in areas involving personal data, cybersecurity, and privacy.

Rationale: Ethical norms often precede formal regulation. Ensuring legal and ethical safeguards is essential to protect sensitive energy data. Proper attribution and traceability of original data must be ensured (e.g., watermarking), especially when handling derivative data or shared datasets.

Feasibility rating: 6 (Very high)

3. Internal Process Redesign (Dimensions 9, 10)

Recommendation: Internal processes within DSOs and energy service providers must be redefined to align with data-sharing requirements.

Rationale: Current data maturity levels are low, and existing practices do not support efficient data interoperability or standardization. Without process adaptation, risks of duplication, inefficiency, or misuse persist.

Feasibility rating: 4 (Moderate)

4. Data Governance and Energy Efficiency (Dimensions 6, 10, 2)

Recommendation: Enhance data governance, quality management, and interoperability to reduce energy waste and improve AI model accuracy.

Rationale: Poor-quality data leads to inaccurate AI predictions, while redundant data storage or training of ineffective models wastes computational (and thus energy) resources. Improving data management is both a sustainability and operational imperative.

Feasibility rating: 4 (Moderate)

5. Digital Infrastructure Robustness (Dimensions 5, 10)

Recommendation: Invest in the robustness and digitalization of the energy infrastructure to enable scalable data sharing.

Rationale: Without digitized infrastructure, data access is severely limited or non-existent. It is a foundational requirement for any data-driven innovation in the sector.

Feasibility ratings: 5 and 3 (Ratings varied across pilots depending on maturity level and funding context)

6. Consumer Awareness and Behavioural Change (Dimensions 1, 2, 6, 9)

Recommendation: Promote consumer education to foster data-informed behaviour change.

Rationale: When consumers understand the value and impact of energy data, they are more likely to adopt efficient consumption patterns, supporting demand-side flexibility and sustainability goals.

Feasibility rating: 3 (Low to moderate, depends on outreach mechanisms and trust)

7. Industrial Engagement and Demand Response (Dimensions 6, 10, 2)

Recommendation: Encourage industrial stakeholders to participate in demand-shaping and response programs through better data access and clarity.

Rationale: High-quality, real-time data will empower industries to optimize energy use and respond dynamically to grid conditions.

Feasibility rating: 4 (Moderate)

8. Open Data and Scientific Innovation (Dimensions 1, 4, 10)

Recommendation: Enable greater openness of energy data to the scientific community.

Rationale: A positive feedback loop may emerge; more accessible data leads to more research, which in turn generates innovative solutions that benefit the energy system as a whole.

Feasibility rating: 6 (Very high, especially for aggregated or anonymized data)

This recommendation set demonstrates the energy sector’s dual focus on infrastructure readiness and governance maturity, with strong emphasis on regulatory drivers, data traceability, and engagement of both consumers and industries. The feasibility ratings reflect a mix of optimism for ethically grounded and regulatory-aligned initiatives, and moderate caution for those requiring deeper institutional or behavioural change.

Agriculture Sector (PSNC / eDWIN)

The PSNC pilot, building on the national agricultural platform eDWIN, addresses data sharing challenges in the farming sector. The recommendations focus on mindset transformation, incentives, regulatory alignment, and digital infrastructure, with a view to supporting a trusted, data-driven ecosystem for sustainable agriculture. Notably, many of the challenges are non-technical and center around behavioral, cultural, and institutional resistance to sharing data.

1. Farmer Trust and Cultural Barriers (Dimension 1)

Recommendation: Introduce targeted incentives and educational programs to increase farmers’ willingness to share data.

Rationale: Farmers are often hesitant to share data due to fears of surveillance or reputational risks. Long-term change requires trust-building, highlighting indirect benefits (e.g., better decision-making, reputation, reciprocity) rather than monetization alone.

Feasibility ratings: 2 (Low – due to deep-seated mindsets and long-term nature of change)

2. Data-Driven Services and Innovation (Dimension 1 & 5)

Recommendation: Encourage new services and direct sales models that benefit from shared data, especially for small and medium-sized farms.

Rationale: New services can incentivize participation by showing practical value. Larger players are often resistant to opening their production lines, but smaller actors may benefit from traceability, labeling, and direct-to-consumer sales.

Feasibility ratings: 2–6 (Varies by scale and readiness of value chain)

3. Environmental Objectives through Datafication (Dimension 2)

Recommendation: Use digital tools like online tracking systems and data standards to support ecological goals such as pesticide reduction and sustainable land use.

Rationale: Although difficult to measure in the short term, digitalization can indirectly support Green Deal objectives.

Feasibility ratings: 4 (for data quality standards); others not rated but considered long-term targets

4. Data Security and Food Safety (Dimension 3 & 7)

Recommendation: Strengthen data security and certification mechanisms to support food safety across the value chain.

Rationale: Security is a political and strategic concern, particularly where food and health are involved. Certification and standardization can support compliance and consumer trust.

Feasibility ratings: 5 (security), 3 (certification)

5. Regulatory Alignment and Data Sovereignty (Dimensions 7 & 11)

Recommendation: Link funding and compliance mechanisms (e.g., agricultural subsidies, research grants) to data-sharing standards and enforceable regulations.

Rationale: Nudging through funding creates strong incentives, especially in a sector where public support plays a large role. However, current tools (e.g., DATAMITE's sovereignty module) may require enhancement to support full traceability or certification.

Feasibility ratings: 2–6 (High when tied to funding; low when addressing deeper systemic issues)

6. Applied Research and Open Science (Dimension 4)

Recommendation: Promote data sharing among applied science communities to improve agricultural models and innovations.

Rationale: While basic research is often mandated to share data, applied researchers are less constrained. Open access to agricultural datasets can accelerate solution development.

Feasibility rating: 6 (High – already improving)

7. Ecosystem Collaboration and New Actors (Dimension 10)

Recommendation: Equip ecosystem actors (e.g., statistical service providers, agribusinesses, SMEs) with tools and platforms to collaborate effectively.

Rationale: Aggregated data is increasingly valuable for trend detection and predictive services. The inclusion of new players like statistical companies suggests a maturing data ecosystem.

Feasibility rating: 6 (High)

8. Business Digitization and SME Integration (Dimension 6)

Recommendation: Support smaller agribusinesses in their digital transition to enable participation in data markets and platforms.

Rationale: While PSNC often works with large-scale actors, small companies require tailored support to engage in data-driven innovation.

Feasibility rating: 4 (Moderate)

In short, the PSNC pilot highlights a clear tension between the strategic potential of agricultural data and the deeply ingrained cultural and structural barriers to sharing it. Many recommendations require long-term cultural change, regulatory support, and a strong incentive architecture. Feasibility ratings reflect the fact that while technical capabilities are emerging, broader adoption will depend on trust-building, policy support, and ecosystem-wide alignment.

Telecommunications Sector (OTE Group)

The OTE pilot addresses intra-organizational data sharing challenges within a large telecommunications group composed of independent subsidiaries. Key barriers include fragmented governance, low awareness among decision-makers, and unclear business models for data sharing. The recommendations focus on raising organizational awareness, improving governance structures, ensuring regulatory alignment, and developing sustainable data-driven business models. The pilot emphasizes that organizational buy-in is a precondition for any technical or regulatory success.

1. Awareness and Organizational Alignment (Dimension 9)

Recommendation: Develop an internal awareness strategy to promote understanding of the value and potential of data sharing across subsidiaries.

Rationale: Raising awareness among decision-makers is essential for shifting organizational mindsets and gaining executive support. Identifying a dedicated sponsor or using external consultants was seen as an effective way to catalyze this change.

Feasibility ratings:

- Create awareness strategy: 4
- Find internal sponsor: 6
- Use 3rd party consultant: 6

2. Transparency and Risk Understanding (Dimension 8)

Recommendation: Improve transparency and risk awareness through strategic communication and third-party input.

Rationale: Traceability is crucial for building trust in data sharing, and clearly understanding risk categories enables better decision-making around security and compliance.

Feasibility ratings:

- Increase transparency: 4
- Develop risk awareness strategy: 4
- Involve 3rd party consultant: 6

3. Process Optimization and Enablement Tools (Dimension 7)

Recommendation: Develop a structured playbook for data sharing processes across the organization.

Rationale: A standardized approach improves operational efficiency, reduces friction, and ensures compliance with internal procedures.

Feasibility rating: 6 (Very high)

4. Sustainable Business Model Development (Dimensions 5, 6)

Recommendation: Define a sustainable business model supported by market analysis.

Rationale: Demonstrating return on investment (ROI) is essential for convincing decision-makers of the long-term value of data sharing. Understanding market needs also clarifies the business case for data monetization or internal efficiencies.

Feasibility ratings:

- Define business model: 5
- Run market analysis: 6

5. Regulatory Compliance and Strategic Monitoring (Dimension 11)

Recommendation: Ensure continuous alignment with evolving regulatory requirements at both EU and regional levels.

Rationale: While complying with external regulations is often perceived as a constraint, establishing an internal team to monitor changes enables proactive strategy adaptation.

Feasibility ratings:

- Comply with regulation: 3
- Build monitoring team: 6

In short, the OTE pilot highlights a strong focus on organizational transformation and leadership engagement as prerequisites for effective data sharing. Technical capabilities were not the main bottleneck; instead, challenges stemmed from limited awareness, low trust, and lack of clarity on business value. High feasibility was associated with internal enablement strategies, external support, and structured planning tools, while regulatory compliance was perceived as more externally constrained and less under the pilot's direct control.

Meteorology Sector (CINECA / MISTRAL)

The CINECA pilot focuses on strengthening the national meteorological data infrastructure through the MISTRAL platform. The aim is to improve data discoverability, accessibility, and usability while responding to increasing demands for resilience, real-time processing, and support for AI-based applications. Unlike other pilots, CINECA operates primarily as a public infrastructure provider, with limited monetization intentions, but with growing attention to user base expansion and service differentiation.

1. Resilient Infrastructure for Big Data (Dimensions 1, 11)

Recommendation: Continue investing in distributed infrastructure to support system resilience and large-scale data management.

Rationale: As weather catastrophes become more frequent, resilience through decentralization becomes critical. Storage and processing needs are increasing, but advances in big data management make the challenge more manageable.

Feasibility rating: Not explicitly rated, but implicitly high (already ongoing and improving)

2. Strategic User Base Expansion (Dimensions 1, 5, 7, 3)

Recommendation: Expand and diversify the user base beyond core national agencies to include energy providers, researchers, airports, and logistics operators.

Rationale: A broader user base justifies infrastructure investment and enhances the societal value of the data. While public agencies guide the roadmap, the platform's utility depends on engaging more operational stakeholders.

Feasibility rating: Not explicitly rated, but described as essential and actively pursued → medium to high

3. Monetization and Service Tiering (Dimensions 5, 10)

Recommendation: Develop a differentiated service model, possibly including a subscription system, while considering legal constraints of public funding.

Rationale: While direct monetization is not a primary goal, introducing post-processing services and tiered access (basic vs. advanced users) can improve value delivery and sustainability. This could also help public agencies optimize cost-sharing.

Feasibility rating: Not explicitly rated, but described as conditional on legal reform and agency support → medium

4. Data for AI and Predictive Modeling (Dimension 4)

Recommendation: Ensure access to more diverse, high-frequency data (e.g., radar, satellite) to support new AI and numerical models.

Rationale: Scientific and operational users increasingly rely on data-intensive methods. Enabling these requires expanding the data pipeline, improving quality and volume.

Feasibility rating: Not explicitly rated, but seen as technically achievable and urgent → high

In short, the CINECA pilot illustrates how a public data infrastructure can evolve toward a service-oriented platform supporting critical societal functions like weather prediction, catastrophe planning, and renewable energy management. The focus is not on direct monetization, but on resilience, scientific innovation, and public value creation. Feasibility hinges on continued investment, regulatory flexibility, and strategic collaboration with public agencies.

Annex D: Interview Questionnaire

Introduction

As you know, our task sets out to identify communalities and differences between the sectors in DATAMITE in terms of non-monetary impacts of data sharing as part of a monetization strategy.

Pilot X aims at Y.

1. What was the motivation/reason to do so in the first place?
2. When starting this initiative, which impacts of data sharing did you consider? Please give an example.
3. Which non-monetary impacts did you consider most relevant? Please elaborate.
 - a. Do you exploit them strategically? If so, which ones?
 - b. Check: Other ones than ours from our workshop (societal, environmental, security, scientific, business-related, macroeconomic)? If yes: Please explain!
4. Have the impact dimensions you consider changed throughout DATAMITE?

Business-related impacts

5. Think about wider impacts (benefits/risks). How will data sharing in your sector have wider impacts (benefits/risks)?
 - a. Can you give examples?
6. How do you expect non-monetary impacts to shape your approach to data sharing and your business practices in general?
7. When you think about business-related non-monetary impacts: Which ones do you consider most important for your sector?
 - a. Do you exploit them strategically? If so, which ones?

Practices

8. Think about the practices of your company and the organization of the energy sector.
 - a. How do you expect data sharing to affect workflows here? Please give examples.
 - b. Check: Do you expect shifts in terms of employment, training, workflows (e.g. work conditions) etc.? Which ones? Which ones would you consider the most challenging?

9. Which conditions have to be met to strengthen data sharing in your sector?
 - a. What are the most important hurdles that currently prevent data sharing in your sector and your initiative more specifically?
 - b. How could you overcome these hurdles?
 - c. In your case: who is data owner and how to deal with this question?
 - d. Check: The EC has identified the lack of tools as key (see above) – is this also true for your sector?

How to enhance reflection

10. What do you expect from analysing and reflecting on non-monetary impacts for your initiative from DATAMITE?
 - a. How would it be possible to strengthen reflection on non-monetary impacts?
 - b. Do you consider this necessary? Why/ why not?
 - c. Should Task 4.4 focus on anything in particular?

Thank you for your time!

Annex E: Visions of Pilot Partners

Vision technology provider, oversees defining data flows and processes (GIDITEK, Pilot 1)

The interviewee articulates a clear vision focused on collaboration, data integration, and project synergy within his organization. Here are the key elements of his vision:

- **Unified Data Architecture:** The interviewee emphasizes the importance of developing a unified architecture for data management across the group. He mentions, "We are developing a new Data Lake, Delta Lake, and Data Warehouse architecture for the whole group" . This indicates his commitment to streamlining data processes and enhancing efficiency.
- **Exploring Synergies:** He highlights the potential for collaboration between various projects, stating, "Exploring synergies between the different projects we have is the main point". This reflects his belief in leveraging existing resources and knowledge to create larger, more impactful initiatives.
- **Data Sharing:** The interviewee envisions a secure and flexible data-sharing solution among different companies within the group. He confirms, "the idea is to share data between different components of the group in a secure and flexible way ". This underscores his focus on collaboration and transparency.
- **Resource Investment:** He acknowledges the significant investment of resources into these initiatives, indicating a long-term commitment to achieving his vision: "We are investing a lot of resources into this task“.

Overall, the interviewee's vision is centred on creating a cohesive and collaborative environment that maximizes the potential of data across various projects and companies.

1. Focus on Secure Data Sharing:

The interviewee emphasizes the importance of secure data sharing, particularly in environments that handle critical infrastructures like distributed energy production systems (e.g., photovoltaic systems for individual homes). The vision is to develop and deploy tools that enable secure, risk-free data exchanges. A central pillar of this vision is to demonstrate that sharing data can be safe

without compromising sensitive information. This would address current concerns in the energy and technology sectors, where security risks often lead to reluctance in sharing data.

2. Leveraging European Regulations and Governance:

The vision acknowledges the growing importance of aligning with European regulations such as the Data Governance Act and other EU governance frameworks. The organization aims to benefit from these legal frameworks by using tools and guidelines that ensure compliance at both national and European levels. The goal is to not only protect the company's interests in Spain but also across the broader European market. The interviewee emphasizes the need for better knowledge and application of these legal tools to strengthen the company's position.

3. Introducing a New Paradigm for Data Sharing:

The interviewee's vision includes the introduction of a new paradigm for how the company approaches data sharing. This paradigm shift is seen as vital for accessing new contracts and opportunities that are currently limited by technical and legal constraints. The organization aims to integrate data sharing into its operations more seamlessly, making it a cornerstone of business strategy rather than a risk to be managed.

4. Concrete Tools for Non-Monetary Benefits:

A key part of the vision is the development of concrete, practical tools that facilitate the measurement and management of non-monetary benefits from data sharing. The interviewee specifically mentions the need for tools that provide tangible ways to assess the value of transparency, security, and trust that come from sharing data. This would be a way to enhance the company's decision-making processes and contribute to long-term strategic goals. There is a desire for these tools to be actionable and not abstract, allowing for their direct application within different departments.

5. Cross-Departmental Adoption and Wider Company Engagement:

The interviewee sees the adoption of these tools and principles as a collective effort that goes beyond his department. He envisions introducing these new ideas and tools to other departments and even to partner companies. The aim is to foster a shared understanding of the importance of data sharing and compliance with European regulations across the organization. This broader engagement is crucial for scaling the benefits of the new paradigm throughout the company.

6. Workshop and Collaboration to Refine the Approach:

A key part of this vision involves ongoing reflection and collaboration. The interviewee acknowledges that the company needs to continue refining its approach to data sharing, security, and non-monetary benefits through dialogue and workshops. The upcoming workshop in Aachen, for example, is seen as a valuable opportunity to further discuss and solidify these ideas, engaging with both internal and external stakeholders to ensure that the company's approach is forward-looking and comprehensive.

7. Measuring Success Through New KPIs:

The interviewee also emphasizes the need for new key performance indicators (KPIs) that go beyond traditional financial metrics. These KPIs would track the success of the non-monetary aspects of data sharing, such as transparency, security, and the number of new contracts or opportunities accessed because of improved data sharing practices. The vision is to use these new KPIs to demonstrate the value of adopting a more open and secure approach to data sharing.

In essence, the vision emerging from the conversation is one where the company aims to transform its approach to data sharing, particularly by leveraging secure tools and European regulations. This transformation would help the organization access new opportunities while ensuring that the data sharing process is safe, transparent, and compliant with the highest legal standards. Non-monetary benefits, such as improved trust, transparency, and security, are seen as essential to this vision, and the company is keen to develop concrete tools to measure and leverage these benefits across its departments. Workshops and collaboration with other stakeholders are also seen as key to refining and executing this vision.

Vision for Telecom Operator (OTE, Pilot 2)

As a telecom operator that also provides various services and operates subsidiaries in various industries, OTE is in a unique position to unlock several advantages from data sharing across business units (business, marketing, network, customer support, HR, etc.). However, there are plenty of other valuable benefits that can boost organizations' efficiency, customer satisfaction, and innovation potential.

1. Improved Customer Experience and Personalization

By sharing data between telecom services and ICT offerings, they can gain a deeper understanding of customer behaviors and preferences. This will lead to:

- **Tailored Services:** With more data at hand, personalized services can be created for customers, offering the right combination of telecom, cloud, and other digital services that suit their individual needs.
- **Improved/Enhanced Customer Interactions:** When data is shared across subsidiaries, customers experience a seamless journey between the services they receive.
- **Proactive Support:** Data insights can help the organisation predict potential issues before they occur (e.g. network predictive maintenance).

2. Increased Efficiency and Cost Savings

Sharing data between different units/ divisions of the organization can streamline operations and reduce costs:

- **Better Resource Allocation:** Data from various business units, like telecom and ICT, can be combined to optimize network performance and service management, avoiding duplicated efforts and ensures smoother operations.
- **Centralized Reporting:** Migrating data in a common data warehouse allows for unified reporting and decision-making.
- **Improved Forecasting:** Combining data from telecom usage, cloud services, and financial performance will give stronger insights into future trends, helping make better long-term decisions.

3. Fueling Innovation and New Services

Data sharing can inspire new ideas and drive innovation within the organization:

- **Creating New Services:** Combining data from telecom and ICT offerings can lead to new products.
- **Faster Development:** When different teams across subsidiaries have access to shared data, they can work together more effectively.
- **Encouraging Cross-Industry Innovation:** Leverage data from diverse sectors to innovate in ways competitors can't.

4. Building a Stronger Market Position

Data sharing can help organization to stand out from the competition by offering a more comprehensive and unified approach:

- **Cross-Selling Opportunities:** When subsidiaries share customer data, it's easier to identify cross-selling opportunities.
- **Stronger Brand Loyalty:** With a better understanding of customer preferences and behaviours, organisation can create more personalized and relevant experiences, making it easier to keep customers.
- **More Targeted Marketing:** Shared data can help organisation identify trends and target specific customer segments more effectively.

5. Improved Security and Risk Management

Data sharing improves security across your subsidiaries:

- **Unified Security Systems:** Sharing data allows organisation to spot vulnerabilities across business more easily.
- **Enhanced Fraud Prevention:** By combining telecom and financial data, for instance, can create stronger fraud detection systems, protecting both business and customers.

6. Better Compliance and Governance

Sharing data across subsidiaries can also address regulatory compliance and improve corporate governance:

- **Easier Compliance Reporting:** Makes regulatory reporting more accurate and less time-consuming, especially in industries with complex rules.
- **Increased Transparency:** Shared data creates a more transparent view of the organisation's operations, helping manage risks and ensure accountability.

Data sharing offers telecom operators with multiple subsidiaries a range of benefits that go beyond monetization. By integrating data across various business units, organizations can

enhance customer experiences, improve efficiency, fuel innovation, and strengthen your market position. Additionally, it allows for better security, risk management, and regulatory compliance.

It is essential to build an efficient data-sharing infrastructure that enables collaboration across subsidiaries while ensuring privacy and compliance are upheld. This holistic approach offered through DATAMITE will enable organisation to be on board in a competitive and data-driven market.

Vision Energy sector (HEDNO and E-REDES, Pilot 3 and 4)

(extracted from Interview with E-REDES, summarized by SCISPACE, cross-checked, validated and re-worked by authors)

The vision for open data sharing at E-REDES is a comprehensive framework that not only addresses the immediate needs of data sharing but also anticipates future challenges and opportunities. This expanded vision can be articulated through several additional dimensions:

- **Sustainability of Data Practices:** The organization recognizes that for open data initiatives to be sustainable, they must be integrated into the core business processes. This involves continuous training and support for employees to foster a mindset that values data sharing as a critical component of their roles. By embedding data sharing into the organizational culture, E-REDES can ensure that it becomes a norm rather than an exception.
- **Feedback Mechanisms:** Establishing robust feedback mechanisms is essential for refining the open data strategy. Engaging with users of the open data portal, including external stakeholders and internal teams, can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the datasets shared. This feedback loop can help identify gaps in data offerings and inform future data collection efforts, ensuring that the organization remains responsive to the needs of its users.
- **Collaboration with Academia and Research Institutions:** By strengthening partnerships with academic and research institutions, E-REDES can leverage external expertise to enhance its data quality and usability. Collaborative projects can lead to innovative applications of the data, driving further societal benefits and demonstrating the value of open data sharing.

- **Promoting Data Literacy:** A critical aspect of the vision is promoting data literacy among stakeholders. By providing training and resources, E-REDES can empower users to effectively utilize the open data available to them. This not only enhances the impact of the data shared but also fosters a community of informed users who can advocate for further data sharing initiatives.
- **Addressing Ethical Considerations:** As the organization expands its open data efforts, it must remain vigilant about ethical considerations surrounding data privacy and security. Developing clear guidelines and ethical frameworks for data sharing will help mitigate risks and build trust among stakeholders. This proactive approach can alleviate concerns and encourage more robust participation in open data initiatives.
- **Long-term Vision and Impact Assessment:** Finally, E-REDES should establish a long-term vision for its open data strategy, including clear goals and metrics for success. Regular impact assessments can help the organization measure the effectiveness of its data sharing efforts and make necessary adjustments. This strategic approach will ensure that open data initiatives continue to align with the organization's mission and societal needs.

In summary, the expanded vision for open data sharing at E-REDES encompasses sustainability, collaboration, education, ethical considerations, and long-term planning. By addressing these dimensions, the organization can enhance its open data strategy, ultimately maximizing its positive impact on society and fostering a culture of transparency and collaboration.

Background information from: The state of European Energy Data Maturity:

- The future vision for the energy sector emphasizes the acceleration of data usage to achieve data democratisation. Energy companies recognize the need to enhance their data sharing capabilities both internally and externally within the next 24-36 months.
- There is a strong commitment to increase investment in data sharing tools, with 51% of companies planning to do so, and 61% intending to train staff on better data utilization in their roles.
- The majority of organizations (92%) either have a data use strategy in place or plan to introduce one in the near future, indicating a growing maturity in organizational data practices.

- Energy players are also focusing on engaging new stakeholders, such as local authorities and customers, to meet evolving requirements related to decarbonisation and electrification of transport and heat.
- The sector aims to enhance visibility and operational reach across the entire energy supply chain to ensure security of supply.
- Digitalisation is a key priority, as it allows energy companies to operate more efficiently by automating processes and moving away from paper-based operations.

Vision Agriculture sector (PSNC/WODR, Pilot 5)

The dynamic development of agricultural global commercial markets requires permanent monitoring and analysis of the large amount of data coming from multiply sources like trade, food production (e.g. crop yields), chemical companies (e.g. fertilizers), seed providers, machinery producers, earth observation data and other actors of agrifood value chain. The data are essential for taking decisions on the best strategies in food production. Quick access to accurate high-quality data can have enormous economic impact for the stakeholders in the sector.

In agriculture there is nowadays a lack of a data sharing culture, trust in sharing data, transparency in data usage, as well as data security and ownership issues. Data owners, such as farmers, are very reluctant to share any data, especially without incentives. Most of the collected data is never shared or even used, or it is only utilized within silos by one institution (there is usually an issue with identifying the data). As a result, the EU Code of Conduct on Agricultural Data Sharing was issued (by the end of 2018) with guidelines around transparent data sharing and signed by various EU associations representing different sectors of the agro-food chain. The document focusses on setting transparent principles, clarifying responsibilities, and creating trust among partners. Nevertheless, putting in practice such principles is still far behind, especially in countries where the code is not even known by most stakeholders.

The data in agriculture is often stored in unstructured or proprietary formats, and represented according to different models, thereby hampering data interoperability and exchange across multiple solutions. The lack of semantic interoperability between different data collections is particularly challenging considering the vast glossaries, for example those related to plant varieties, which are defined differently by different stakeholders. Integration between such systems is costly and very time-consuming.

Hence, a key challenge in data sharing is to agree on the model used for data representation. In the agriculture domain, there are dozens of ontologies/vocabularies, which have been created for different purposes/applications. Currently over 150 resources are available just in Agroportal, the largest repository of agri-related semantic resources, and generally each is having a different focus or specialization. So, instead of requiring agreement on only one model, more recent approaches focus on creating the interoperability pathways between existing standards and well-known models. This is the case, for example, of the Agriculture Information Model (AIM), which harmonizes and aligns relevant cross-domain standards with domain models, bridging various views on the agriculture data and providing a formal representation enabling unambiguous translations between them and establishing the basis to enable a semantic interoperability data space.

There is a strong movement at the EU level, where several cross-sectoral/horizontal activities and sector-specific actions have been launched to create an environment fostering the sharing and (re-)use of data. The European Strategy for Data (February 2020) aims to establish a Single Market for data, enabling data flow between countries and sectors and easy access and use of data based on a common understanding as well as regulations that respect European values. Accordingly, the EC has launched various initiatives including the Data Governance Act, which establishes a legal foundation and framework to facilitate data sharing within the EU, an implementing Act on High Value Data Sets, and the Data Act and a Horizontal Act of AI, which include provisions on access rights between parties in IoT data sharing contexts and mechanisms for Business to Government data sharing in specific situations.

Moreover, another initiative that is aiming to be game changer in the sector for sharing the data is the Common European Agriculture Data Space, which aims to support trustworthy data sharing in the sector and the development of commonly agreed business and governance models. It has been rolled out in two steps: first, a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) provided a proposal for governance structures business models and building blocks. Based on these results the implementation action, to start next year, will set up the data space. Finally, a partnership on agriculture data has been setup with the aim to enhance sustainable agricultural production and to strengthen policy monitoring and evaluation capacities through exploiting the potential of Earth Observation, environmental, agricultural and other data, in combination with state-of-the-art data technologies. Only recently, within research institutions, some national funding agencies are

mandating that final results be stored following the FAIR principles for reusability, but this pertains only to scientific projects.

In addition, in the agri-food domain, food safety and quality are essential. The digital revolution has provided many opportunities for monitoring and optimizing processes throughout the entire food production chain (from farm to fork). However, innovative services, particularly those based on AI, require high-quality data and a wide range of trusted data sources from different providers. Effective passporting in agriculture, a system that tracks and shares critical data throughout the entire food production chain, depends on overcoming significant challenges in data sharing, including trust issues, transparency, and data security. Farmers and other stakeholders are often hesitant to share their data, which limits the potential for integrated, data-driven solutions. Agrego¹⁶ aims to address these challenges by providing a centralized platform where data from various sources can be securely aggregated, managed, and shared. However, to fully harness the benefits of passporting through Agrego, several strategic enhancements are needed.

One crucial area is the monetization of data sharing through passporting. By integrating data marketplaces and data spaces into the Agrego platform, we can create new revenue streams for farmers and other data owners. These tools allow stakeholders to securely share their data while retaining control over how it is used, providing an incentive to participate in data sharing. For instance, farmers could sell anonymized data related to crop yields or farming practices, which could then be used by other actors in the agricultural value chain for research, development, and optimization of agricultural processes.

Moreover, utilizing data spaces, collaborative environments that facilitate data exchange between trusted partners, can enhance the functionality of passporting within Agrego. These spaces ensure that shared data is not only secure but also easily accessible and interoperable across different systems. By leveraging the advancements from our work in WP4, such as standardized data models and improved data governance frameworks, Agrego can support the utilization of these data spaces, allowing for seamless integration of passporting data across the agricultural sector.

¹⁶ <https://agregop.pl/> [21.11.2025]

In addition, data collected through passporting can be utilized to develop new services and products within the agricultural sector. For example, analytics services can use this data to provide insights into market trends, optimize supply chain logistics, or even improve crop management practices through predictive modeling. This not only adds value to the data itself but also creates a virtuous cycle of data sharing and innovation.

In summary, by integrating data marketplaces and data spaces with Agrego, and by promoting a culture of data sharing and trust, we can unlock significant economic opportunities through passporting. These efforts will not only enhance the transparency and efficiency of agricultural production but also create new avenues for stakeholders to monetize their data, ultimately driving innovation and sustainability in the sector.

Vision Meteorological Data (CINECA, Pilot 6)

1. Focus on Data Infrastructure and Scalability

- **Challenge of Growing Data Volumes:** One of the key challenges CINECA foresees is the exponential growth in the volume of data, which is expected to reach petabytes in size. This increase will necessitate a shift in infrastructure capacity to ensure efficient data sharing, processing, and storage. Current systems may not be equipped to handle such large-scale data in the future, which will require CINECA to continuously upgrade its infrastructure.
- **Technical Solutions:** The vision includes developing more advanced, scalable infrastructures to manage these large datasets effectively. The infrastructure will need to evolve to accommodate the growing size and complexity of meteorological and related environmental data.

2. Expanding Use Cases for Meteorological Data

- **Business and Downstream Applications:** CINECA envisions its meteorological data being used by other entities for business purposes, though it doesn't currently pursue these applications itself. They see potential for businesses to develop downstream applications or create business models based on the meteorological data they provide. These

applications could be in areas like agriculture, environmental management, or natural disaster prediction (e.g., flooding or landslides).

- **Facilitation Role:** While CINECA focuses on the technical side, they envision being an enabler or facilitator for other companies and institutions that could leverage the data for innovation, research, or business development. They view their role as providing the infrastructure and data, with others taking the initiative to extract value from it.

3. Enabling Open Access and Expanding User Base

- **Broadening Access:** CINECA aims to make its data more widely accessible to a larger community, particularly to researchers and institutions that could benefit from high-quality meteorological data. The vision is to reach more users, beyond just their consortium partners, by making their data available through European portals and open-access frameworks.
- **User Levels and Data Quality:** They foresee different levels of user access, ranging from general public users to institutional and research users who may need more advanced data processing tools. Improving data quality and ensuring better data completeness are seen as key components to making the data more usable and impactful.

4. Post-Processing Services as Potential Business Models

- **Post-Processing and Value-Added Services:** CINECA sees a future where they may offer advanced post-processing services to their users. These services could include filtering, extracting specific data sets, or custom-tailoring meteorological data for specific use cases (e.g., high-resolution forecasts for specific regions).
- **Monetization Potential:** While currently their focus is non-monetary, they acknowledge the potential to develop business models around these services, possibly introducing premium features for advanced users in the future. CINECA is open to exploring monetization options, such as charging fees for more detailed or customized data services.

5. Collaboration with Government and Research Institutions

- **Partnerships with Meteorological Agencies:** A core part of their vision involves continued collaboration with national and regional meteorological agencies, such as the Italian Meteorological Agency (ARPA). These partnerships are crucial for maintaining the data and infrastructure, as well as for developing new models and services.
- **Future Role in Environmental Forecasting:** They expect their infrastructure and data services to contribute to broader environmental forecasting efforts, such as predicting floods, landslides, and other natural disasters. This aligns with the non-monetary, societal benefits that are at the heart of their current projects.

6. Data Quality Assurance and New Data Models

- **Ensuring Data Quality:** CINECA places significant emphasis on the quality assurance of the data they handle. They are looking to improve tools that ensure data completeness and reliability, making it more useful for both researchers and public agencies.
- **New Forecasting Models:** The vision includes incorporating new types of forecasting models, including AI-driven models, into their services. They are already working on nowcasting (short-term forecasting) models and aim to integrate more advanced models in the future.

7. Experimentation and Innovation Hub

- **Pilot Projects and Experimentation:** CINECA sees its projects as an "experimental ground" for testing new data-sharing technologies and models. By engaging in these innovative pilot programs, they aim to learn and adapt, improving their infrastructure and services over time. These pilots serve as case studies for larger-scale implementations across Europe.
- **Non-Monetary Impacts Focus:** A key part of their vision is to continue focusing on non-monetary impacts, particularly those related to public safety (e.g., flood and weather forecasting). They are keen to explore and enhance the societal benefits of their work, with less emphasis on commercial gains, at least for now.

CINECA's vision revolves around upgrading infrastructure to handle increasing data volumes, facilitating the use of their meteorological data for downstream applications, expanding access to a larger user base, and improving data quality. While they focus on technical aspects, they see their role as an enabler of innovative uses of the data by others. Future possibilities include monetizing post-processing services and continuing to contribute to public safety through accurate environmental forecasting. They aim to be a key player in the data-sharing ecosystem, driving both technical innovation and societal benefits.

This vision reflects both their immediate challenges and their aspirations for the future of meteorological data handling and sharing.

Annex F: Thematic Comparison Matrix

Dimension	HEDNO (Energy - Greece)	CINECA (Meteorological - Italy)	E-REDES (Energy - Portugal)	GIDI (Technology Provider - Spain)	OTE (Telecom - Greece)	PSNC (Agriculture - Poland)
1. Technical Interoperability	Semi-automated pipeline with data gathering software (18+ months implementation); Internal data-sharing system where "people will be involved, but through some pipelining that's more efficient"	Scalable infrastructure for petabyte-scale data volumes; Advanced post-processing services (filtering, extracting, custom-tailoring); New forecasting models including AI-driven and nowcasting	Common data warehouse for unified reporting	"Developing a new Data Lake, Delta Lake, and Data Warehouse architecture for the whole group"	Centralized/common data warehouse; Migration to unified reporting systems	Agriculture Information Model (AIM) harmonizes cross-domain standards; Over 150 semantic resources in Agroportal; Interoperability pathways between existing standards

<p>2. Data Governance</p>	<p>New roles: data stewards, governance officers, business owners, data owners; "Permanent company regulation" under development (weeks to months); Standard operating procedures for evaluating, authorizing, delivering data</p>	<p>Tools to ensure data completeness and reliability; Quality assurance emphasis</p>	<p>Feedback mechanisms with users; Clear guidelines and ethical frameworks; Regular impact assessments</p>	<p>Cross-departmental adoption; "New paradigm for data sharing approach"</p>	<p>Unified governance across business units (business, marketing, network, customer support, HR)</p>	<p>EU Code of Conduct on Agricultural Data Sharing (issued end of 2018); FAIR principles mandated by research institutions for final results</p>
<p>3. Legal and Regulatory Compliance</p>	<p>Currently obliged by law to share data with regulatory bodies, ministries, energy providers; "Generally, either we are obliged by law, or in some cases...by a letter from the Ministry"; EU data space participation being explored</p>	<p>Collaboration with national/regional meteorological agencies (ARPA)</p>	<p>Strategic planning with clear goals and metrics for success</p>	<p>Aligning with "Data Governance Act and other EU governance frameworks"; "Benefit from these legal frameworks...to protect the company's interests in Spain...and across the broader European market"</p>	<p>Easier compliance reporting "especially in industries with complex rules"; Increased transparency</p>	<p>Data Governance Act; Implementing Act on High Value Data Sets; Data Act; Horizontal Act of AI; Common European Agriculture Data Space (CSA and</p>

						implementation action)
4. Trust and Data Ethics	"Balances regulatory compliance, internal efficiency, and societal value"; Trust as foundation of ecosystem	Focus on "public safety (e.g., flood and weather forecasting)"; "Non-monetary impacts, particularly those related to public safety"	"Addressing ethical considerations surrounding data privacy and security"; "Developing clear guidelines and ethical frameworks"; "Proactive approach can alleviate concerns"	"Demonstrate that sharing data can be safe without compromising sensitive information"; "Security risks often lead to reluctance in sharing data"; Focus on transparency, security, and trust	Enhanced fraud prevention; Unified security systems; Privacy and compliance upheld	"Lack of...trust in sharing data, transparency in data usage, as well as data security and ownership issues"; "Farmers are very reluctant to share any data, especially without incentives"; EU Code focuses on "transparent principles, clarifying responsibilities, and creating trust"

<p>5. Economic and Business Models</p>	<p>Focus on "non-monetary benefits of sharing the data"; "If you don't want to monetize, but all the previous steps...are also really important to you"; Data-driven service evaluation capacity</p>	<p>Currently non-monetary focus; "Potential to develop business models" around post-processing services; "Monetization options, such as charging fees for more detailed or customized data services"; "Premium features for advanced users in the future"</p>	<p>"Sustainability of data practices...integrated into core business processes"</p>	<p>"New paradigm...vital for accessing new contracts and opportunities"; "New KPIs that go beyond traditional financial metrics" to track transparency, security, new contracts/opportunities</p>	<p>Cross-selling opportunities between subsidiaries; Stronger brand loyalty; Targeted marketing</p>	<p>"Monetization of data sharing through passporting"; "Data marketplaces and data spaces...create new revenue streams"; "Farmers could sell anonymized data related to crop yields or farming practices"; "Create a virtuous cycle of data sharing and innovation"</p>
<p>6. Data Quality and Usability</p>	<p>"When we reach the maturity of the data with good data quality and</p>	<p>"Data quality assurance...significant emphasis";</p>	<p>Enhanced data quality through feedback</p>	<p>"Concrete, practical tools that facilitate the measurement and</p>	<p>Better forecasting through combined</p>	<p>"Data...stored in unstructured or proprietary</p>

	data rate and readiness to be...published"; "Data ready in a better quality, but sooner"	"Improving tools that ensure data completeness and reliability"; "Different levels of user access, ranging from general public users to institutional and research users"	mechanisms with users	management of non-monetary benefits"; Tools that "provide tangible ways to assess the value"	data from multiple sources	formats, and represented according to different models, thereby hampering data interoperability" ; "Lack of semantic interoperability between different data collections"
7. Cultural and Organizational Readiness	"Significant organizational culture shift"; "Key people have to make decisions in order to enforce this change"; Currently "work in the margin...of the operations in the company. So it's not our first priority"; "Mental shift...isn't something	"Experimental ground for testing new data-sharing technologies"; Pilot projects as learning opportunities; "Aim to learn and adapt"	"Continuous training and support for employees to foster a mindset that values data sharing"; "Embedding data sharing into the organizational culture...becomes a	"Cultural shift across departments"; "Foster a shared understanding of the importance of data sharing and compliance"; "Collective effort that goes beyond his department"	Seamless journey between services across subsidiaries	"Lack of a data sharing culture" in agriculture sector; "Most of the collected data is never shared or even used, or it is only utilized within silos";

	that's just being diffused within the company" (limited to small group)		norm rather than an exception"			"Putting in practice such principles is still far behind, especially in countries where the code is not even known"
8. Human and Technical Capacity	"Training people for new roles like data governing, governance, specialist data stewards, business owners, data owners"; "Training them to do what is being asked"	Technical expertise in handling large-scale meteorological data; Infrastructure scaling capabilities	"Promoting data literacy among stakeholders"; "Providing training and resources...empowers users to effectively utilize the open data"	"Workshops and collaboration...ongoing reflection and collaboration"; "Workshop in Aachen...to further discuss and solidify these ideas"	Teams across subsidiaries can "work together more effectively" with shared data access	Research institutions requiring FAIR principles; Technical capacity exists but integration costly and time-consuming

<p>9. Stakeholder Alignment and Incentives</p>	<p>Need for "concrete demonstration...to people that have more influence in the company"; "Still in a very immature state"; External validation through DATAMITE helps "attract more interest from...higher level, employees and directors"; Comparison with "other streams of consultants...PwC...talking about maturity models"</p>	<p>"Enabler or facilitator for other companies and institutions"; "View their role as providing the infrastructure and data, with others taking the initiative to extract value"; Reaching users "beyond just their consortium partners"</p>	<p>"Strengthening partnerships with academic and research institutions"; "Leverage external expertise"; "Collaborative projects can lead to innovative applications...driving further societal benefits"</p>	<p>"Introducing these new ideas and tools to other departments and even to partner companies"; "Broader engagement is crucial for scaling the benefits"</p>	<p>Improved customer experience; Personalized services; Proactive support capabilities</p>	<p>"Data owners, such as farmers, are very reluctant to share any data, especially without incentives"; Need for "incentive to participate in data sharing"; "Trusted partners" in data spaces</p>
<p>10. Infrastructure and Accessibility</p>	<p>"Open data portal" planned to "satisfy a lot of the needs of the potential data consumers...without having the need to go ad hoc"; Internal pipelines for processing, review, publication; Move from</p>	<p>"European portals and open-access frameworks"; "Make data more widely accessible to a larger community, particularly to</p>	<p>Open data portal implementation</p>	<p>"Secure and flexible data-sharing solution among different companies within the group"</p>	<p>Centralized systems avoiding "duplicated efforts" across business units; Streamlined operations</p>	<p>"Agrego platform where data from various sources can be securely aggregated, managed, and shared"; "Data</p>

	"reactive to proactive data sharing"	researchers and institutions"				spaces— collaborative environments that facilitate data exchange between trusted partners"
11. Political and Strategic Alignment	EU data space participation being explored but "not clear...what data are we going to publish really in a data space and towards whom"; Ministry requirements for "development plan of every region"; "Electric vehicles, EV charge stations and...ever increasing demand for renewable energy sources"; Support for	Contributing to "broader environmental forecasting efforts, such as predicting floods, landslides, and other natural disasters"; Alignment with European meteorological data initiatives	Long-term vision with "clear goals and metrics for success"; Strategic alignment with organizational mission and societal needs	Leveraging European regulations "as strategic advantage"; "Not only protect the company's interests in Spain but also across the broader European market"	Competitive advantage in "data-driven market"	"European Strategy for Data (February 2020)...establish a Single Market for data"; "Common European Agriculture Data Space...support trustworthy data sharing"; "Partnership on agriculture

	"new players...to provide innovative solutions"					data...enhance sustainable agricultural production"; "Game changer in the sector for sharing the data"
--	---	--	--	--	--	--

Annex G: Preliminary Version of the DATAMITE Reflection Tool (‘DATAreflect’)

Instructions

What is DATAreflect?

DATAreflect offers organizations a practical and strategic tool to unlock the full potential of data sharing beyond just monetary gain. It helps users identify concrete, often overlooked benefits, such as reducing bureaucratic friction, creating new partnerships, improving organizational visibility, or strengthening their public image.

For companies unsure where to begin, DATAreflect serves as a low-threshold entry point into responsible data sharing, offering clear reflection categories to guide internal discussions and strategic planning. It supports informed decision-making by highlighting ecological, societal, and organizational impacts, allowing users to align data practices with broader goals and values. Whether used to enhance existing processes, develop new use cases, or shape policy thinking, DATAreflect empowers organizations to make data sharing meaningful, manageable, and beneficial from day one.

Why responsible data sharing?

Responsible data sharing is essential to ensure that the benefits of data use, such as innovation, transparency, and improved decision-making, are realized without compromising privacy, security, or ethical standards. It promotes trust among stakeholders by respecting individuals’ rights and addressing concerns about misuse, bias, or exploitation. Especially in business, research and policy contexts, responsible data sharing enables collaboration, reproducibility, and informed action while safeguarding sensitive information. By

establishing clear guidelines and accountability mechanisms, it helps balance openness with protection, ultimately supporting more equitable and sustainable outcomes.

How was DATAreflect developed?

DATAreflect has been developed within the DATAMITE project. DATAMITE is an initiative funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme (N° 101092989) fostering data monetisation, interoperability, trading and exchange.

DATAreflect specifically aims to integrate 'potentials of data sharing beyond economic value by researching and bringing in dimensions that are not only monetary'. Thus, it brings forward the potentials and side-effects of data sharing on an organizational as well as broader societal level.

DATAreflect is based on the foresight process conducted within the DATAMITE project (for details on methodology and results see D4.4). Here, ZSI developed reflection categories and validated them in dialogue with pilot partners (GIDITEK, OTE, E-REDES, HEDNO, WODR, CINECA). These categories build the foundation of DATAreflect.

Why use DATAreflect?

DATAreflect aims at engaging organizations and companies in reflecting on how their intention to share data may affect their own organization as well as their environment, ecologically or societally. DATAreflect provides companies with a starting point for broad reflection and strategic exploration of their aspirations to start or strengthen their activities of data sharing in a responsible way.

For this, organizations and companies can use DATAreflect in different ways:

- a. as a broad reflection tool to start thinking about impacts of data sharing in the organization's respective sector.
- b. as a strategic tool to systematically explore dimensions that could eventually be affected by data sharing activities of an organization.

- c. as a supplement in combination with existing internal processes of organizations (e.g. information management processes) to deepen the considerations on the impacts of data sharing.
- d. for reflection when developing different use cases of data sharing (e.g., Open Data, etc.) (for potential business models for different use cases see DATAMITE D4.1).
- e. to rethink and revise policy processes.

How to use DATAreflect?

DATAreflect is an easy-to-use tool (pdf graphic and/or clickable tool) that provides the user with categories and subcategories for reflecting on data sharing. For each subcategory, a reflecting question is proposed.

Organizations could start either by prioritizing categories and/or subcategories according to their mission and try to answer these questions, or by going through the catalogue of questions one by one, trying to find answers for their own organization.

Limitations of DATAreflect

DATAreflect is a flexible tool that helps organizations begin reflecting on responsible data sharing in a way that fits their specific context. The included categories and questions are not exhaustive, they were developed from literature and refined with DATAMITE project partners. Not all categories will be equally relevant; organizations are encouraged to focus on what matters most to their goals, sector, and data practices. Rather than a checklist, DATAreflect offers a starting point for strategic thinking, helping users explore the broader value of data sharing beyond monetization.

The Tool

Category	Subcategory	Explorative questions
Ecology	Contributing to ecological topics	How does (your) data sharing improve ecological issues? How might shared data contribute to more sustainable supply chains or reduce waste? Could your data sharing support circular economy models?
	Ecological impact of data sharing	What is the ecological impact of your data sharing to the environment? How do you address it?
Security	General	Does the data shared contain sensitive security-related information? If yes, what are the risks and potential impact of data being exposed?
	National level	In case of data breach and misuse, could your data lead to national security issues? If yes, how? What do you do/ could be done to prevent this?
	Resilience	How does data sharing affect your sector's ecosystem resilience (e.g., during natural disasters)?
	General	Does your data sharing relate to topics of scientific interest? In what way?

Scientific- Research	Data sharing for improving knowledge generation	Does data sharing improve scientific knowledge generation? How?
	Generating and promoting innovation	Does data sharing generate and promote innovation within your company? If yes, which innovation and on what level/in which division? In collaboration with whom (outside your company)?
Macro- economic	Shifting economic structure(s)	Does data sharing initiate shifts in economic structures in your sector?
	Increasing monopolization	Does data sharing lead to/increase monopolisation of data in your sector? How could this be prevented?
	Economic imbalance	Could data sharing initiate new or increase existing economic inequalities within your sector? How could this be prevented?
Customer & business	General	Does the data shared address customer and business related issues? Which ones? Are they related to direct or indirect monetization?
	Improved management and maximized (cost) efficiency	How can your data sharing improve management within your company? How can it maximise (cost) efficiency?
	Data loss and negative (business) consequences	In case of data breach and misuse, could your data lead to data loss and negative (business) consequences? If yes, how? What do you do/ could be done to prevent this?

	Digital divide	Could data sharing increase the digital divide with regard to your customers/users? How could this be prevented?
Policy	General	Does your data sharing relate to policy? If so, in what way?
	Effects of data sharing on governance and policy	Does your data sharing affect governance (i.e., political governance structures) and policy? How? In what regards (which fields, e.g. research policy...)?
	Data sharing for enhancing democracy and improving decision making	Does it affect policymaking and decision-making? If so how (e.g. by providing data,...)?
	Strengthening democracy through empowerment and participation	Who is able to participate in data sharing and the processes that data sharing are linked to? How can your data sharing democratise processes outside in your company? Is this needed (in what way)?
Ethics	General	Are there ethical issues related to your data sharing? Which ones? How do you address them?
	Fairness and Equity	Could your data sharing practices disproportionately impact certain groups or regions?
	Data sharing for the greater good	How does your data sharing contribute to the greater good? Do your customers (data providers) agree?

Privacy	General	What are privacy issues related to data sharing in your case?
	Strategies to deal with privacy challenges	How do you address privacy challenges related to your data? What is staff role name that conveys this information? Is there additional training needed?
	Confidentiality & Exposure	How can threats of confidentiality and exposure in sharing your data be minimized?
Cultural	General	How does (your) data sharing contribute to cultural aspects, e.g. in relation to cultural heritage etc.?
Organisational	General	Does your data sharing improve data generation, decision-making, promoting new ideas, enabling collaboration,...?
	Addressing legal and ethical concerns of individuals (researchers/employees)	Are there concerns of people responsible for data sharing? How can they be reassured? Is there additional training needed to deal with these issues?
	Considering individual efforts	Are there downsides to data sharing falling on the backs of individual people (e.g. individual researchers who have to make efforts to ensure data security)? Which ones? How can these unintended side-effects be addressed and countered?

Organisational	Increasing collaboration	Does data sharing enable collaboration within your company? If so, between which divisions? Has data sharing led to new collaborations or expanded your stakeholder network?
	Change in communication	How does data sharing change internal communication?
	Enhancing democratic decision making	How can your data sharing democratize processes within in your company? Is this needed (in what way)?
	Ensuring accountability and transparency	How does data sharing increase transparency in/of your company/ your process? How does data sharing increase the accountability of your company/ your process? Who is accountable for the shared data (and ensure compliance with regulation etc.) in this case (e.g., which staff role within the company or project)?
	Ensuring accessibility	How do you ensure that your data accessible? To/by whom?
	Digital divide	Could data sharing increase the digital divide between employees of your company? What could you do to avoid this?
	Data sharing for improving knowledge generation	Does data sharing improve knowledge generation within your company? How?

Organisational	Generating and promoting innovation	Does data sharing generate and promote new ideas within your company? Which ideas? On what level/in which division? In collaboration with whom (outside your company)?
	Change in reputation	Does sharing data improve your organization's standing in the public or within your industry? How has data sharing influenced your organization's external perception?
	Diversity and inclusion within the company	Is data sharing reinforcing or reducing inequality within your company?
	Potential misuse of data	How do you prevent misuse of data? Who is in control of data?
Societal	Bias	Do you check /reflect on the bias of your data? If so, how? How do you un-bias your data?
	De-contextualization and misinterpretation of data	Do you check whether your data is context dependent? Could your data be misinterpreted? How do you guide third parties to deal with your data?
	Potential misuse of data	Is there potential of misuse of your data? How would this affect society in a wider sense (e.g., if you are handling sensitive data)?
	Discrimination and Stigmatization	In case of data breach and misuse, could your data lead to discrimination and stigmatization? If yes, how? What do you do/ could be done to prevent this?

Societal	Social inequality	<p>Could your data sharing / using your data increase or manifest social inequality? If yes, how? What do you do/ could be done to prevent this?</p> <p>Who would be affected (which groups)?</p> <p>How can benefits of data sharing be fairly distributed among those who share (companies as well as customers/people who provide data)?</p>
	Increasing the digital divide in the public (incl. research)	<p>Could data sharing or using your data increase or manifest the digital divide, i.e. between knowledgeable and lay people? If yes, how?</p> <p>What do you do/ could be done to prevent this (if this is the aim)?</p> <p>Who would be affected (which groups)?</p>
	Increasing the digital divide in a global sense	<p>Could data sharing or using your data increase or manifest the digital divide globally (i.e., between more privileged and less privileged countries)? If yes, how?</p> <p>What do you do/ could be done to prevent this (if this is the aim)?</p> <p>Which countries could be affected?</p>
	Considering individual efforts	<p>How do you consider wider effects of efforts for data sharing falling on individuals?</p> <p>How can these efforts be incentiviced?</p>

Societal	Trust	<p>Is trust between sharing partners (sharing/receiving) an issue? If yes, how?</p> <p>How can trust be enhanced in the social processes underlying data sharing ('starting from the social')?</p> <p>How can trust in data sharing between them be enhanced?</p> <p>How can trust of data providers (e.g., customers) be ensured?</p> <p>How can sharing data enhance trust in your organization/ your project/ your process? Do you focus on this as well?</p>
	Gender and discrimination	<p>Who could be negatively affected by sharing data downstream? Are there adverse impacts related to gender, ethnicity etc.to be foreseen? What can be done to prevent them?</p>
	Willingness to share depends on recipients	<p>Who are data providers willing to share data with?</p> <p>How can you ensure that they remain willing to share data with you?</p>
Regulatory	<i>addressed in T4.5 (not part of the tool)</i>	